

Bangladesh University of Engineering & Technology

**Design of a 100 MTPD Sulfuric Acid and 9 MTPD Oleum
Production Plant**

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Statement of Academic Integrity

This project entitled “Design of a 100MTPD Sulfuric Acid Plant” is submitted to complete the course ChE 408: Process Design Sessional. It is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in the Department of Chemical Engineering at Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology. The work presented in this thesis has not been previously submitted for a degree at any other institution. We confirm that all the sources of information used in this design thesis have been acknowledged, and that all the calculations and results presented in this thesis are authentic and based on our own observation. No part of this report was intentionally copied or written with any such method that marks this report as plagiarized. Thorough rechecking were done to avoid undesiring flaws such as typing mistakes, spelling mistakes etc. Yet, no writing is flawless and accurate. We agree that due to my limitation of knowledge, there can be some mistakes in this report. We are extremely sorry for them. Any feedback about the project or any other academic advice is highly expected from the readers.

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1. PROJECT DEFINITION

A sulfuric acid plant with a capacity of 100 MTPD 98% sulfuric acid per day and 9 MTPD Oleum, including all offsite auxiliaries, utilities, and support facilities, is to be established in Dilarpur, Narsingdi, Bangladesh, with granular sulfur as feedstock.

Area Requirement: 25.60 km² (Estimated)

Operating Days: 330 Days

Shifts: 3

Shift Length: 8 hours

1.1 Raw Material Specification and Sources

1. Sulfur

- Type: Granular Refined Sulfur
- Price: \$230 – \$250 per MT
- Category: Bright Granular Elemental Sulfur
- Color: Yellow
- Density: 2.05 g/cm³
- Melting Point: 119°C
- Boiling Point: 444.6°C
- Specific Gravity: 1.015 (at 25°C)
- Molecular Weight: 32.066 g/mol
- Solubility: Insoluble in Water, slightly soluble in Alcohol
- Packing Details: 25kgs or 50kgs P.P bag
- Ash Max: 0.02%
- Fe Max: 0.0005%
- Carbon Disulfide Insoluble: 0.03%
- Sulfur: 99.95%
- Mesh: 200, 300, 325
- Moisture: 0.01%
- Acid Content: 0.01% D (H₂SO₄)
- Lining Quantity: 1 × 20 FCL = 22.5MT
- Source: Mahaveer Surfactants Private Limited, T Nagar, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Figure 1: Sulfur.

2. Catalyst

- Catalyst Name: Vanadium Pentoxide
- Chemical Formula: V_2O_5
- Price: \$18140 per MT
- Grade: Industrial
- Color: Yellow
- Purity: 98%
- Density: 3.36 g/cm^3
- Molecular Weight: 181.88 g/mol
- Category: Powdered, Adhesives, Antioxidants, Surfactant
- Solubility: Insoluble in Water, slightly soluble in Alcohol
- Packing Details: 25kgs bag
- Source: Forbes Pharmaceutical, Mumbai, Maharashtra

3. Air

- Composition: $N_2 = 79\%$
 $O_2 = 21\%$
- Source: Environment

4. Water

- Source: Meghna River
- Water Quality Index: 0.211
- pH: Around 6.85
- Temperature: 19.1 to 19.6°C
- BOD: 1.0 to 7.0 mg/L
- DO: 4.7 to 8.1 mg/L
- COD: Around 125 mg/L
- Hardness: 94 to 126 mg/L
- TDS: 113 to 197 mg/L

Figure 2: Catalyst.

1.2 Product Specifications

The sulfuric acid produced by this plant will conform to the following specifications:

Concentration: Specifically, 98.0% H₂SO₄ by weight but this plant can produce different concentrations of sulfuric acid according to customers demand like 93% or 95% can also be produced.

Other contents in the acid:

- Free SO₃. less than .5%
- Iron - Less than 5 ppm.
- Arsenic- Less than 1 ppm.
- Chloride- less than 0.002%
- Lead – less than 0.5 ppm
- Residue on ignition- less than 0.02%

Appearance: Clear and colorless liquid, free from visible suspended solids with a boiling point of 337° C.

Specific Gravity: 1.84 g/cm³ at 25°C.

The produced sulfuric acid is a strong acid with a very low pH and should be stored in appropriate corrosion-resistant materials to maintain its quality.

1.3 Utilities and Sources

Cooling Water

Water Type - Demineralized

pH Range - 6.4 – 6.8

Supply Temperature - Ambient +15°C

Microbiological Control - Regular biocide treatment

Pressure Differential - Less than acid pressure

Steam

In a sulfuric acid plant, we typically need steam with three different categories. The steam is generated from the process itself. No external steam is needed in the process. The specification of the three types of required steams to run a contact process are,

High pressure steam

Pressure - 600–900 psig

Temperature - Up to 400°C

Usage - Turbogenerators, large equipment drives

Steam Quality - Superheated or saturated

Medium pressure steam

Pressure - 150–250 psig

Temperature - Up to 204°C

Usage - Process heating, acid dilution

Steam Quality - Saturated

Low pressure steam

Pressure - ~50 psig

Temperature - ~149°C

Usage - Auxiliary heating, dilution

Steam Quality – Saturated

Instrument Air

Pressure - 7 bar

Dew Point - $\leq -40^{\circ}\text{C}$ (at operating pressure)

Oil Content - $\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$

Particle Size - Maximum solid particle size: 1 micron

Concentration of solid particles - $\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$

Air Temperature - Below 40°C

Process Air

Pressure - 7 bar

Dew Point - $\leq -40^\circ\text{C}$ (at operating pressure)

Oil Content - $\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$

Particle Size - Maximum solid particle size: 1 micron

Concentration of solid particles - $\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$

Air Temperature - Below 40°C

Electricity

Huge amount of electricity is required to run a sulfuric acid production plant. It is used to run blowers, fans, pumps, cooling system, electric heaters of the process. Additionally, electricity is required to run offices, DCS sections and even street lights insight the plant. Plant has its own power plant as a secondary source of electricity, and it can use electricity from the national grid as a primary source.

2. MARKET SURVEY

2.1 Description of Sulfuric Acid

Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), often referred to as the "king of chemicals," is one of the most important and widely used industrial chemicals in the world. It is a highly corrosive, dense, and oily liquid with strong acidic properties. Due to its versatility, it plays a crucial role in various industries, including fertilizer production, petroleum refining, wastewater treatment, and chemical manufacturing.

Key Properties of H_2SO_4

- Chemical Formula: H_2SO_4
- Molar Mass: 98.079 g/mol
- Appearance: Colorless to slightly yellow viscous liquid
- Odor: Odorless (pure form)
- Density: $\sim 1.84 \text{ g/cm}^3$ (concentrated form)
- Boiling Point: $\sim 337 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (concentrated)
- Solubility: Highly soluble in water (releases significant heat—exothermic reaction)

2.2 Uses and Applications of Sulfuric Acid

Sulfuric acid is an incredibly versatile and widely used chemical with applications spanning numerous industries and even some household uses. It's often called the "king of chemicals" due to its extensive applications and high production volume worldwide, which can even serve as an indicator of a nation's industrial strength.

Figure 3: percentage of uses of Sulfuric acid in different sectors.

By far the largest amount of sulfuric acid is used to make phosphoric acid, used, in turn, to make the phosphate fertilizers.(Phosphoric Acid, n.d.) It is widely used in metal processing for example in the manufacture of copper (Copper, n.d.) and the manufacture of zinc (Zinc, n.d.) and in cleaning the surface of steel sheet, known as 'pickling', prior to it being covered in a thin layer of tin, used to make cans for food.

It is also used to make caprolactam, which is converted into polyamide 6 and in the manufacture of titanium dioxide, used, for example, as a pigment.(Titanium Dioxide, n.d.)

Amongst its many other uses is in the manufacture of hydrofluoric acid (Hydrogen Fluoride, n.d.) and phenol with propanone (Phenol, n.d.) all of which are used in many industries. Other notable uses are in battery making, cleaning agents, dehydrating agents in laboratory settings and textile and paper industries.

2.3 Application of Sulfuric Acid in Industries

Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) is an incredibly versatile and widely used chemical with applications spanning numerous industries and even some household uses. It's often called the "king of chemicals" due to its extensive applications and high production volume worldwide, which can even serve as an indicator of a nation's industrial strength.

Here's a breakdown of its key uses and applications

1. Fertilizer Production

The largest single use of sulfuric acid is in the production of phosphate fertilizers such as superphosphate of lime and ammonium phosphate. It's used to process phosphate rock into phosphoric acid, a key ingredient in these fertilizers.

It's also used to produce ammonium sulphate, another important nitrogen and sulphur-containing fertilizer, often as a byproduct of other industrial processes.

2. Chemical Manufacturing

Sulfuric acid is a crucial reagent in the synthesis of a vast array of other chemicals, including:

Other inorganic acids like hydrochloric acid (HCl), nitric acid (HNO_3), and phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4).

Sulphate salts used in various industrial processes. Some of the examples:

- Synthetic detergents.
- Dyes and pigments.
- Explosives like TNT.
- Pharmaceuticals.
- Synthetic fibers like rayon.
- Plastics and resins.

3. Metal Processing

Pickling: Sulfuric acid is used to clean the surface of metals like steel, iron, and copper to remove rust, scale, and other impurities before further processing, such as electroplating with tin or zinc (as in the production of food cans).

Extraction and Purification: It's used in the extraction of metals from their ores, such as in copper smelting and zinc manufacturing.

Electroplating: It forms part of the electrolyte solution in some electroplating processes.

4. Petroleum Refining

Sulfuric acid is used as a catalyst in various refining processes, including the alkylation of isobutane with isobutylene to produce high-octane gasoline components like isooctane.

It's also used to remove impurities from crude oil.

5. Water and Wastewater Treatment

Sulfuric acid is used to adjust the pH of water, making it suitable for drinking or industrial use.

It helps in the removal of solid particles and impurities during wastewater treatment.

6. Battery Electrolyte:

Dilute sulfuric acid is the electrolyte in lead-acid batteries, commonly found in vehicles. It facilitates the flow of electrons between the lead plates to generate electricity.

7. Industrial Cleaning Agent:

Due to its strong acidic and dehydrating properties, concentrated sulfuric acid is a key ingredient in some industrial-strength cleaning products, such as drain openers, where it can dissolve grease, hair, and tissue paper. It's also used to clean metal surfaces.

8. Other Applications:

Paper Production: Used in the production of wood pulp and the manufacture of aluminium sulphate, which is used in paper sizing.

Mining and Metallurgy: Used in leaching processes to extract valuable metals from ores.

Textile Industry: Used in the manufacturing of rayon.

Agriculture (direct use): In some cases, dilute sulfuric acid is used to acidify alkaline soils to improve plant growth or as a defoliating agent for crops like potatoes before harvesting.

Laboratory Reagent: Used extensively in chemical laboratories for various analytical and synthetic purposes.

Production of other sulfates: Used to manufacture various sulfate salts like aluminum sulfate (used in water treatment and papermaking) and copper sulfate (used as a fungicide and in electroplating).

The diverse properties of sulfuric acid, including its strong acidity, dehydrating capabilities, and oxidizing potential at higher concentrations, make it indispensable in so many different chemical and industrial processes. However, it's crucial to remember that sulfuric acid is a highly corrosive and hazardous substance that requires careful handling and storage.

2.4 Global Perspective

2.4.1 Bangladesh Perspective

Sulfuric acid is widely used in many chemical industries in Bangladesh, including fertilizer production, manufacturing other acids like hydrochloric acid and nitric acids. Sulfuric acid is mainly used in the production of fertilizer. Bangladesh produces approximately 10 lakh (1 million) tonnes of urea fertilizer annually. The country also produces about one lakh (100,000) tonnes of TSP fertilizer and this demand is increasing day by day. With the current growing demand, production of fertilizer is also increasing and so the sulfuric acid. This increasing demand played a great role in the industrialization of sulfuric acid. Many industries were formed to manufacture sulfuric acid. Name of these industries are-

1. WATA Chemicals
2. Torsha Chemical Industries Ltd
3. Stellar Exports

However, the production capacity of these industries cannot cope with the growing demand and so there is always a deficiency in production. To adjust the demand, sulfuric acid is imported from

various countries every year. In 2023, Bangladesh imported \$494k of Sulfuric Acid, becoming the 98th largest importer of Sulfuric Acid (out of 186) in the world. During the same year, Sulfuric Acid were the 904th most imported product (out of 1,162) in Bangladesh. In 2023, Bangladesh imported from: India (\$418k)(India (IND) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners | The Observatory of Economic Complexity, n.d.), Japan (\$63k)(Japan (JPN) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners | The Observatory of Economic Complexity, n.d.), China (\$10.7k)(China (CHN) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners, n.d.), Germany-y (\$1.19k) (Germany (DEU) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners | The Observatory of Economic Complexity, n.d.), and Denmark (\$673) (Denmark (DNK) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners | The Observatory of Economic Complexity, n.d.).

The fastest growing origins for Sulfuric Acid imports in Bangladesh between 2022 and 2023 were: India (\$245k), and Denmark (\$590).

Figure 5: Sulfuric acid import data from various countries.

2.4.2 Global Perspective

The global sulfuric acid market size accounted for USD 15.56 billion in 2024 and is expected to be worth around USD 33.90 billion by 2034, at a CAGR of 8.1% from 2024 to 2034. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Figure 6: Sulfuric acid global market size from 2023 from 2034.

(Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Figure 7: Sulfuric acid market size according to region.

The Covid-19 pandemic has negatively impacted the market in North America, Europe, Asia Pacific, Latin America, Middle East & Africa and the demand for the product decreased tremendously due to the disruption of supply chains and restrictions on transportation worldwide in 2020. Several companies operating in the automotive, paper & pulp, metal, petroleum, and other

industries have incurred enormous losses, which led to a decline in the demand for the products manufactured using sulfuric acid. But from 2021, the demand again started growing and by 2030, the demand will grow more.

2.5 Future Prospects of Sulfuric Acid Market

2.5.1 Current Uses and Demand in Bangladesh

Based on the context of Bangladesh, the primary industries likely consuming sulfuric acid are fertilizer production and other industrial applications. Fertilizer production is a key sector in Bangladesh, utilizing sulfuric acid in phosphate fertilizer production. For more nitrogen-based fertilizer in Bangladesh to achieve food automation, implying a significance in agricultural sector. Other potential uses include chemical manufacturing, textile processing, and metal treatment, though specific data for Bangladesh may be limited.

The expected Demand for H_2SO_4 will depend on consumption of H_2SO_4 . From the graph, we can find that the expected consumption is increasing day by day. Estimated import data from 2010 to 2030 shows that the rate is increasing for a few hundred thousand dollars in the international market every year, but export data is not as much increasing. If we can produce more in future, we may export more. With this goal our plant is designed to produce more sulfuric acid than needed as our plant will produce around 100Metric ton per day, which is more than two times our consumption. As a result, we will be able to export more and more.

Table 1: Different H_2SO_4 manufacturers Annual Production Capacity

Name of Plant	Annual Production Capacity (Metric Tons)	Reference
Wata Chemicals Ltd.	48,000	<u>Wata Chemicals Ltd.</u>
Kalurghat Sulfuric Acid Plant (Proposed)	45,000	<u>ResearchGate</u>
Crescent Chemical Ltd.	58,400	<u>Sulphuric Acid on the Web</u>
Chittagong TSP Complex (TSP-2 Unit)	146,000	<u>World Bank Document</u>
Ashuganj Fertilizer and Chemical Company Limited	Not specified	<u>Wikipedia</u>

2.5.2 Factors Influencing Future Demand in Bangladesh

Agricultural growth is a significant driver, as increased activity to achieve food automation will likely increase demand for fertilizers and sulfuric acid. Industrial development in Bangladesh has the potential to increase demand across various sectors.

2.5.3 Extrapolation or Trend Analysis of Expected Demand

Specific demand forecast data for sulfuric acid in Bangladesh is not available within our current resources. Based on anticipated agricultural growth and industrial development, there is a likely increasing trend in demand. This trend is justified by the need for food security (driving fertilizer demand) and the requirements of a developing industrial sector.

2.6 Market Price Trend

2.6.1 Price Trend of Sulfuric Acid Production

Specific historical and current price data for sulfuric acid in Bangladesh are not available within our current resources. Generally global factors influencing sulfuric acid prices include:

Raw material costs (sulfur): According to Volza's Bangladesh Import data, Bangladesh imported 73 shipments of Sulfur during Oct 2023 to Sep 2024 (TTM). These imports were supplied by 46 foreign exporters to 43 Bangladesh buyers, marking a growth rate of -1% compared to the preceding twelve months. Within this period, in Sep 2024 alone, Bangladesh imported 10 Sulfur shipments. This marks a year-on-year growth of 900% compared to Sep 2023, and a 233% sequential increase from Aug 2024. Bangladesh imports most of its Sulfur from India, China, and Russia.

Table 2: Estimated Price Range of H₂SO₄.

Year Range	Estimated Price Range (USD/Metric Ton)
2010-13	80 - 150
2014-17	90 – 180
2018-20	120 – 250
2021-23	150 – 350

2024-27	180 - 400
2028-30	200 - 500

Energy prices: Depends on which process we choose and which fuel and resources we use.

Current electricity costs for industrial users in Bangladesh are 7.4-12Tk/Unit. Fuel costs (natural gas, coal, etc.) are on an average 14.75Tk per m³ of NG, if the sulfuric acid plant requires direct fuel for heating or other processes.

Transportation costs: Depends on our country's current situation. This includes different types of reasons like seasonal resistance, time and geographical conditions of our country and many others.

2.6.2 Product Price Trends according to different Concentrations

The standard “Contact Process” will include different concentrations of products according to our need. Buyers specify the concentration they need (generally 93%, 98% oleum). Producers adjust prices accordingly. The price trend of sulfuric acid is not linearly related to its concentration because it is just one of the criteria that affect the price where the higher the concentration the higher the value. Producing higher concentrations requires additional energy and processing, adding to the cost. Generally, more concentrated sulfuric acid is more valuable per unit mass. This is because: It contains less water, reducing transportation costs per unit of active H₂SO₄.

Some applications require specific concentration, and it costs more to produce those.

2.7 Distribution of Customers and Seasonal Variations in Demand

Sulfuric acid is mainly distributed to different chemical industries to run their fertilizer plants, petroleum refineries, metal processing plants and many more. It is also used in textile industries, raw materials production of textile, battery production and some other chemical manufacturing. (Welcome to Stellar Exports, Stellar Exports Is an India Based Company Engaged in Export Import Sourcing of Chemicals, Minerals, Food Products , Pharma & Agro Products., n.d.) Apart from all these places, sulfuric acid is also illegally distributed to the people in many places of the country. Poor monitoring of government is the main reason for such mismanagements. The most

famous retail shops of the country for sulfuric acid are located in Tantibazar, Old Dhaka. Sulfuric acids are also sold at Armanitola and Hatkhola of Old Dhaka. (Pay Tk 30, Buy a Pound of Acid, 2008, p. 3) However, this amount is very negligible in comparison to the industrial distribution.

The major consumer chemical plants of sulfuric acid are mentioned below.

Fertilizer Industries: The currently running and most prominent fertilizer industries in Bangladesh are Ashuganj Fertilizer and Chemical Company Limited, Chittagong Urea Fertilizer Limited, Ghorasal Polash Urea Fertilizer Public Limited Company, Karnaphuli Fertilizer Company Limited and Shahjalal Fertiliser Factory. The location and daily production rate of fertilizer is given in the table below. It was made using the latest available data on internet. Yet, the latest modifications which wasn't notified to the internet aren't considered due to lack of availability.

Table 3: Largest fertilizer industries of Bangladesh.

Name of the Fertilizer Industries	Location	Daily Production (Metric Ton/day)	References
Ashuganj Fertilizer and Chemical Company Limited	Brahmmanbaria	1100	(আশুগঞ্জ সার কারখানা, 2020)
Chittagong Urea Fertilizer Limited	Chittagong	1000	(Industries Get New Life for LNG, 2025)
Ghorasal Polash Urea Fertilizer Public Limited Company	Narshingdi	750	(Missed Deadline Makes Ghorashal Fertiliser a Drag on State Cooffers, 2023)
Karnaphuli Fertilizer Company Limited and Shahjalal Fertiliser Factory	Chittagong	1725-1500	(“Karnaphuli Fertilizer Company Limited,” 2025)
Shahjalal Fertiliser Factory	Sylhet	1500	(Production at Shahjalal Fertiliser Company Suspended for 2 Months, n.d.)

Textile Industries: The textile industries require a high amount of sulfuric acid in the pretreatment stage, scouring, pH neutralization, finishing of wool and synthetic fibers, wastewater treatment, cationic dye fixation and many more. The location and the daily production comparison are mentioned below.

Table 4: Largest textile industries of Bangladesh.

Name of the Textile Industry	District	Daily Production Capacity	Sources
Beximco Textiles (BexTex)	Gazipur	100,000 yards of finished fabric	(www.bextex.net, n.d.)
Square Textiles Ltd.	Gazipur	30,000 kg of yarn	(About Square Textiles Ltd., n.d.)
DBL Group	Gazipur	125 tons of knit fabric	(Knitting, n.d.)
Envoy Textiles Ltd.	Mymensingh	54 million yards of denim fabric annually	(Envoy Textiles to Invest in Sustainable Waste Fabric Recycling The Business Standard, n.d.)

Sulfuric acid is also used in metal processing industries. The data of some of the prominent metal processing industries are given below.

Table 5: Largest metal manufacturing industries in Bangladesh.

Name of the Industry	District	Annual Production Capacity (Metric Tonnes)	Sources
Bangladesh Steel Re-Rolling Mills (BSRM)	Chattogram	2.4 million	(Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study The Daily Star, n.d.)

Abul Khair Steel (AKS)	Chattogram	1.5 million	(Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study The Daily Star, n.d.)
GPH Ispat	Chattogram	0.8 million	(Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study The Daily Star, n.d.)
Kabir Steel Re-Rolling Mills (KSRM)	Chattogram	0.8 million	(Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study The Daily Star, n.d.)
Bashundhara Multi-Steel Industries Ltd. (BMSIL)	Chattogram	3.0 million (projected by 2025)	("Bashundhara Group," 2025)
Anwar Ispat	Munshiganj	0.3 million	(Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study The Daily Star, n.d.)

Analyzing the mentioned data, we can reach at a conclusion that the highest sulfuric acid consuming region in the country is Chittagong. Moreover, districts near Dhaka city, i.e., Gazipur, Munshiganj, Narshingdi also have a moderate Acid consumption demand. The following chart summarizes the demand analysis of sulfuric acid within the country.

Figure 8: Ranking of different regions in order of the demand of sulfuric acid in Bangladesh.

The overall demand of sulfuric acid throughout the year doesn't vary much throughout the year according to weather. Yet, the demand of fertilizer varies throughout the year. Which may have a slight impact on the demand of sulfuric acid. Bangladesh primarily has three cropping seasons: Boro (January–May), Aus (March–August), Aman (July–December). Before the cropping periods of these three seasons, the fertilizer demand stays at peak, which causes an uprise in the demand of sulfuric acid. During the last six month of the year, the fertilizer demand is generally lower than the first six months of the year. However, if we count the opportunity of exportation, the demand of sulfuric acid throughout the year doesn't show much fluctuations throughout a year.

2.8 Product Specification of Sulfuric Acid

The specification of industry grade sulfuric acid is provided by ASTM International, BIS (Bureau of Indian Standards), ECHA (European Chemical Agency) and NIST (National Institute of Standard and Technology). In Bangladesh, industries typically prioritize the ASTM international grade of the product (ASTM E223-08). Hence, we are considering it for the specification of sulfuric acid. (E223 Standard Test Methods for Analysis of Sulfuric Acid, n.d.)

Table 6: Product specification.

Property	Specification
Concentration	98% (weight basis)
Appearance	Clear, colorless to slightly yellow liquid
Specific Gravity	1.84 g/cm ³
Free SO ₃ Content	≤ 0.5%
Iron (Fe) Content	≤ 5 ppm
Arsenic (As) Content	≤ 1 ppm
Chloride (Cl ⁻) Content	≤ 0.002%
Lead (Pb) Content	≤ 0.5 ppm
Residue on Ignition	≤ 0.02%
Colour (APHA/Hazen)	≤ 20
Boiling Point	~337°C
Packaging Compatibility	HDPE drums, carbon steel tanks (internally coated)

2.9 Justification of the Production and Production Size

2.9.1 Bangladesh's Strategic Imperative: Establishing Sulfuric Acid Production Plant

Bangladesh currently faces a significant reliance on imported sulfuric acid, with imports valued at \$494,000 in 2023, positioning the country as a notable global importer. The average import price in 2024 was reported at \$270 per ton, marking a 32% increase from the previous year. This dependence persists despite the compound's critical role across multiple key sectors including fertilizer production, chemical manufacturing, metal processing, petroleum refining, water treatment, battery manufacturing, and textiles. Imports, particularly from India, are on an upward trend, while exports remain negligible at just \$10,500 in 2022. This stark imbalance highlights a domestic supply shortfall that leaves Bangladesh vulnerable to global market volatility. (The Observatory of Economic Complexity, n.d.)

Relying on foreign sources for such a vital industrial input exposes the country to risks such as international price fluctuations, supply chain disruptions due to geopolitical tensions or global events, and a steady outflow of valuable foreign currency. In this context, establishing a domestic sulfuric acid production facility emerges as a strategic necessity.

Local production would offer numerous benefits. First and foremost, it would ensure a more secure and stable supply chain for Bangladesh's vital industries, insulating them from unpredictable international dynamics. It would also help reduce the \$494,000 currently spent on imports each year, conserving much-needed foreign exchange reserves. Additionally, a domestic plant would create direct employment opportunities in operations, engineering, and management, while also generating indirect jobs in related sectors such as transportation, logistics, and raw material supply.

The bar chart compares the Sulfuric Acid market in Bangladesh to the top 5 major economies in Asia for 2027, revealing India as the dominant market with an "Exponential" growth of 17.44%, followed by China's "Growing" market at 5.08%. Bangladesh's "Stable" market, with a value of 4.07%, is similar in size to Korea's 4.08% but significantly smaller than India's, while Japan and Australia exhibit considerably smaller and stable markets at 1.26% and 0.15%, respectively. In the Asia region, the Sulfuric Acid market in Bangladesh is projected to expand at a stable growth rate of 4.07% by 2027. The largest economy is China, followed by India, Japan, Australia and South Korea. (Bangladesh Sulfuric Acid Market (2025-2031) | Trends & Revenue, n.d.)

Figure 9: Comparative Analysis of Sulfuric Acid Market in Bangladesh and Major Asian Economies (2027). (Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 | Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study | The Daily Star, n.d.)

Beyond immediate economic advantages, localizing sulfuric acid production would foster the development of national expertise in chemical manufacturing, contributing to broader industrial growth. With sustained investment and capacity building, Bangladesh could transition from being a net importer to a competitive regional exporter. This shift would position the country to tap into the growing global sulfuric acid market, projected to reach \$35.72 billion by 2029, thereby enhancing its international trade footprint and strengthening overall economic resilience.

The following graph forecasts a steadily accelerating growth rate for the Bangladesh sulfuric acid market between 2025 and 2029, starting at 3.61% in 2025 and progressively increasing to 5.25% by 2029, indicating a strengthening demand driven by macroeconomic factors and market trends. This projected growth presents a favorable outlook for establishing a sulfuric acid plant in Dhaka, suggesting an expanding market to cater to and potentially necessitating considerations for future expansion to capitalize on the increasing demand from key consuming industries in Bangladesh. In the Asia region, the Sulfuric Acid market in Bangladesh is projected to expand at a stable growth rate of 4.07% by 2027. The largest economy is China, followed by India, Japan, Australia and South Korea.

Figure 10: Trend Analysis and Forecast of Bangladesh Sulfuric Acid Market Growth. (2025-2029) (Bangladesh Steel Industry Top Producers 2024 | Four Steelmakers Control 53% of the Market: Study | The Daily Star, n.d.)

2.10 Justification of the Proposed Production Capacity

Using the 2023 average import price of sulfuric acid, the estimated import volume for 2023 can be calculated to be around 2691 metric tons approximately **2700** metric tons per year. As the demand is increasing, the import volume will also increase to some extent. Assuming a moderate compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6%, based on past trends and projected industrial expansion, Bangladesh's sulfuric acid import demand in 2030 is projected to reach approximately 4,000 metric tons per year. This demand underscores the need for strategic investments in local production facilities to reduce dependency on imports, ensure cost stability, and support expanding industrial sectors. Furthermore, due to increasing market demand and the emergence of new application areas for sulfuric acid, the actual demand could surpass this projection, highlighting an even greater urgency for capacity enhancement and domestic production development. So we are designing our plant to produce around **33000** metric tons of sulfuric acid per year or **100** metric tons per day. Thus, there will be a product surplus of around **29000** metric tons after meeting the annual national demand. With increasing international demand on mind, we target to export our product as well.

3. DESIGN BASIS

3.1 Climate Condition

In Narsingdi, the wet season is hot, oppressive, and mostly cloudy and the dry season is warm and mostly clear. Over the course of the year, the temperature typically varies from 56°F to 92°F and is rarely below 51°F or above 98°F.

3.1.1 Average Temperatures in Narsingdi

The hot season lasts for 3.8 months, from March 13 to July 7, with an average daily high temperature above 89°F. The hottest month of the year in Narsingdi is June, with an average high of 90°F and low of 80°F.

The cool season lasts for 1.6 months, from December 14 to February 2, with an average daily high temperature below 80°F. The coldest month of the year in Narsingdi is January, with an average low of 57°F and high of 77°F.

Figure 11: The daily average (red line) and low (blue line) temperature. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Average	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
High	77°F	83°F	89°F	92°F	91°F	90°F	89°F	89°F	89°F	88°F	85°F	79°F
Temp.	66°F	72°F	80°F	84°F	84°F	85°F	84°F	84°F	84°F	82°F	76°F	69°F
Low	57°F	62°F	70°F	75°F	78°F	80°F	80°F	80°F	79°F	76°F	68°F	60°F

Figure 12: The summary of figure-1 dictating highest temperature, lowest temperature and average temperature of each month of Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

3.1.2 Precipitation

A wet day is one with at least 0.04 inches of liquid or liquid-equivalent precipitation. The chance of wet days in Narsingdi varies very significantly throughout the year.

The wetter season lasts 6.0 months, from April 14 to October 12, with a greater than 38% chance of a given day being a wet day. The month with the most wet days in Narsingdi is July, with an average of 22.7 days with at least 0.04 inches of precipitation.

Figure 13: The percentage of days in which various types of precipitation are observed, excluding trace quantities: rain alone (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

The drier season lasts 6.0 months, from October 12 to April 14. The month with the fewest wet days in Narsingdi is December, with an average of 0.8 days with at least 0.04 inches of precipitation.

Among wet days, we distinguish between those that experience rain alone. The month with the most days of rain alone in Narsingdi is July, with an average of 22.7 days. Based on this categorization, the most common form of precipitation throughout the year is rain alone, with a peak probability of 74% on July 31.

Table 7: Possible number of rainy days in Narsingdi in different months. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Days of	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Rain	1.2d	2.4d	5.6d	12.2d	18.5d	20.7d	22.7d	21.7d	18.7d	9.8d	1.8d	0.8d

3.2 Meteorological condition

3.2.1 Wind Speed

The wide-area hourly average wind vector (speed and direction) at 10 meters above the ground. The wind experienced at any given location is highly dependent on local topography and other factors, and instantaneous wind speed and direction vary more widely than hourly averages. The average hourly wind speed in Narsingdi experiences significant seasonal variation over the course of the year. The windier part of the year lasts for 5.4 months, from March 24 to September 6, with average wind speeds of more than 7.1 miles per hour. The windiest month of the year in Narsingdi is July, with an average hourly wind speed of 9.6 miles per hour. The calmer time of year lasts for 6.6 months, from September 6 to March 24. The calmest month of the year in Narsingdi is November, with an average hourly wind speed of 4.3 miles per hour.

Figure 14: Average wind speed in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Table 8: Average of mean hourly wind speeds in meter per hour in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Wind Speed (mph)	5.0	5.5	6.7	8.3	8.4	9.4	9.6	8.3	6.3	4.6	4.3	4.5
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3.2.2 Wind direction

The wind is most often from the west for 3.3 weeks, from February 18 to March 13, with a peak percentage of 38% on March 7. The wind is most often from the south for 6.9 months, from March 13 to October 11, with a peak percentage of 88% on July 9. The wind is most often from the north for 4.2 months, from October 11 to February 18, with a peak percentage of 58% on January 1.

3.2.3 Relative Humidity

Narsingdi experiences extreme seasonal variation in the perceived humidity. Unlike temperature, which typically varies significantly between night and day, dew point tends to change more slowly,

so while the temperature may drop at night, a muggy day is typically followed by a muggy night. Narsingdi experiences extreme seasonal variation in the perceived humidity.

Figure 15: Wind direction in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

The muggier period of the year lasts for 8.8 months, from March 3 to November 27, during which time the comfort level is muggy, oppressive, or miserable at least 26% of the time.

The month with the fewest muggy days in Narsingdi is January, with 0.7 days that are muggy or

Table 9: The percentage of time spent at various humidity comfort levels, categorized by dew point.

Figure 16: Humidity comfort levels in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

worse.

3.2.4 Rainfall

The rainy period of the year lasts for 9.8 months, from February 9 to December 1, with a sliding 31-day rainfall of at least 0.5 inches. The month with the most rain in Narsingdi is July, with an average rainfall of 10.1 inches.

The rainless period of the year lasts for 2.2 months, from December 1 to February 9. The month with the least rain in Narsingdi is January, with an average rainfall of 0.3 inches.

Figure 17: Average monthly rainfall in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Table 10: Average rainfall in different months in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Rainfall	0.3"	0.6"	1.6"	4.2"	8.1"	10.1"	10.1"	8.5"	7.5"	4.0"	1.0"	0.3"

3.2.5 Water Temperature

Narsingdi is located near a large body of water (e.g., ocean, sea, or large lake). This section reports on the wide-area average surface temperature of that water.

The average water temperature experiences some seasonal variation over the course of the year.

The time of year with warmer water lasts for 5.3 months, from May 11 to October 19, with an average temperature above 80°F. The month of the year in Narsingdi with the warmest water is June, with an average temperature of 82°F.

The time of year with cooler water lasts for 2.8 months, from December 17 to March 9, with an average temperature below 71°F. The month of the year in Narsingdi with the coolest water is January, with an average temperature of 68°F.

Figure 18: Average water temperature in Narsingdi. (Sulfuric Acid Market Size to Reach USD 33.90 Bn by 2034, n.d.)

Table 11: Average temperature in Narsingdi in different months. [30]

Water	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Temperature	68°F	68°F	72°F	76°F	80°F	82°F	82°F	82°F	82°F	80°F	76°F	71°F

3.3 Geological Data

A perfect chemical plant location should have easy access to the raw material sources and be near consumer industries. This helps reduce transportation costs for both raw materials and finished products. We should also consider the land price of the area, availability of manpower, utilities, and community resources, i.e., schools, hospitals etc. Since the main raw material of this plant, sulfur is mostly imported, it would be suitable to establish the plant near a river port.

3.3.1 Site Plant Location

Considering all these criteria, the suitable location for our chemical plant would be at Dilarpur, Narsingdi. Dilarpur is an inland island area in the Meghna river located in Narsingdi district. This area has a high elevation from the sea level, cheap land price, easy access to the required utility and raw materials to establish a sulfuric acid plant using contact method.

Figure 19: Map of the site.

3.3.2 Site Characteristics

The area of the Dilarpur inland island is 25.6 km² and the total perimeter of this land is 23.28 km. It is very suitable to establish the plant, and also expand it to a handsome level. All the perimeter of this land has the facility of access of the Meghna river. We have the Narsingdi Launch Terminal near the location, which ensures that this route is suitable for lightering vessels to sail in this location. The location has parks, schools and other community resources to ensure the community need of the employees. The location of Narsingdi is a great solution for the raw materials and product transportation cost. The utilities of this plant require huge amount of water. The main three raw material of this industry are sulfur, water and air. Suitable air is available in this location. To manage the other two raw materials, we must establish the plant near a river. This strategy reduces the raw material transport and supply price to a optimum level. The textile industries located in Gazipur, Dhaka, Narsingdi region requires a very significant amount of sulfuric acid. Ashuganj Fertilizer & Chemical Company Limited (AFCCCL) located in Brahmanbaria, Ghorasal Polash Urea Fertilizer Public Limited Company located in Narsingdi also consumes high amount of sulfuric acid. Establishing the plant in this location will reduce the product transportation cost to all these plants. Thus, we can supply sulfuric acid to all these industries at a comparatively cheaper price. Moreover, frequent road and river transportation is available to the industries of Chittagong from this location. It is important to shift their interest in our plant from their previous supplier to establish the industry. Cheaper supply of quality product is the best motivation to achieve this goal.

3.3.3 Soil Characteristics and Soil Type

The region of Dilarpur belongs to the deep red brown terrace soil. They are characterized by their reddish-brown to yellow-brown color, strong to extreme acidity, and friable clay texture over deeply weathered, red-mottled Madhupur Clay. Typically, well to moderately well-drained, they are mainly classified as Ferric Alisols. (Bhuiyan et al., 1999) The soil classification of this region is Entisol. Entisols are soils of recent origin with minimal profile development, often lacking distinct horizons beyond an A-horizon. They form in areas where soil-forming processes are limited, such as floodplains, sand dunes, or steep slopes, and are characterized by their diversity in environmental settings and land use. (https://www.uidaho.edu/cals/soil-orders/entisols?utm_source=chatgpt.com) The area has clay loam type soil texture. The soil

porosity of this area varies from 41% to 50%. There is medium amount of organic matter available in this region. As mentioned before, the soil of this region is strongly acidic. No objection of salinity is available about this land. Despite being surrounded by river, this is a medium high land. This is not a forest area. Hence, no environmental restrictions are applicable on this land. (Islam et al., 2017)

Table 12: Soil carecteristics of the site.

Characteristics criteria	Characteristics	Reference
Soil Region	Deep red brown terrace soil region	(Entisols Soil & Water Systems University of Idaho, n.d.)
Soil Classification	Entisoil	(Entisols Soil & Water Systems University of Idaho, n.d.)
Soil Texture	Clay loam	(Entisols Soil & Water Systems University of Idaho, n.d.)
Soil Porosity	41% to 50%	(Islam et al., 2017)
Organic Matter	Medium amount	(Islam et al., 2017)
pH Characteristics	Strongly acidic	(Islam et al., 2017)
Salinity	N/A	(Islam et al., 2017)
Elevation	Medium high land	(Islam et al., 2017)

3.3.4 Topography and Seismic Condition

The land has a flat status with a constant elevation of 6-7m from the sea level. (Khan & Awal, 2009) The Seismic Zone Coefficient, Z represents the relative intensity of earthquake ground motion in a specific region. It is a key factor used in structural design calculations to determine the horizontal seismic force a structure must withstand. The value of Seismic Zone Coefficient is 0.2. The land area doesn't have a significant earthquake information. The magnitude of earthquake at the nearest area from the land is from 3.5 to 4.5. (Mahabub et al., 2020)

3.3.5 Justification and Limitations of the Sight

The region chosen in Narsingdi has the following benefits for which, it was chosen to construct the plant.

- **Easy Access to the Raw Materials:** Dilarpur is an inland island. It is completely surrounded by Meghna River. The Narsingdi Launch Ghat is very near the location, which confirms the easy movements of lightening vessels through the waterway near this land. Since our main raw material, sulfur is imported, we need frequent waterway near the sight. Moreover, the river is a good source of the raw materials of other utilities i.e., steam, drinking water, process water, etc.
- **Saving the Product Transportation Cost:** The region near Narsingdi, i.e., the plants of Dhaka, Gazipur, and Brahmanbaria (Ashuganj Fertilizer & Chemical Company Limited) has a high demand of sulfuric acid. Sulfuric acids can be supplied to these industries with a cheaper price. Moreover, due to an excellent waterway access, we can easily supply our product to Chittagong.
- **Cheap Land:** The land cost of Dilarpur is way cheaper than Chittagong or any other sight. Since the plant requires a good amount of land area, it is definitely an issue to consider. This is important for expansion of the plant for future.
- **Community Facility:** Dilarpur has a good number of parks, schools and markets in that region. This is important to consider the comfort of the employees.

The limitations of this sight are explained below:

- The land has strong acidic soil. This may increase the construction cost of the plant.

- Since the place is an inland island, there are chances of rise of the water level due to global warming in the future.
- The place is not a well reputed industrial area. This may take a while to grab the attention of all the stakeholders of this plant.

3.4 Raw Materials

3.4.1 Description

Raw Materials and Their Use in Sulfuric Acid Production

The production of sulfuric acid, specifically using the Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) process (which is the most common and efficient method), involves the following raw materials and their roles:

1. Sulfur:

- **Source:** Mahaveer Surfactants Private Limited, T Nagar, Chennai, India.
- **Role:** Sulfur is the primary raw material. It is burned with air to produce sulfur dioxide (SO₂).
- **Reaction:** $S(s) + O_2(g) \rightarrow SO_2(g)$

2. Air:

- **Source:** Environment.
- **Role:** Air provides the oxygen necessary for two key oxidation steps:
 1. Burning sulfur to sulfur dioxide.
 2. Oxidizing sulfur dioxide to sulfur trioxide (SO₃).

3. Catalyst (Vanadium Pentoxide – V₂O₅):

- **Source:** Forbes Pharmaceutical, Mumbai, India.
- **Role:** Vanadium Pentoxide acts as a catalyst to speed up the oxidation of sulfur dioxide to sulfur trioxide. This reaction is otherwise slow.
- **Reaction:** $2SO_2(s) + O_2(g) \rightarrow 2SO_3(g)$

4. Water:

- **Source:** Meghna River
- **Role:** Water is used in the absorption towers to absorb sulfur trioxide and convert it into sulfuric acid.

- **Reaction:** $\text{SO}_3(\text{g}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l}) \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(\text{l})$
- SO_3 is absorbed into sulfuric acid rather than water directly, to control the heat of reaction and prevent mist formation.

Use of Raw Materials (Such as for DCDA Process)

1. **Sulfur Burning:** Sulfur is burned in a furnace with air to produce sulfur dioxide (SO_2).
2. **Primary Catalytic Oxidation:** The SO_2 gas is mixed with more air and passed over a vanadium pentoxide catalyst in a converter. This converts a portion of the SO_2 to sulfur trioxide (SO_3).
3. **Intermediate Absorption:** The gas mixture is cooled, and the SO_3 is absorbed into sulfuric acid in a primary absorption tower, forming more sulfuric acid.
4. **Secondary Catalytic Oxidation:** The remaining SO_2 gas is passed over another bed of vanadium pentoxide catalyst to further convert SO_2 to SO_3 . This "double contact" increases the overall conversion efficiency.
5. **Final Absorption:** The remaining SO_3 is absorbed into sulfuric acid in a final absorption tower, producing the concentrated sulfuric acid product.

3.4.2 Possible Sources

1. Sulfur:

Sulfuric acid production can utilize several sulfur sources, including elemental sulfur, sulfur dioxide from the oil and gas industry, and sulfur-containing gases from metallurgical processes. Additionally, sulfuric acid can be recycled and used as a source:

- **Elemental Sulfur:** Crude oil and natural gas often contain sulfur compounds, which are extracted and then burned to produce sulfur dioxide (SO_2).
- **Sulfur Dioxide (SO_2) from Metallurgy:** Roasting metal sulfides (like pyrite) releases SO_2 , which can be used as a raw material for sulfuric acid production.

- **Sulfur Dioxide from Oil and Gas:** Crude oil and natural gas processing can also generate sulfur-containing gases, including SO_2 , that can be used in sulfuric acid production.
 - **Spent Sulfuric Acid:** Recycling and reusing spent sulfuric acid from various industrial processes is also a source for sulfuric acid production.
2. **Air:** Air can easily be taken from Environment, which will be free of cost.
3. **Catalyst (Vanadium Pentoxide - V_2O_5):**

Vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5), used as a catalyst in sulfuric acid production, can be extracted from various sources, including titanomagnetite, phosphate rocks, uranium-vanadium deposits, oil residues, and spent catalysts:

- **Primary Sources:**
 - **Titanomagnetite:** This is a common source, and vanadium is present in the V(III) form in these deposits.
 - **Phosphate rocks:** Vanadium can be extracted from these rocks.
 - **Uranium-vanadium deposits:** These deposits also contain vanadium, which can be extracted.
 - **Fossil fuels:** Vanadium can be found in crude oil, coal, and tar sands.
- **Secondary Sources:**
 - **Spent catalysts:** Vanadium pentoxide can be recovered from spent catalysts used in the contact process for sulfuric acid production.
- **Other sources:**
 - **Slag:** Vanadium can be extracted from slag, a byproduct of titanomagnetite and iron ore processing.
 - **Oil Residues:** Residues from oil processing can also be a source of vanadium.

4. **Water:**

Near the Meghna River, potential water sources include the river itself, groundwater, and smaller rivers or streams that feed into the Meghna. The Meghna River is a significant source of water, particularly for our plant in Dilarpur, Narsingdi, Bangladesh, which is planning to increase its reliance on the river for drinking water. Groundwater is also a major source of water in the region, but its over-abstraction is causing water level depletion:

- **Meghna River:**

The Meghna River is abundant in water and is a reliable source for our plant. However, the river's water quality needs to be maintained and monitored to ensure its long-term sustainability.

- **Groundwater:**

Currently, a large portion of water supply comes from groundwater sources. However, the excessive abstraction of groundwater is causing the water level to decrease, raising concerns about its sustainability.

- **Rainwater:**

Bangladesh receives significant rainfall, which replenishes both surface water and groundwater resources. Rainfall is a crucial factor in maintaining water availability, especially during the monsoon season.

3.4.3 Possible Prices

Potential avenues for finding suppliers of sulfur and vanadium pentoxide in or that supply to Bangladesh:

Sulfur Suppliers:

- **Export Genius and Volza:** These platforms list numerous import companies and foreign suppliers of sulfur to Bangladesh. They can be valuable for identifying potential partners. There are also some other companies based in China, India, and other regions that frequently export sulfur to Bangladesh.
- **go4WorldBusiness:** This is one of the suppliers of sulfur in Bangladesh. Prices for sulfur vary depending on the specific grade, origin, and quantity. For example, granular sulfur from Turkey might be listed at \$100-\$250 per metric ton, while granular sulfur from Turkmenistan could be priced at \$120 per metric ton.
- **Mahaveer Surfactants Private Limited:** These platforms feature a wide range of foreign sulfur suppliers and import companies operating in Bangladesh. They have listed granular sulfur selling price in their website which is \$230 – \$250 per MT.
- **Bangladesh-Specific Chemical Marketplaces:** They might list sulfur suppliers or distributors within Bangladesh.

- **Industrial Chemical Suppliers in Bangladesh:** They often handle base chemicals like sulfur. So, it could be a possibility for our raw material, especially sulfur.

Vanadium Pentoxide Suppliers

- **IndiaMART:** While the document mentions a supplier in India (Forbes Pharmaceutical), IndiaMART can be a broader resource for finding other Indian suppliers who might export to Bangladesh. They supply V_2O_5 for the price of \$18.14/kg. which is around \$18140 per MT.
- **go4WorldBusiness:** Similar to sulfur, this platform lists industrial chemical suppliers in Bangladesh, some of which may offer vanadium pentoxide.
- **Global Chemical Suppliers:** Websites that list chemical suppliers globally (like Alibaba, ChemSources, etc.) can be searched with "vanadium pentoxide" and filtered by suppliers who ship to Bangladesh.
- **Local Chemical Distributors:** Search for chemical distributors within Bangladesh, as they may stock or be able to source vanadium pentoxide.
- **ASESCHEM (India):** This Indian company lists Vanadium Pentoxide on their website and may export to Bangladesh.
- **Volza:** This platform provides import data for Vanadium in Bangladesh, which can help identify companies that are already importing it.

Our raw material sulfur will be sourced from Mahaveer Surfactants Private Limited, T Nagar, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, while V_2O_5 will be procured through IndiaMART, supplied by Forbes Pharmaceuticals.

3.5 Utility

The estimated utility of the plant, their specifications and other informations are given below.

3.5.1 Cooling Water

Cooling water is used during SO_2 and SO_3 processing in the plant. The source of raw material for cooling water would be the Meghna river. It would go through a water purification process before using it in the main process. The cooling water for a sulfuric acid plant is utilized in closed-loop

systems, such as fin-fan coolers, to prevent scaling and corrosion. (Forzatti et al., 2013) The pH range of this water should be 6.4 to 6.8. https://www.cheresources.com/invision/topic/1819-chemical-involved-in-cooling-tower/?utm_source=chatgpt.com The temperature of the water should be typically maintained about 15°C higher than the ambient air temperature in fin-fan coolers. (Sulphuric Acid Plant Water Saving Options, n.d.) It is essential to prevent microbial growth in the water, which can lead to biofouling and reduced heat transfer efficiency. (Cooling Water Treatment Chemistry Control and Monitoring, n.d.)

Table 13: Specification of cooling water.

Parameter	Specification/Consideration
Water Type	Demineralized
pH Range	6.4 – 6.8
Supply Temperature	Ambient +15°C
Microbiological Control	Regular biocide treatment
Pressure Differential	Less than acid pressure

3.5.2 Steam

The steam should also go through water treatment process. It should go through pre-filtration process to remove large particles, coagulation and flocculation process to agglomerate fine particles, filtration to remove fine particulates, controlling the hardness and softness of the water, reverse osmosis to reduce the dissolved salts, organics and microbes and some other processes. The steam is generated from the process itself. No external steam is produced to supply in the industry. The specification of the three types of required steams to run a contact process are,

Table 14: Specification of steam.

Parameter	High-Pressure (HP) Steam	Medium-Pressure (MP) Steam	Low-Pressure (LP) Steam
Pressure	600–900 psig	150–250 psig	~50 psig
Temperature	Up to 400°C	Up to 204°C	~149°C
Usage	Turbogenerators, large equipment drives	Process heating, acid dilution	Auxiliary heating, dilution
Steam Quality	Superheated or saturated	Saturated	Saturated

3.5.3 Instrument Air

Air is processed to be clean, dry, and oil-free compressed air used specifically for instrumentation and control systems, not for general plant operations. Such type of air is called instrument air. The specifications of this air are stated below.

Table 15: Specification of instrument air.

Parameter	Specification
Pressure	7 bar
Dew Point	$\leq -40^{\circ}\text{C}$ (at operating pressure)
Oil Content	$\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$
Particle Size	Maximum solid particle size: 1 micron Concentration if solid particles $\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$
Air Temperature	Below 40°C

3.5.3 Process Air

Process air is mainly used for the oxygen feed in the plant. To be more specific, it is supplied to sulfur burners and converters to convert sulfur to sulfur dioxide and sulfur dioxide to sulfur trioxide. The specifications of process air are mentioned below.

Table 16: Specification of process air.

Parameter	Specification
Pressure	0.3 – 0.5 bar
Oxygen Content	Near 21%
Dust Content	$\leq 1 \text{ mg/m}^3$
Sulfur Content	$< 0.1 \text{ ppm}$
Moisture Content	Should be low
Oil Content	None
Temperature	Near 25°C
Particulate Size	$< 1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$

3.5.4 Electricity

Huge amount of electricity is required to run a sulfuric acid production plant. It is used to run blowers, fans, pumps, cooling system, electric heaters of the process. Additionally, electricity is required to run offices, DCS sections and even street lights insight the plant. Plant has its own power plant as a secondary source of electricity, and it can use electricity from the national grid as a primary source.

4. SELECTION OF THE PROCESS

4.1 Different Processes

Sulfuric acid, a globally essential chemical, is manufactured through various processes tailored to production scale, location, and economic considerations. Its origins trace back to the tenth century, with Valentinus detailing its preparation in the fifteenth century by burning sulfur with saltpeter. The Industrial Revolution spurred numerous advancements in sulfuric acid production, notably the lead chamber process in the eighteenth century and the contact process in the nineteenth century. Today, the contact process is the dominant method in sulfuric acid manufacturing plants. Selecting the optimal process for a specific plant necessitates a comprehensive evaluation of all available methods against desired economic objectives. Common sulfuric acid production pathways include:

1. Single Contact Single Absorption (SCSA) Process
2. Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) Process
3. H_2O_2 Process
4. Wet Contact Process
5. Pressure Process Based on NO_x
6. Unsteady State Oxidation Process

4.1.1 Summary of the Processes

4.1.1.1 Single Contact Single Absorption (SCSA) Process

The Single Contact Sulfuric Acid (SCSA) process is a catalytic one-step method for producing sulfuric acid directly from sulfur dioxide gas. It involves oxidizing SO_2 to SO_3 over a vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5) catalyst with potassium/sodium compounds as a promoter, where the SO_3 then reacts with sulfuric acid to generate the product acid; this process completes oxidation and absorption in a single reactor.

Main Raw Material: Elemental sulfur.

Process Conditions:

Sulfur Burning: Molten sulfur is burned in dry air at around $900 - 1000^\circ\text{C}$ to produce SO_2 .

SO_2 Oxidation: SO_2 and excess air is passed over a vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5) catalyst in a multi-bed converter at temperatures ranging from $400 - 620^\circ\text{C}$ and pressures slightly above atmospheric ($1 - 2 \text{ atm}$).

SO₃ Absorption: Sulfur trioxide (SO₃) is absorbed in concentrated sulfuric acid (98-99%) in an absorption tower, forming more concentrated acid.

Process Automation:

Generally automated, but older or smaller plants might have more manual involvement in monitoring and control compared to modern facilities. The basic steps of sulfur burning, catalytic conversion, and absorption are continuous and lend themselves well to automation. However, tasks like maintenance, sampling, and occasional troubleshooting might require manual intervention.

Safety and Environmental Impact:

Safety concerns in the SCSA process center around the handling of molten sulfur, posing burn and fire hazards, and exposure to sulfur dioxide gas, which can severely irritate the respiratory system. Direct contact with sulfuric acid at various concentrations also presents a significant risk of chemical burns. Environmentally, the primary issue is the substantial emission of SO₂ due to lower conversion rates, contributing to acid rain and respiratory problems. Additionally, the generation of acidic wastewater requiring treatment and the potential for spills of corrosive materials are key environmental considerations.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Simplified design with lower capital cost ▪ Fewer units: one catalyst bed & absorber ▪ Suitable for low SO₂ content gases ▪ Elemental sulfur is used as feedstock 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited acid concentration (~93–95%) ▪ Catalyst fouling from high absorber temps ▪ Needs corrosion-resistant materials ▪ Higher SO₂ emissions

4.1.1.2 Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) Process

The Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) process is an advanced two-step method that improves efficiency over other traditional methods. In DCDA, SO_2 is first catalytically converted to SO_3 in a primary reactor using optimized catalysts like vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5). The SO_3 then reacts with sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) in an inter-pass absorber to produce oleum. The gases from the exit of the inter-pass absorption tower are again reheated to about $425 - 435^\circ\text{C}$ and subjected to more catalyst passes to increase the overall degree of conversion achieved.

Main Raw Material: Elemental sulfur.

Process Conditions:

Sulfur Burning: Same as SCSA, around $900 - 1000^\circ\text{C}$.

First SO_2 Oxidation Stage: SO_2 conversion over V_2O_5 catalyst at $400 - 450^\circ\text{C}$ and $1 - 2$ atm.

Intermediate Absorption: SO_3 formed is absorbed in concentrated sulfuric acid.

Second SO_2 Oxidation Stage: Remaining SO_2 is further converted over V_2O_5 catalyst at similar temperatures and pressures.

Final Absorption: Remaining SO_3 is absorbed in concentrated sulfuric acid to produce the final product.

Process Automation:

Highly automated. Modern DCDA plants are large-scale and rely heavily on sophisticated instrumentation, control systems, and computer monitoring to manage the complex two-stage conversion and absorption. This minimizes the need for constant manual intervention in the core process operations.

Safety and Environmental Impact:

While more environmentally sound, the DCDA process still involves safety hazards like SCSA, particularly the handling of concentrated sulfuric acid, which can cause severe burns. The added complexity of the dual absorption system and potentially higher operating pressures in some areas introduce further safety management needs. From an environmental perspective, DCDA significantly reduces SO_2 emissions, thus lessening its contribution to acid rain. However, it still

produces wastewater that necessitates treatment before discharge, and the risk of accidental spills of corrosive substances remains a concern requiring robust preventative measures.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High SO₂ conversion efficiency (~99.5%) ▪ Produces concentrated acid (98–99%) ▪ Low SO₂ emissions ▪ Efficient heat recovery ▪ Can produce oleum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High capital/operational costs ▪ Complex setup ▪ Possible NO_x emissions ▪ Need corrosion-resistant monitoring

4.1.1.3 H₂O₂ Process

Roasting is a process where metals are extracted from sulfide ores, during which sulfur dioxide (SO₂) is produced. To meet emissions standards at an extraction facility, two Packed Bed Scrubbers were installed in series. The scrubber uses hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) to convert SO₂ to 40% sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) which can be used in the process or sold as a product, and SO₂ emissions must be controlled due to the health and environmental risks that the gas presents. The raw materials of the H₂O₂ Process are sulfur dioxide, which can be obtained from burning sulfur or sulfide ores, or from other industrial sources, and hydrogen peroxide.

Main Raw Material: Sulfur dioxide, hydrogen peroxide.

Process Conditions:

Reaction: Sulfur dioxide reacts with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in an aqueous solution.

Temperature: Typically operates at relatively low temperatures, often below 100°C.

Pressure: Usually operates at or near atmospheric pressure.

Catalyst: May involve catalysts to enhance the reaction rate depending on the specific process design.

Process Automation: Likely to be highly automated, especially in larger-scale industrial settings. The need for controlled addition of hydrogen peroxide, management of exothermic reactions, and maintaining specific concentrations would necessitate automated systems for safety and efficiency.

Safety and Environmental Impact:

The H₂O₂ Process presents notable safety hazards associated with handling concentrated hydrogen peroxide, a strong oxidizer that can cause severe burns and decompose violently. The potential for exothermic reactions with other materials requires careful temperature control. Environmentally, while the primary byproduct is water, which is benign, the production of hydrogen peroxide itself has environmental implications. Additionally, spills of hydrogen peroxide, although it decomposes, can still cause temporary soil and water contamination and pose a safety risk due to its reactivity.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Excellent SO₂ removal efficiency (~99.7%)▪ Zero waste▪ Ideal for pollution control	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Low acid concentration▪ High H₂O₂ cost▪ Not suitable for large-scale production

4.1.1.4 Wet Contact Process

The wet contact process, an industrial technique used today to produce sulfuric acid, involves three main steps: oxidation of sulfur to sulfur dioxide by burning sulfur or sulfide ores in excess air, catalytic oxidation of sulfur dioxide to sulfur trioxide, an exothermic, reversible reaction that occurs over a heated catalyst (often vanadium pentoxide - V₂O₅) in a chain of reactors, where temperature, pressure, the presence of a catalyst, and the levels of oxygen and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) all have an impact on the reaction, and hydration of sulfur trioxide to form sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), where, instead of adding water directly to sulfur trioxide, the sulfur trioxide is first dissolved in fuming sulfuric acid (oleum), which can then be diluted with water to create concentrated sulfuric acid. The raw materials of the wet contact process are sulfur, which can be obtained from elemental sulfur or sulfide ore such as pyrite, air, which provides the oxygen needed for the oxidation of sulfur dioxide to sulfur trioxide, and water, which is used to hydrate sulfur trioxide to form sulfuric acid.

Main Raw Material: Sulfur, air, water.

Process Conditions:

Feedstock Flexibility: Can handle various sulfur-containing feeds, including those with moisture.

Combustion: Sulfur or other feeds are burned in air, potentially with steam present, at high temperatures.

Catalytic Oxidation: SO₂ to SO₃ conversion over catalyst (such as V₂O₅) at temperatures typically between 400 – 600°C.

Absorption: SO₃ is absorbed in sulfuric acid, often with water in addition to control concentration.

Process Automation:

Largely automated, similar to the SCSA and DCDA processes. The continuous nature of the combustion, catalytic conversion, and absorption steps allows for significant automation. Handling variations in feedstock might require some manual adjustments, but the core process flow is typically automated.

Safety and Environmental Impact:

The Wet Contact Process shares safety risks associated with handling sulfur and sulfuric acid, but the presence of steam and hot, humid gases increases the potential for thermal burns. The moist environment can also accelerate equipment corrosion, raising safety concerns related to leaks and structural integrity. Environmentally, this process may generate larger volumes of less concentrated wastewater, and there's a possibility of steam plumes containing trace amounts of acid mist. Moreover, the overall SO₂ conversion efficiency might be lower than DCDA if not carefully controlled, leading to higher sulfur dioxide releases.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ High acid purity (98–99%)▪ High SO₂ conversion (95–98%)▪ Lower raw material/energy use▪ Safer than direct SO₃ hydration	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ High temperature/pressure needed▪ Generates heat and acid mist▪ Can't use wet SO₂ gas▪ Not for small-scale use

.4.1.1.5 Pressure Process Based on NO_x

The pressure process based on NO_x of sulfuric acid manufacturing is an alternative method of producing sulfuric acid from sulfur dioxide gas. Oxidation of sulfur dioxide to nitrogen dioxide, which is done by passing sulfur dioxide and air over a platinum-rhodium (Pt – Rh) catalyst at high pressure (10 – 15 atm) and temperature (800 – 900°C), where the nitrogen dioxide formed is then cooled and liquefied, Oxidation of nitrogen dioxide to nitrogen pentoxide, which is done by passing the liquid nitrogen dioxide over a lead chamber catalyst (lead oxide or lead nitrate) at low temperature (0 – 5°C) and pressure (1 – 2 atm), where the nitrogen pentoxide formed is then separated from the unreacted nitrogen dioxide by fractional distillation, and Hydration of nitrogen pentoxide to form nitric acid and sulfuric acid, which is done by adding water to the liquid nitrogen pentoxide, which decomposes into nitric acid and sulfuric acid, where the acids are then separated by fractional distillation or solvent extraction. The raw materials of the pressure process based on NO_x are: Sulfur dioxide, which can be obtained from burning sulfur or sulfide ores, or from other industrial sources, air, which provides the oxygen and nitrogen needed for the oxidation of sulfur dioxide and nitrogen dioxide, and water, which is used to hydrate nitrogen pentoxide to form nitric acid and sulfuric acid.

Main Raw Material: Sulfur dioxide, air and water.

Process Conditions:

Oxidation: Sulfur dioxide is oxidized to sulfur trioxide using nitrogen oxides as catalysts under elevated pressures (6 – 10 atm).

Temperature: Operates at relatively lower temperatures compared to the contact process, typically in the range of 200 – 400°C.

Absorption: SO₃ is absorbed in water or diluted sulfuric acid.

Process Automation:

More likely to be automated due to the higher operating pressures and the need for precise control of the NO_x catalyst and reaction conditions. Automation ensures safer and more efficient operation under these more demanding conditions.

Safety and Environmental Impact:

This method introduces unique and significant safety hazards due to the use of toxic nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and operation at elevated pressures, increasing the risk of leaks and the release of harmful gases. Handling sulfuric acid also remains a safety concern. Environmentally, the potential for NO_x emissions, which contribute to smog and acid rain, is a major drawback. The process also generates spent catalyst containing heavy metals that require careful disposal, and wastewater may contain nitrates and other nitrogen compounds needing specific treatment.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Produces both nitric and sulfuric acids▪ Lower temperature operation▪ Utilizes SO_2 from various sources▪ No separate oxidizer needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ High pressure and catalyst costs▪ Heat/pressure management required▪ Acid separation needed▪ Complex and costly

4.1.1.6 Unsteady State Oxidation Process

The fundamentals of catalytic processes in reversed flow fixed bed reactor operation are well known. Basically, a large bed of catalyst is used both as a reversing, regenerating heat exchanger and as a catalytic reactor for the SO_2 oxidation reaction. Cold SO_2 gas is fed into the catalyst bed and is heated to the catalyst ignition temperature by the heat stored in the bed. At this point, the conversion reaction proceeds, producing heat. The heat is absorbed by the catalyst in the bed, increasing its temperature. When the front comes close to the exit side of the bed, the flow through the reactor is reversed. Flow reversals are made every 30 – 120 minutes. The reactor consists of a body, central column, and incorporated intermediate heat exchangers. Conical partitions divide the reactor into three contact compartments with grids supporting three catalyst beds and two beds of inert material. The separate compartments are interconnected by the annular space of the heat exchangers. The raw materials of the unsteady state oxidation process are sulfur dioxide (SO_2), which is typically produced from the burning of sulfur or sulfide ores, air, which provides the oxygen needed for the oxidation of sulfur dioxide to sulfur trioxide, and water, which is used to hydrate sulfur trioxide to form sulfuric acid. Main Raw Material: Sulfur dioxide, air and water.

Process Conditions:

Process conditions are highly variable and depend on the specific chemical reactions and oxidizing agents used.

Process Automation:

Automation would likely be essential for any industrial application of this process due to the need for precise and dynamic control of the operating conditions over time. Manual control of unsteady state processes would be extremely challenging and inefficient.

Safety and Environmental Impact:

Safety and environmental issues for the Unsteady State Oxidation Process are highly variable and dependent on the specific chemical reactions, catalysts, and operating conditions employed, as it is not a standard industrial method. Potential hazards could arise from the handling of specific oxidizing agents and reaction intermediates, while environmental impacts would be determined by the nature of any emissions, byproducts, and wastewater generated by the process design. Without specific details, a generalized four-line summary is challenging.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ High first-bed conversion (80–90%)▪ Auto-thermal at low SO₂ concentrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Requires precise control▪ Explosion risk▪ Not viable for large-scale use

4.1.2 Raw Materials and General Cost Considerations

Elemental Sulfur: Elemental sulfur is the main raw material for most sulfuric acid production methods like SCSA and DCDA. Its price can vary due to market demand, mining costs, transportation, and supply levels. Current prices online range from about \$0.23 to \$4 per kg for small quantities, but bulk prices are usually lower and depend on the grade and supplier. If it can be imported from India, it may cost around \$250 – \$300 per metric ton.

Air: Air is a crucial and generally inexpensive raw material, as it provides the oxygen needed for the oxidation of sulfur dioxide. However, the cost associated with air in industrial processes comes from the energy required to compress and move large volumes of air using compressors. This can account for a significant portion of a plant's electricity consumption (potentially 10-30%). The actual cost depends on factors like compressor efficiency, operating hours, and electricity rates. Some estimates suggest a cost of 15-30 cents per 1000 cubic feet of compressed air, but this can vary widely.

Water: Water is used in several sulfuric acid production processes (Wet Contact, Pressure Process based on NO_x , Unsteady State Oxidation, Modified Lead Chamber) for various purposes, including hydration and forming the acid. The cost of industrial water varies significantly depending on location, source (e.g., municipal supply, well), treatment requirements, and discharge regulations. In Bangladesh, for example, shadow prices for industrial water have been estimated around Tk1,800 per cubic meter (approximately \$21 USD). However, this is a shadow price reflecting productivity, and actual costs might differ. Some industrial zones might have specific water charges.

Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x): These are used as catalysts in the Pressure Process Based on NO_x and the Modified Lead Chamber Process. The cost of nitrogen oxides would depend on their production method (e.g., from decomposing niter or oxidizing ammonia), purification requirements, and transportation. Industrial gases like nitric oxide or nitrogen dioxide can be purchased in cylinders, with prices varying based on purity and quantity. For instance, online listings for nitrogen dioxide cylinders show prices ranging from \$21.50 to \$60.00 per liter for bulk quantities.

Steam: Used in the Modified Lead Chamber Process for diluting and humidifying sulfur dioxide gas. The cost of industrial steam is derived from the fuel used to generate it (e.g., natural gas, coal, biomass), boiler efficiency, and operational costs like water treatment and maintenance. Steam costs are often calculated per 1000 lb or per kg, considering the fuel cost and boiler efficiency. It will be provided from the utility section.

Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂): Used in the H₂O₂ Process. The cost of hydrogen peroxide depends on its concentration, grade, and quantity purchased. Industrial-grade hydrogen peroxide prices can vary significantly based on the supplier and market conditions.

Chamber Acid: A recycled solution of 62 – 70% sulfuric acid used in the Modified Lead Chamber Process. While it's recycled material, there would be costs associated with its initial production, concentration maintenance, and handling. Sulfuric acid prices vary based on concentration and supplier. For instance, 98% sulfuric acid has been listed around 15 to 23 cents/kg. Chamber acid, being a lower concentration, might have a different price point, but it's often tied to the overall sulfuric acid market.

4.2 Selection and Justification of the Process

4.2.1 Selection of the Process

For our sulfuric acid production facility, the Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) process has been chosen, with elemental sulfur combustion serving as the source for sulfur dioxide (SO_2) generation. The DCDA process is a technologically advanced and widely adopted industrial method for large-scale sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) manufacturing as it is specifically designed to optimize the conversion of sulfur dioxide (SO_2) into sulfur trioxide (SO_3), thereby ensuring a higher overall acid yield and improved process efficiency.

4.2.2 Justification for the Selected Process

After evaluating multiple production technologies, the Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) process has been selected as the most suitable method for our sulfuric acid plant. This decision is based on its superior conversion efficiency, product quality, operational safety, and long-term economic and environmental advantages, particularly for a grass-roots, large-scale facility using elemental sulfur as the feedstock.

Comparison of DCDA with Other Sulfuric Acid Production Processes

Key parameters for comparison of the selected process with other processes included conversion efficiency, environmental performance, product quality, operational safety, scalability, and cost-effectiveness.

1. DCDA vs. SCSA Process

The SCSA process, while simpler in design, is limited in performance. It achieves SO_2 conversion efficiencies of approximately 98–98.5%, resulting in higher sulfur dioxide emissions. This necessitates a more robust gas treatment setup downstream. This necessitates larger and more expensive scrubbing units to meet emission standards, increasing operational costs. In contrast, the DCDA process reaches conversion levels of 99.6–99.98%, significantly reducing emissions and improving overall acid yield.

2. DCDA vs. Wet Sulfuric Acid (WSA) Process

The WSA process is best suited for low-SO₂ off-gas streams and is generally not applicable when elemental sulfur is the feedstock, as in our case. WSA also relies on costly noble metal catalysts and can yield variable product purity. It allows for the recovery of acid in vapor form without the need for intermediate absorption, making it effective for small-scale or waste gas applications. DCDA is optimized for high SO₂ concentrations and achieves consistent acid quality with widely available vanadium-based catalysts, making it more economically favorable.

3. DCDA vs. Pressure Process Based on NO_x

The Pressure Process (NO_x-based) for sulfuric acid production operates at high pressures (up to 15 atm) and involves handling toxic nitrogen oxides, which require complex and costly containment systems. The process is also highly intricate, involving multiple reaction stages and equipment for liquefaction and separation, leading to increased capital and maintenance costs. In contrast to DCDA, which uses clean elemental sulfur, the Pressure Process deals with reactive intermediates under harsh conditions, raising safety and environmental concerns.

4. DCDA vs. Unsteady State Oxidation Process

The Unsteady State Oxidation Process involves periodic reversal of gas flow (typically every 30-120 minutes) to manage heat regeneration, introducing operational instability and complicating automation. This intermittent flow also increases the risk of thermal imbalance and hot spot formation, which can lead to catalyst degradation or even explosion hazards due to uncontrolled temperature wave propagation. While the unsteady process might be feasible for small-scale or experimental use, it lacks the proven industrial reliability of DCDA, which enables continuous, steady-state sulfuric acid production.

5. DCDA vs. Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂) Process

The H₂O₂ Process, which involves scrubbing SO₂ from gas streams using hydrogen peroxide, serves primarily as a gas-cleaning method and not as a dedicated acid production route. It produces only low-concentration sulfuric acid (~40%) as a by-product, making it unsuitable for industrial-grade applications. Additionally, the H₂O₂ method relies on costly hydrogen peroxide, rendering it economically impractical for bulk acid generation. DCDA, on the other hand, uses cost-effective,

recyclable vanadium-based catalysts and is easily scalable, making it the preferred choice for high-volume, industrial sulfuric acid production.

In addition to its core efficiency, the DCDA process offers a range of significant technical and economic advantages that substantiate its selection as the most suitable technology for contemporary sulfuric acid production.

Feedstock Simplicity: DCDA utilizes elemental sulfur, which is both widely available and logistically simpler to manage compared to sulfide ores or by-product gases required in other processes.

High-Quality Product Output: The process yields 98 to 99% concentrated sulfuric acid directly, eliminating the need for extra concentration units such as evaporators, which are essential in older methods like the lead chamber process.

Energy Integration: DCDA systems allow effective integration with heat recovery units, improving thermal efficiency and reducing energy costs over long-term operations.

Catalyst and Equipment Cost: Unlike the WSA process, which often relies on costly noble metal catalysts (e.g., platinum), DCDA uses vanadium-based catalysts, which are cheaper and more suited to high-SO₂ streams.

Oleum Production Capability: The process also allows for oleum production, supporting industries that require fuming sulfuric acid, such as explosives or dyes.

Long-Term Operational Advantage: Although the initial capital cost of setting up a DCDA plant may be higher, the overall operational savings and environmental benefits including lower SO₂ emissions, high purity, and automated, safer operations, justify the investment for a mega-scale, greenfield facility.

Based on the above comparison, the DCDA process stands out for its high efficiency, product quality, and environmental compliance. While initial capital costs may be higher, the long-term operational benefits and lower emissions make it the most strategic choice for a self-sufficient, modern sulfuric acid production plant.

Rough Estimation of Gross Profit and feasibility

Rough Gross Profit Calculation Based on Reaction Pathway for Sulfuric Acid Plant

Reaction Pathway

1. $S + O_2 \rightarrow SO_2$
2. $SO_2 + 1/2 O_2 \rightarrow SO_3$
3. $SO_3 + H_2SO_4 \rightarrow H_2S_2O_7$ (Oleum formation)
4. $H_2S_2O_7 + H_2O \rightarrow 2 H_2SO_4$

Step 1: Information and Assumptions

Plant capacity: 100 MTPD sulfuric acid (98%)

Selling price: BDT 19.3 per kg (average from provided range(Made-in-China.Com - Manufacturers, Suppliers & Products in China, n.d.)

Sulfur price: BDT 30/kg (from import price) (BD Bangladesh Sulfur Price Today: 110\$ Granular, LUMP 16.05.2025, n.d.)

Air energy cost: Average 0.275 USD per 1000 ft³

Water cost: BDT 21/1000L = BDT 0.021/L (pumping cost)

Step 2: Molar Masses

Table 17: Molar masses.

Compound	Molar Mass (g/mol)
S	32
O ₂	32
SO ₂	64
SO ₃	80
H ₂ SO ₄	98
H ₂ S ₂ O ₇	178

Step 3: Required Raw Materials for 100 MTPD

H_2SO_4 produced per day = 100,000 kg = 100,000,000 g

Moles of H_2SO_4 = 100,000,000 / 98 \approx 1,020,408 mol

$\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$ needed = 1,020,408 / 2 = 510,204 mol

SO_3 and H_2SO_4 for oleum = 510,204 mol each

SO_2 and S required = 510,204 mol each

Step 4: Masses of Raw Materials Per Day

Sulfur: 510,204 \times 32 = 16,327 kg

Oxygen: 510,204 + 510,204/2 = 765,306 mole \times 32 = 24,490 kg

Sulfuric acid for oleum: 510,204 \times 98 = 50,999 kg

Water: 510,204 \times 18 = 9,184 kg

Step 5: Oxygen Cost from Air

Moles O_2 = 765,306 mol

Volume = 17,142 m^3

Air volume = 17,142 / 0.21 = 81,632 m^3 = 2.88 \times 10⁶ ft³

Energy cost/day = 2,882 \times 0.275 = 792.7 USD/day \approx 83,126 BDT/day

Step 6: Estimated Raw Material Cost (BDT)

Table 18: Raw material cost

Material	Mass (kg/day)	Price (BDT/kg)	Daily Cost (BDT)
Sulfur	16,327	30	489,810
Oxygen (energy)	24,490	-	83,126
Sulfuric Acid	50,999	19.3	984,877 (recycled)
Water	9,184	0.021	193

Step 7: Total Raw Material & Utility Cost

Total Cost = 489,810 \times 16,327+ 83,126 x 24,490+ 193 \times 9,184= 573,129 BDT/day

Step 8: Revenue Estimation

Sulfuric acid produced = 100,000 kg/day

Selling price = 19.3 BDT/kg

Revenue/day = 1,930,000 BDT

Revenue/year = 1,930,000 BDT × 330 = 636,900,000 BDT

Step 9: Gross Profit Per Day

Gross Profit/day = Revenue - Cost

$$= 1,930,000 - 573,129$$

$$= 1,356,871 \text{ BDT/day} = 1.357 \text{ million BDT/day}$$

Step 10: Gross Profit Per Year

Operating days/year = 330 days

Gross Profit/year = 1,356,871 BDT/day × 330 days

Gross Profit/year = 447,767,430 BDT = 447.8 million BDT

Step 11: Gross Profit Margin Calculation

The Gross Profit Margin is a key indicator of profitability.

Gross Profit Margin = (Gross Profit / Revenue) × 100

Gross Profit = 447,767,430 BDT

Revenue = 636,900,000 BDT

Gross Profit Margin = (447,767,430 / 636,900,000) × 100

$$\approx 0.7031 \times 100$$

$$\approx 70.31\%$$

Thus, the gross profit margin of approximately 70.31% signifies a healthy and profitable operation.

Summary Table

This is a simplified gross profit estimation, excluding depreciation, taxes, and financing costs.

Table 19: Summary of the profit calculation.

Parameter	Value
Sulfur required	16,327 kg/day
Oxygen required	24,490 kg/day
Water required	9,184 kg/day
Raw material + utilities	573,129 BDT/day
Sulfuric acid produced	100,000 kg/day
Revenue	1,930,000 BDT/day
Gross profit	447.8 million BDT
Gross profit Margin	70.31%

Remarks on Gross Profit Estimation

It is important to note that the gross profit calculation presented above is a preliminary and approximate assessment, based on a simplified reaction pathway and several assumptions. Key factors such as plant installation and depreciation costs, labor, maintenance, environmental compliance, catalyst usage, utility overhead, and other indirect expenses have not been included in this analysis. Moreover, certain material inputs such as recycled sulfuric acid in the oleum process were not costed fully, and utility estimates, particularly for oxygen sourced from air, were approximated using general energy consumption data.

Therefore, while the calculated gross profit margin of approximately 70.31% may suggest a highly profitable venture, this figure likely overestimates the true profitability of a full-scale industrial operation. In realistic commercial scenarios, where comprehensive operational and capital expenditures are considered, the actual gross profit margin is expected to fall within a more conservative range of 25–50%. As such, this analysis should be viewed as a rough feasibility check, not a definitive financial projection. Further detailed techno-economic analysis, including capital investment estimates and sensitivity studies, would be necessary to support investment decisions with confidence.

Approximate Feasibility Analysis

A feasibility analysis is a systematic assessment conducted to determine the practicality, viability, and profitability of a proposed project. It evaluates whether the project can be successfully implemented with the available resources and under existing constraints. The analysis typically encompasses several dimensions, including technical, economic, market, legal, operational, and schedule feasibility, to identify potential risks, estimate costs and benefits, and support informed decision-making. Its primary objective is to ensure that the project is worth pursuing before significant financial or time investments are made.

1. Technical Feasibility

The proposed sulfuric acid production plant is based on well-established and widely adopted chemical reactions involving the contact process. The multi-step reaction pathway, from sulfur to sulfuric acid via sulfur dioxide and sulfur trioxide, utilizes readily available raw materials like elemental sulfur, atmospheric oxygen (from air) and water. The 98% purity specification confirms a high-grade product suitable for diverse industrial applications such as fertilizer production, chemical synthesis, petroleum refining, and wastewater treatment. The production capacity of 100 MTPD aligns well with industrial-scale operations, and the technology required (converters, absorbers, drying towers, etc.) is mature, accessible, and scalable.

2. Economic Feasibility

A comprehensive cost and revenue analysis has been performed:

Daily Production: 100,000 kg of 98% sulfuric acid

Selling Price: 19.3 BDT/kg (based on global price range)

Raw Material & Utility Costs: 573,129 BDT/day (including sulfur, water, and energy for air)

Daily Revenue: 1,930,000 BDT

Daily Gross Profit: 1,356,871 BDT

Annual Gross Profit (330 operational days) = 447,767,430 BDT

This leads to a Gross Profit Margin = 70.3% which is an excellent return, indicating a strong potential for profitability and financial sustainability.

3. Market Feasibility

Sulfuric acid is a commodity chemical with consistent global demand. Bangladesh, in particular, has an active market driven by the agriculture, textiles, and battery industries. Local production can reduce import dependency and create a competitive pricing advantage. Given the price range of \$120–210/ton on the global market, local production at a moderate cost ensures robust margins and market flexibility.

4. Environmental and Regulatory Feasibility

Sulfuric acid production involves potential emissions like SO₂, which must be strictly controlled. However, modern technology includes effective tail gas treatment systems (e.g., electrostatic precipitator, catalytic converters and scrubbers) to ensure compliance with environmental standards. Operating within national and international guidelines will be critical, but entirely feasible with the proper plant design.

5. Risk Assessment and Mitigation

A thorough evaluation of potential risks associated with the sulfuric acid production plant is essential to ensure long-term operational and financial sustainability. The principal risks and their associated mitigation strategies are described below.

a. Raw Material Price Volatility (Sulfur):

The cost of elemental sulfur may fluctuate due to global supply chain disruptions or geopolitical factors. This risk can be mitigated through long-term procurement contracts, diversification of supply sources, and prioritizing local suppliers to reduce transportation costs and dependency on imports.

b. Environmental and Regulatory Compliance Risks

Sulfuric acid production involves emissions (SO₂) that are subject to stringent environmental regulations. To address this, the plant must be equipped with advanced emission control technologies, continuous air quality monitoring systems, and adhere to local environmental standards to avoid penalties or operational shutdowns. Implementing strict safety protocols, emergency response plans, and continuous safety training are vital to protect workers and minimize liability.

c. Market Price Fluctuations

The selling price of sulfuric acid can vary based on global demand and supply trends. Delays or shortages in raw materials, equipment, or utilities can impair production schedules. Developing multiple supplier relationships and maintaining inventory buffers can reduce such vulnerabilities. Maintaining competitive pricing, optimizing production efficiency, and developing strategic partnerships with downstream industries (e.g., fertilizer, battery, or chemical manufacturers) can help stabilize revenue streams. (Sulphuric Acid Outlook | S&P Global Commodity Insights, n.d.)

4.3 Description of the Process

The Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) process is the advanced method used for the industrial production of high-purity sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), typically up to 98% concentration. It is an improvement of the contact process, designed to achieve maximum conversion (>99.7%) of sulfur dioxide (SO_2) to sulfur trioxide (SO_3) and a high sulfuric acid yield.

The DCDA process consists of the following steps.

Sulfur Melting and Purification

Elemental sulfur is first introduced into a steam-heated melter, where it is gradually heated until it reaches its melting point. The melting point of sulfur is 115-120 °C, depending on its crystal structure. To ensure uniform heat transfer and to speed up the melting process, an agitator is used to continuously stir the sulfur within the melter.

Figure 20: Molten sulfur viscosity as a function of temperature. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

Molten sulfur exhibits a viscosity minimum at around 430 K, with a sharp increase in viscosity just above this temperature. To ensure smooth flow, sulfur is typically fed to burners at approximately 410 K, just below this critical point. This temperature is maintained using 420 K steam circulated through coils in the storage tank.

Figure 21: Sulfur melting process into a steam-heated melter. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

It is then passed through a pressure leaf filter, which serves to remove solid impurities such as dirt, ash, and other particulate matter that may compromise the quality of the final product. This filtration step is essential, particularly for applications that require high-purity sulfur, including the production of sulfuric acid and fertilizers. (Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry | Major Reference Works, n.d.)

Once filtered, the molten sulfur is transferred to insulated storage tanks equipped with steam heating systems. These tanks are designed to maintain the sulfur in liquid form, preventing solidification and ensuring consistent flow during handling and transfer operations. (Chemical Engineering Design, 2012) Given the hazardous properties of molten sulfur, particularly the potential release of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), appropriate safety measures must be in place. These include continuous gas monitoring, effective ventilation systems, and compliance with occupational and fire safety standards to protect both personnel and equipment. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

Air Cleaning and Drying

In sulfuric acid plants, dry air is essential to prevent corrosion, catalyst damage, and sulfuric acid mist formation. Ambient air is filtered to remove dust ($0.001\text{--}0.01\text{ g/Nm}^3$) using electrostatic precipitation and scrubbing. (Brimstone | Transforming Industry, n.d.) Molten sulfur is inherently

dry, but combustion air still requires drying. The drying tower, constructed from acid-resistant materials and filled with ceramic packing, efficiently removes moisture by allowing air to flow countercurrently to the sulfuric acid (98.5–99% H₂SO₄).

Figure 22: Dehydration of sulfur combustion air in a sulfur burning acid plant. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

This acid absorbs moisture from the air through the reaction:

2nd Edition | Elsevier Shop, n.d.)

Concentrated sulfuric acid (~98.5% H₂SO₄) is ideal for air and gas drying due to its extremely low water vapor pressure, making it highly effective at removing moisture. Additionally, it is less corrosive than lower concentration acids and reduces the volume of water that needs to be circulated in the drying system. This step is vital for maintaining plant performance and preventing sulfuric acid mist. The drying process reduces moisture content to 0.05 g/Nm³ protecting equipment like heat exchangers from acid condensation and ensuring catalyst integrity. The dried air is then blown into the sulfur burning furnace by a centrifugal blower operating at 0.3-0.5 bar pressure. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

Combustion of Sulfur to SO₂

In a sulfur-burning sulfuric acid plant, molten sulfur is pumped into a preheated sulfur burner, where it is atomized and combusted with dried air at temperatures ranging from 900–1200°C. The combustion process follows the highly exothermic reaction:

The burner, located at one end of a brick-lined or steel sulfur furnace, is preheated to ensure immediate sulfur ignition. Internal baffles are installed within the furnace to create a tortuous flow path, promoting complete combustion and preventing downstream condensation of elemental sulfur. The resulting flue gas exits the burner at approximately 1200°C, typically containing around 12% sulfur dioxide (SO₂), 9% oxygen, and 79% nitrogen by volume. The presence of sulfur trioxide (SO₃) remains minimal (0.1–0.2% by volume), as the equilibrium for SO₂ oxidation is unfavorable at such high temperatures.

Figure 23: Sulfur burning and heat recovery. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

Various burner designs are used based on capacity requirements. A simple pressure-nozzle burner atomizes sulfur using pumping pressure, while two-component burners utilize the combustion air stream for atomization, offering a broader throughput range (5–170 tons/day) at lower operating pressures. Advanced systems like Lurgi's rotary burner can handle up to 400 tons/day. Additionally, Lurgi's two-stage combustion process can produce gas with up to 18% SO₂ by burning sulfur in oxygen-deficient conditions in the first stage, thereby minimizing nitrogen oxide (NO_x) formation. Residual sulfur is oxidized in an afterburner with injected dried air. (Frank Raymond Allchin, 1979)

The hot gas stream is directed through a waste heat boiler located at the furnace's outlet. This system reduces the gas temperature to 390–440°C while producing high-pressure steam, which

can be utilized for electricity generation and process heating. This step not only recovers energy efficiently but also ensures that the process gas is at an optimal temperature for subsequent catalytic conversion. (Department of Energy, n.d.)

Catalytic Conversion: SO₂ to SO₃ (First Contact)

The cooled SO₂-rich gas from the sulfur burning furnace is passed through a four-bed catalytic converter, where it undergoes oxidation to form sulfur trioxide (SO₃).

The oxidation reaction is:

The reaction is exothermic ($\Delta H = -98.3 \text{ kJ/mol}$), and thus, thermodynamically favored at lower temperatures. However, optimal conversion is achieved within a controlled temperature range of 410–430°C (683K- 703K) and a pressure of approximately 1.2–1.5 atm.

Figure 24: Equilibrium constant for SO₂ oxidation as a function of temperature. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

The equilibrium constant for the reaction decreases sharply with increasing temperature by nearly 80,000 times between 600 K and 1400 K, indicating that higher temperatures significantly reduce the equilibrium conversion of SO_2 to SO_3 .

Figure 25: Maximum attainable (equilibrium) SO_2 oxidation as a function of reaction temperature. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

The above figure further confirms that the maximum attainable SO_2 oxidation drops from nearly 100% at 600 K to about 2% at 1400 K. While higher temperatures may increase reaction rates, they shift the equilibrium backward, reducing SO_3 yield. Temperatures above 430°C shift the equilibrium backward, reducing SO_3 yield, while temperatures below 410°C risk the precipitation of vanadium compounds, which can deactivate the catalyst. This challenge is mitigated by using a vanadium-based catalyst system (comprising vanadium oxide, alkali pyrosulfates such as K, Na, or Cs, and a porous silica support), which becomes active at 660–690 K and fully active at 680–700 K due to the formation of a molten catalytic layer.

Figure 26: Heat-up paths, intercepts and cooldown paths. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

Typically, the catalytic converters are designed with **four stages** housed within a single vertical reactor. Further it can be designed with a 3–1 bed arrangement, where three beds are placed before the intermediate absorption step, and one bed is located after it. This configuration allows for a gradual increase in SO₂ conversion efficiency and effective heat management. Temperature control is critical for optimal catalytic activity.

The catalysts used in modern plants are typically extruded cylindrical pellets composed of 4–9% V₂O₅, with alkali metal sulfate promoters on a silica carrier such as diatomaceous earth or zeolites. The vanadium oxide catalysts operate most efficiently within the 410–440°C temperature range, while cesium-promoted catalysts, introduced in the late 1980s by companies like Topsoe and Monsanto, perform effectively at 360–400°C. However, temperatures exceeding 600°C reduce the conversion efficiency of SO₂ and cause structural damage to the catalyst. To prevent catalyst deactivation via solidification, the feed gas must enter the catalytic beds at or above the catalyst's full activation temperature, enabling rapid SO₂ oxidation at optimal conditions for equilibrium SO₃ production.

The process also generates catalyst dust, which can lead to increased pressure drops across the catalyst beds. To mitigate this, periodic removal and screening of the catalyst are required. Ring-shaped catalysts, developed by companies such as Topsoe, are widely used due to their lower dust

pressure drops, improving operational efficiency. Other catalyst shapes, such as ribbed rings and cylinders, are also in use. (Engineering, 2017)

The converters may be constructed from brick-lined, steel, or cast iron, though newer units often use stainless steel for durability and resistance to corrosion. Excessive heat, especially above 600°C, can deactivate the catalyst, reducing its effectiveness and leading to structural damage. Conversely, temperatures that are too low hinder the reaction rate, preventing efficient SO₂ to SO₃ conversion. To maintain optimal temperature conditions and remove the heat generated during the reaction, interstage boilers or heat exchangers are used to remove excess heat, ensuring the catalyst remains effective throughout the process.

After exiting the third catalyst bed, the process gas typically achieves 90–95% SO₂-to-SO₃ conversion, which is insufficient for modern environmental standards. To increase overall efficiency (>99.7%) and reduce emissions, the gas undergoes an intermediate absorption step before entering the final catalyst bed.

Figure 27: Intermediate absorption tower increasing overall conversion. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

The hot gas (~500–520°C) is first cooled to 60–80°C using heat exchangers and enters a packed absorption tower, where it flows counter-current to 98.5–99% concentrated sulfuric acid. The SO₃ is absorbed to form oleum (H₂S₂O₇) through the reaction:

Using concentrated acid ensures low vapor pressure of water, allowing effective SO₃ capture and avoiding the formation of acid mist. This step also shifts the chemical equilibrium in the next catalytic stage by lowering the SO₃ partial pressure, promoting further oxidation of SO₂ and enhancing total conversion to >99.7%.

The oleum formed in the intermediate absorption stage is subsequently diluted with water to produce sulfuric acid at the desired concentration.

Meanwhile, the SO₂-rich gas stream is reintroduced into the final catalytic bed, where the remaining SO₂ undergoes further oxidation. Since a large portion of SO₃ was removed in the intermediate absorber, the equilibrium of the oxidation reaction shifts forward, enabling a more complete conversion of SO₂ to SO₃. This step significantly enhances the overall efficiency of the process, raising SO₂ conversion rates to 99.5% or higher. As a result, SO₂ emissions are reduced by an order of magnitude, making the DCDA process substantially more environmentally friendly than the older Single Contact Single Absorption (SCSA) method. Some systems even incorporate a five-stage configuration to improve conversion rates and accommodate higher throughput. (Engineering, 2017)

Sulfur trioxide (SO₃) formed in the catalytic converter is absorbed in concentrated sulfuric acid rather than directly reacting with water. While the direct reaction between SO₃(g) and H₂O(l) to form H₂SO₄(l) is thermodynamically favorable ($\Delta H = -130$ kJ/mol at 25°C), it is extremely exothermic and leads to the formation of hot sulfuric acid vapor.

This vapor is difficult and costly to condense, making direct SO₃ and water absorption impractical for strong gas. Instead, SO₃ is absorbed into recirculated concentrated sulfuric acid, which contains a small amount of water and a large amount of H₂SO₄ to moderate the reaction and absorb the released heat. This reaction produces oleum (H₂S₂O₇), which is then diluted to yield commercial-grade sulfuric acid.

Absorption takes place in packed towers operating at 60–80°C, where SO₃ gas flows counter-currently to the descending acid. The optimum absorber acid concentration is around 98.3%, near the H₂O–H₂SO₄ azeotrope, which ensures the lowest vapor pressures of SO₃, H₂O, and H₂SO₄, enabling over 99.9% absorption efficiency.

Figure 28: Mass H₂SO₄ out of absorption tower as a function of mass SO₃ into the tower. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

The above figure shows the linear relationship of production of sulfuric acid with the feed SO₃.

Before entering the absorber, the gas is cooled first by gas-gas heat. The absorbers are packed with materials such as Raschig rings or Berl saddles to enhance surface area for mass transfer. Mist eliminators, including impingement separators or Teflon/glass fiber filters, are used to prevent acid mist emissions.

Figure 29: Absorption in strong sulfuric Acid. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

In some plants, part of the SO₃ stream is diverted to an oleum tower, where it is absorbed in recirculating oleum to produce fuming sulfuric acid. The intermediate absorber setup also allows higher SO₂ conversions in the final catalytic beds due to the reduced SO₃ load. Reheating of gas between converter stages and absorbers is achieved via heat exchangers using hot converter gas, ensuring proper reaction temperatures are maintained throughout the process.

Flue gas from the main absorption tower contains oxides of sulfur (and possibly oxides of nitrogen) due to high temperature during Sulfur melting and burning). A required scrubber is required to treat flue gas prior to discharge (flue gas desulfurization).

Oleum Dilution and Acid Circulation

Oleum produced from the air-drying tower, intermediate absorber, and final absorber is collected and directed to dedicated holding tanks. These tanks serve both as storage and distribution points for supplying oleum back to the air-drying unit as needed. From these holding tanks, oleum is transferred to dilution tanks where it is converted into commercial-grade sulfuric acid through a controlled exothermic reaction with deionized water:

The oleum tower is engineered to ensure safe and efficient dilution by maximizing contact between oleum and water through internal packing or trays, and by managing the substantial heat generated

during the reaction. The controlled environment within the tower minimizes mist formation and enhances mixing efficiency. Following this stage, the diluted stream enters dilution tanks, which further regulate the final acid concentration by adjusting the water flow rate based on the desired output and oleum inflow rate. These tanks also homogenize the acid and ensure consistency in product quality, often equipped with agitators for thorough mixing. Heat exchangers may be installed to recover the significant heat released during the dilution process. The resulting sulfuric acid, typically concentrated to 98%, is stored in acid storage tanks and partially recycled to the air-drying tower, intermediate absorber, and final absorber to sustain continuous absorption operations. This integrated oleum dilution system, incorporating both the oleum tower and dilution tanks, ensures efficient use of oleum and maintains optimal acid concentration for commercial applications.

Tail Gas Treatment

Despite the efficiency of primary and secondary absorption stages in sulfuric acid production, trace amounts of sulfur dioxide (SO_2) and sulfur trioxide (SO_3) may remain in the tail gases. To comply with stringent environmental regulations, these residual gases require further treatment before atmospheric release. Hay, Porretta, and Wiggins (2003) detail the design and implementation of advanced tail gas scrubbing systems, emphasizing the importance of integrating multiple treatment stages to achieve optimal emission reductions.

Initially, tail gases are directed through alkaline scrubbers where they react with neutralizing agents, such as sodium hydroxide or ammonia solutions, effectively removing acidic components.

Figure 30: Dynawave scrubber for removing particulate and soluble impurities. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

In order to estimate the degree of recovery of gases from the tail gas the solubility properties can be used from the curve shown below.

Figure 31: Solubility data for Sulfur Trioxide in water. (Hydrogen Sulfide - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration, n.d.)

Subsequently, acid mist filters or electrostatic precipitators are employed to capture fine aerosols and mist particles, ensuring that particulate emissions are minimized. In some configurations, chemical or catalytic processes are utilized to further reduce residual SO₂ levels, enhancing the overall efficiency of the emission control system. These combined methodologies not only ensure compliance with environmental standards but also contribute to the sustainable and responsible operation of sulfuric acid production facilities.

5. PROCESS BLOCK DIAGRAM (PBD) AND PROCESS FLOW DIAGRAM (PFD)

5.1 Process Block Diagram

Figure 32: PBD of the entire plant.

5.2 Process Flow Diagram

Figure 33: PFD of the entire plant.

6. MATERIAL BALANCE

6.1 Key Assumptions

1. The composition of air entering the system includes nitrogen, oxygen, water vapor (moisture), and particulate matter (dust) and 100% dust is removed by Air Filter.
2. The inlet air's moisture content corresponds to 70% humidity at a temperature of 37.4°C.
3. For the dry air component, the molecular ratio of nitrogen to oxygen is fixed at 79:21.
4. The oxygen supplied for the process is 40% in excess of the stoichiometric requirement.
5. Sulfur combustion in the furnace is assumed to be complete.
6. The conversion rates for SO₂ to SO₃ in the reactor beds are: 65% in the first bed, 75% in the second bed, 95% in the third bed, and 99% in the fourth bed.
7. All sulfur trioxide produced is 99% absorbed in two absorption towers.
8. The final sulfuric acid product stream has a concentration of 98% H₂SO₄ by mass, with the balance being water.

Basis: 100 kg S/hr feed to the sulfur burner furnace.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{S in mole} &= \frac{100 \text{ kg S}}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1 \text{ kmol S}}{32 \text{ kg S}} \right. \\ &= 3.125 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \text{ S} \end{aligned}$$

6.2 Sulfur Furnace

40% excess air is fed at the burner.

Feed O₂ Calculation

$$0.21n_1 = \frac{3.125 \text{ kmol S}}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1.4 \text{ kmol O}_2}{1 \text{ kmol S}} \right.$$

$$\text{or, } 0.21n_1 = 4.375 \frac{\text{kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore n_1 = 20.83 \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

Sulfur Balance

$$(1 - x_1 - x_2)n_2 = 3.125 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Nitrogen Balance

$$x_1 n_2 = (20.8333 - 4.375) \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} = 16.458 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

O₂ Balance

$$n_2 x_2 = (4.375 - 3.125) \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore n_2 x_2 = 1.25 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

From equation (i), (ii) and (iii),

$$n_2 - 1.25 - 16.458 = 3.125$$

$$\therefore n_2 = 20.833 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{So, } x_1 = \frac{16.458 \text{ kmol N}_2}{20.833 \text{ kmol}} = 0.790 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{kmol}}$$

$$\text{So, } x_2 = \frac{1.25 \text{ kmol O}_2}{20.833 \text{ kmol}} = 0.060 \frac{\text{kmol O}_2}{\text{kmol}}$$

$$\text{So, } 1 - x_1 - x_2 = 1 - 0.790 - 0.060 = 0.15 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{kmol}}$$

Table 20: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Sulfur Burner after scale up.

Component	Inlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}\right)$		Outlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$
	Stream No. 6	Stream No. 37	Stream No. 7
Sulfur	3.125	-	-
N ₂	-	16.458	16.458
O ₂	-	4.375	1.25
SO ₂	-	-	3.125

6.3 1st Bed of the Converter

Reaction Equation

Thus, SO_3 production rate,

$$n_4 x_3 = \frac{3.125 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.65 \text{ kmol SO}_3}{1 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right. = 2.031 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_3}{\text{hr}}$$

SO₂ balance

$$n_4 x_4 = 3.125 - 2.03 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} = 1.094 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

Air requirement for the First bed

$$\text{O}_2 (\text{req}) = \frac{3.125 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1.4 \text{ kmol O}_2}{2 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right| \frac{0.65 \text{ mol}}{1 \text{ mol}} = 1.42 \frac{\text{kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{N}_2 (\text{req}) = \frac{1.42 \text{ kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.79 \text{ kmol N}_2}{0.21 \text{ kmol O}_2} \right| = 5.349 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Air required} = \text{N}_2 \text{ required} + \text{O}_2 \text{ required} = 6.771 \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

6.4 2nd Bed of the Converter

Reaction Equation

Thus, SO_3 production rate,

$$\frac{1.094 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.75 \text{ kmol SO}_3}{1 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right. = 0.8205 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_3}{\text{hr}}$$

SO₂ balance

$$n_{5x7} = 1.094 - 0.8205 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} = 0.2735 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

Air requirement for the Second bed

$$O_{2(\text{req})} = \frac{1.094 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1.4 \text{ kmol O}_2}{2 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right| \frac{0.75 \text{ mol}}{1 \text{ mol}} = 0.5744 \frac{\text{kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$N_{2(\text{req})} = \frac{0.5744 \text{ kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.79 \text{ kmol N}_2}{0.21 \text{ kmol O}_2} \right| = 2.1602 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Air required} = N_2 \text{ required} + O_2 \text{ required} = 2.7344 \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

6.5 3rd Bed of the Converter

Reaction Equation

Thus, SO₃ production rate,

$$\frac{0.2735 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.95 \text{ kmol SO}_3}{1 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right. = 0.2598 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_3}{\text{hr}}$$

SO₂ balance

$$n_{6x_{10}} = 0.2735 - 0.2598 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} = 0.0137 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

Air requirement for the Third bed

$$\text{O}_2 (\text{req}) = \frac{0.2735 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1.4 \text{ kmol O}_2}{2 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right| \frac{0.95 \text{ mol}}{1 \text{ mol}} = 0.1819 \frac{\text{kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{N}_2 (\text{req}) = \frac{0.1819 \text{ kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.79 \text{ kmol N}_2}{0.21 \text{ kmol O}_2} \right| = 0.6843 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Air required} = \text{N}_2 \text{ required} + \text{O}_2 \text{ required} = 0.8659 \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

6.6 Intermediate Absorption Tower

Composition of H_2SO_4 (mole basis),

$$n_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4} = \frac{0.98\text{g H}_2\text{SO}_4}{98\text{g H}_2\text{SO}_4} \times 1 \text{ mol H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.01 \text{ mol H}_2\text{SO}_4$$

$$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{0.02\text{g H}_2\text{O}}{18\text{g H}_2\text{O}} \times 1 \text{ mol H}_2\text{O} = 1.111 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol H}_2\text{O}$$

$$x_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4} = \frac{0.01}{1.111 \times 10^{-3} + 0.01} = 0.9$$

$$x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{1.111 \times 10^{-3}}{1.111 \times 10^{-3} + 0.01} = 0.1$$

SO₂ balance

$$n_6 x_{10} = 0.0137 = n_7 x_{12}$$

N₂ balance

$$n_6 x_{11} = n_7 x_{14}$$

O₂ balance

$$n_6(1 - x_9 - x_{10} - x_{11}) = n_7(1 - x_{12} - x_{13} - x_{14})$$

Reaction Equation**Oleum balance**

$$n_9 = \frac{(0.2598 + 0.8205 + 2.031) \text{ kmol SO}_3}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.99 \text{ kmol H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7}{1 \text{ kmol SO}_3} \right| \frac{0.1553}{\text{hr}}$$

$$= 19.834 \frac{\text{kmol H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7}{\text{hr}}$$

We produce Oleum 15%. It means 15% SO₃ and 100% H₂SO₄ by mass,

$$n_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4} = \frac{1 \text{ g H}_2\text{SO}_4}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1 \text{ mol H}_2\text{SO}_4}{98 \text{ g H}_2\text{SO}_4} \right| = 0.0102 \text{ mol H}_2\text{SO}_4$$

$$n_{\text{SO}_3} = \frac{0.15 \text{ g SO}_3}{80 \text{ g SO}_3} \times \frac{1 \text{ mol SO}_3}{1} = 1.875 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol SO}_3$$

$$\therefore x_{16} = \frac{1.875 \times 10^{-3}}{1.875 \times 10^{-3} + 0.0102} = 0.1553 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_3}{\text{kmol}}$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_{16} = 1 - 0.1553 = 0.8447 \frac{\text{kmol H}_2\text{SO}_4}{\text{kmol}}$$

$$\therefore \text{Amount of SO}_3 \text{ in Oleum} = 3.08 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} = 246.417 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore \text{Amount of H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ in Oleum} = 16.763 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} = 1642.781 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore \text{Mass flow rate of this stream, } m_9 = 1889.198 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore \text{Mass fraction of SO}_3 \text{ in 15\% Oleum} = \frac{15}{115} = 0.13$$

$$\therefore \text{Mass fraction of H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ in 15\% Oleum} = \frac{100}{115} = 0.87$$

H₂SO₄ balance

$$0.9n_8 = 0.8447 \times 19.834$$

$$\therefore n_8 = 18.63 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

Water balance

$$n_7 x_{15} = 18.63 \times 0.1 = 1.86$$

6.7 4th Bed of the Converter

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{SO}_3 \text{ production rate} &= \frac{0.0137 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \bigg| \frac{0.99 \text{ kmol SO}_3}{1 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \\
 &= 0.0136 \frac{\text{kmol SO}_3}{\text{hr}}
 \end{aligned}$$

SO₂ balance

$$\therefore n_{10}x_{16} = (0.0137 - 0.0136) \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} = 1 \times 10^{-4} \frac{\text{kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

Air requirement for Fourth bed

$$O_{2(\text{req})} = \frac{0.0137 \text{ kmol SO}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{1.4 \text{ kmol O}_2}{2 \text{ kmol SO}_2} \right| \frac{0.99 \text{ mol}}{1 \text{ mol}}$$

$$= 9.49 \times 10^{-3} \frac{\text{kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$N_{2(\text{req})} = \frac{9.49 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kmol O}_2}{\text{hr}} \left| \frac{0.79 \text{ kmol N}_2}{0.21 \text{ kmol O}_2} \right| = 3.57 \times 10^{-2} \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Air required} = N_2 \text{ required} + O_2 \text{ required} = 4.52 \times 10^{-2} \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

For the First bed

$$\text{Total air inlet, } n_3 = 4.52 \times 10^{-2} + 0.8662 + 2.7352 + 6.752 \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$= 10.4167 \frac{\text{kmol Air}}{\text{hr}}$$

N₂ balance

$$10.4167 \times 0.79 + 20.833 \times .79 = n_4 x_5$$

O₂ balance

$$n_4 - n_4 x_3 - n_4 x_4 - n_4 x_5 = 10.4167 \times 0.21 - 1.0156 + 1.25$$

$$\therefore n_4 - 2.031 - 1.094 - 15.023 \times 0.79 = 2.422$$

$$\therefore n_4 = 30.234 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_3 = \frac{2.031}{30.234} = 0.067$$

$$\therefore x_4 = \frac{1.094}{30.234} = 0.0362$$

$$\therefore x_5 = \frac{11.8682}{30.234} = 0.817$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_3 - x_4 - x_5 = 1 - 0.067 - 0.0362 - 0.817 = 0.0801$$

For the Second bed

N₂ balance

$$n_5 x_8 = 24.687$$

SO₃ balance

$$n_5 x_6 = (0.8205 + 2.031) = 2.8515$$

O₂ balance

$$\therefore n_5 - n_5 x_6 - n_5 x_7 - n_5 x_8 = 2.422 - 0.5744$$

$$n_5 - 2.8515 - 0.2735 - 24.687 = 1.8476$$

$$\therefore n_5 = 29.8238 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_6 = \frac{2.8515}{29.6505} = 0.0956$$

$$\therefore x_7 = \frac{0.2735}{29.6505} = 0.0092$$

$$\therefore x_8 = \frac{24.687}{29.6505} = 0.8277$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_6 - x_7 - x_8 = 1 - 0.943 - 9.0488 \times 10^{-3} - 0.8168 = 0.067$$

For the Third bed

N₂ balance

$$n_6 x_{11} = 24.687 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

SO₃ balance

$$n_6 x_9 = 2.8515 + 0.2598 = 3.1113$$

O₂ balance

$$n_6 - n_6 x_9 - n_6 x_{10} - n_6 x_{11} = 1.8426 - 0.1948$$

$$\therefore n_6 - 3.1113 - 0.0137 - 24.687 = 1.8426 - 0.1948$$

$$\therefore n_6 = 29.6939 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_9 = \frac{3.1113}{29.4598} = 0.1056$$

$$\therefore x_{10} = \frac{0.0137}{29.4598} = 4.650 \times 10^{-4}$$

$$\therefore x_{11} = \frac{24.687}{29.4598} = 0.837$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_9 - x_{10} - x_{11} = 0.06337$$

Intermediate Absorber

N₂ balance

$$n_7 x_{14} = 24.687 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

SO₃ balance

$$n_7 x_{13} = 3.1113 - 3.0802 = 0.0311$$

O₂ balance

$$n_7 - n_7x_{12} - n_7x_{13} - n_7x_{14} - n_7x_{15} = 1.6763$$

$$\therefore n_7 - 0.0137 - 0.0311 - 24.687 - 1.675 = 1.6763$$

$$\therefore n_7 = 28.476 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_{12} = \frac{0.0137}{28.0831} = 4.8784 \times 10^{-4}$$

$$\therefore x_{13} = \frac{0.0311}{28.0831} = 1.107 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\therefore x_{14} = \frac{24.687}{28.0831} = 0.879$$

$$\therefore x_{15} = \frac{1.675}{28.0831} = 0.059$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_{12} - x_{13} - x_{14} - x_{15} = 0.0604$$

For Fourth bed Reactor

N₂ balance

$$n_{10}x_{18} = 24.687 \frac{\text{kmol N}_2}{\text{hr}}$$

SO₃ balance

$$n_{10}x_{17} = 0.0311 + 0.0136 = 0.0447$$

O₂ balance

$$n_{10} - n_{10}x_{16} - n_{10}x_{17} - n_{10}x_{18} - n_{10}x_{19} = 1.2632$$

$$\therefore n_{10} - 10^{-4} - 0.0447 - 24.687 - 1.675 = 1.6561$$

$$\therefore n_{10} = 28.0629 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_{16} = \frac{10^{-4}}{28.0629} = 4.80 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\therefore x_{17} = \frac{0.0447}{28.0629} = 1.57 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\therefore x_{18} = \frac{24.687}{28.0629} = 0.87$$

$$\therefore x_{19} = \frac{0.2628}{28.0629} = 65.42 \times 10^{-2}$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_{16} - x_{17} - x_{18} - x_{19} = 0.109$$

6.8 Final Absorption Tower

Assume 99% absorption, $\text{SO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$

$$\therefore \text{SO}_3 \text{ at Oleum outlet: } n_{13} \times 0.155 = (n_{10} \times x_{17}) \times 0.99$$

$$\text{or, } n_{13} \times 0.155 = (0.045) \times 0.99$$

$$\text{or, } n_{13} \times 0.155 = 0.0442$$

$$\text{or, } n_{13} = 0.285 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} = 27.18 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore n_{12} \times x_{31} = 0.045 \times 0.01 = 0.00045 \dots \dots \dots \text{(i)}$$

H₂SO₄ balance

$$0.9n_{11} = n_{13} \times 0.845$$

$$\therefore n_{11} = 0.268 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

Water balance

$$n_{10} \times x_{19} + n_{11} \times 0.1 = n_{12} \times x_{33}$$

$$\therefore n_{12} \times x_{33} = 1.877 \dots \dots \dots \text{(ii)}$$

N₂ Balance

$$n_{10} \times x_{18} = n_{12} \times x_{32}$$

$$n_{12} \times x_{32} = 24.683 \dots \dots \dots \text{(iii)}$$

SO₂ Balance

$$n_{10} \times x_{16} = n_{12} \times x_{30}$$

$$n_{12} \times x_{30} = 1.37 \times 10^{-4} \dots \dots \dots \text{(iv)}$$

O₂ Balance

$$n_{10} \times x_{O_2} = n_{12} \times (1 - x_{30} - x_{31} - x_{32} - x_{33})$$

$$n_{12} - n_{12}x_{30} - n_{12}x_{31} - n_{12}x_{32} - n_{12}x_{33} = 0.576$$

$$n_{12} - 0.0001 - 0.00045 - 11.87 - 0.2892 = 0.576$$

$$n_{12} = 28.44 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} = 785.102 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_{30} = 4.82 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\therefore x_{31} = 1.58 \times 10^{-5}$$

$$\therefore x_{32} = 0.868$$

$$\therefore x_{33} = 0.066$$

$$\therefore 1 - x_{30} - x_{31} - x_{32} - x_{33} = 0.066$$

Table 21: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Final Absorber after scale up.

Component	Inlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}\right)$		Outlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	
	Stream No.20	Stream No.39	Stream No.22	Stream No.27
SO ₃	0.0447	-	4.49×10 ⁻⁴	0.0442
SO ₂	1.37×10 ⁻⁴	-	1.37×10 ⁻⁴	-
N ₂	24.68	-	24.683	-
H ₂ O	1.85	0.0268	0.576	-
O ₂	1.87	-	1.877	-
H ₂ SO ₄	-	0.2412	-	0.24

6.9 Oleum Storage Tank

For the n_{13} stream,

In Mass Basis:

$$\therefore \text{Mass of } SO_3 = (n_{13} \times 0.155) \times 80 \text{ kg} = 3.534 \text{ kg}$$

$$\therefore \text{Mass of } H_2SO_4 = (n_{13} \times 0.847 \times 98) \times 98 \text{ kg} = 23.6 \text{ kg}$$

$$\therefore \text{Mass of } n_{13} \text{ stream, } m_{13} = 27.18 \text{ kg Oleum}$$

To produce,

(H_2SO_4 :Oleum) in 11: 1 mass ratio, $25.92 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$ Oleum should go to the Oleum Storage tank.

$$\therefore m_{24} = 25.92 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore m_{23} = (27.124 - 25.92) = 1.26 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}} = 0.0133 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

Table 22: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Oleum Storage Tank after scale up.

Component	Inlet Flow Rate ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	Outlet Flow Rate ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	
	Stream No. 26	Stream No. 29	Stream No. 33
H ₂ SO ₄	23.6	12.702	10.896
SO ₃	3.534	1.898	1.628
Total	27.18	14.6	12.524

6.10 Air Filter

Let's assume that our process needs 40% excess air to complete the conversion and the inlet air has 70% humidity at 37.4°C dry temperature.

Total Dry Air required = Air to the burner + Air to the converter

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (20.833 + 10.4162) \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \\
 &= 31.249 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Molecular weight of Dry Air, $M_A = 0.79 \times 28 + 0.21 \times 32$
 $= 28.84 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{kgmol}}$

For Dry Air,

Component	Mole%	Mass%
N ₂	79	76.7
O ₂	21	23.3

\therefore Mass of Dry Air = $901.22 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$

Absolute Humidity, $H_a = 0.01 \text{ kg} \frac{\text{H}_2\text{O}}{\text{kg}} \text{ DA}$ (From Psychrometric Chart)

\therefore Wet air = $1 + 0.01 = 1.01 \text{ kg/kg DA}$

\therefore Water content, $\text{H}_2\text{O} = \frac{0.01 \text{ kg}}{\text{kg DA}} \left| \frac{\text{kg DA}}{1.01 \text{ kg Wet Air}} \right.$
 $= 0.0099 \frac{\text{kg H}_2\text{O}}{\text{kg wet air}}$

$\therefore x_{21} = 0.0099 \frac{\text{kg H}_2\text{O}}{\text{kg Wet Air}}$

Dust Content, $x_{24} = 0.0027\% = 0.000027$

Dry Air = $(\text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2) = 100 - 0.0027 - 0.99 = 99.0073\%$

Wet Air Mass, $m_{14} = \frac{901.22}{0.990073} = 910.256 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$

Mass Fraction of N₂ in Wet Air, $x_{23} = \frac{648.5475}{901.45} = 0.7594$

$$\text{Mass Fraction of O}_2 \text{ in Wet Air, } x_{22} = \frac{207.9525}{901.45} = 0.2306$$

Assumed that all dust is separated in filter.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, Dust mass flow rate, } m_{16} &= \text{Wet Air} \times 0.0027\% \\ &= 910.256 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}} \times 0.0027\% \\ &= 0.0246 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}} \end{aligned}$$

$$m_{15} = m_{14} - m_{16} = 910.23 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{H}_2\text{O content in purified air, } x_{25} = 0.0099 \times \frac{m_1}{m_2} = 9.9 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\text{N}_2 \text{ content in purified air, } x_{27} = \frac{693.24}{m_2} = 0.759$$

$$\text{O}_2 \text{ content in purified air, } x_{26} = \frac{209.98}{m_2} = 0.231$$

Table 23: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Air Filter after scale up.

Component	Inlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	Outlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	
	Stream No. 1	Stream No. 2	Stream No. 40
H ₂ O	8.924	8.924	-
O ₂	207.874	207.874	-
N ₂	684.561	684.561	-
Dust	0.024	-	0.024
Total	901.22	901.22	

6.11 Air Dryer

Assumed outlet H_2SO_4 concentration = 97%

$$\therefore \text{Mass of Dry Air, } m_{19} = 901.22 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore x_{29} = \frac{691.24}{m_{19}} = 0.767$$

$$\therefore x_{28} = \frac{209.98}{m_{19}} = 0.233$$

H_2O Balance:

$$m_{15}x_5 + m_{17} \times 0.02 = m_{18} \times 0.03$$

$$\therefore m_{17} \times 0.02 - m_{18} \times 0.03 = -9.011 \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Overall Balance:

$$m_{15} + m_{17} = m_{18} + m_{19}$$

$$910.23 + m_{17} = m_{18} + 901.22$$

$$\therefore m_{18} - m_{17} = 9.01 \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Solving (i) and (ii),

$$\therefore m_{17} = 874.07 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore m_{18} = 883.08 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

Table 24: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Air Dryer after scale up.

Component	Inlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$		Outlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	
	Stream No. 2	Stream No. 31	Stream No. 3	Stream No. 18
H ₂ O	8.924	17.312	-	26.236
O ₂	207.874	-	207.953	-
N ₂	684.561	-	684.547	-
H ₂ SO ₄	-	848.308	-	848.314
Total	1766.97		1767.05	

6.12 Oleum Dilution Tank

$$\text{Amount Oleum reacted} = n_9 + n_{23} = 19.856 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Amount H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ produced} = 2 \times 19.856 = 39.712 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Amount H}_2\text{O required} = 19.856 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} = 357.411 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

S balance

$$m_{18} \times \frac{0.97}{98} + n_9 \times 0.845 \times 1 + n_9 \times 0.155 \times 1 + n_{23} \times 0.155 \times 1 + n_{23} \times 0.845 = n_{22} \times 0.9$$

$$\therefore n_{22} = 31.77 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore m_{22} = 2859.59 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

H balance

$$\frac{m_{18} \times 0.97 \times 2}{98} + \frac{m_{18} \times 0.03 \times 2}{18} + n_9 \times 0.845 \times 2 + n_{23} \times 0.845 \times 2 + n_{21} \times 2$$

$$= m_{22}(0.9 \times 2 + 0.1 \times 2)$$

$$\therefore n_{21} = 4.69 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\therefore m_{21} = 84.37 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

Table 25: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Oleum Dilution Tank after scale up.

Component	Inlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$				Outlet Flow Rate $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$
	Stream No. 33	Stream No. 19	Stream No. 18	Stream No. 36	Stream No. 23
H ₂ O	-	-	26.236	6.044	23.695
H ₂ SO ₄	10.896	255.128	848.314	-	1161.037
SO ₃	1.628	38.122	-	-	-
Total	1186.368				1184.732

6.13 Sulfuric Acid Circulation Tank

H₂SO₄ Mass Balance

$$n_{22} \times 0.9 = (n_8 \times 0.9) + (n_{11} \times 0.9) + \left(m_{17} \times \frac{0.98}{98}\right) + (n_{25} \times 0.9)$$

$$\therefore n_{25} = 3.167 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \quad \text{thus, } m_{25} = 285 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$$

This amount of H₂SO₄ is stored in the Sulfuric Acid Storage Tank.

Table 26: Mass flow rates of the inlet and outlet streams around Sulfuric Acid Circulation Tank after scale up.

Component	Outlet Flow Rate ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	Inlet Flow Rate ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)			
	Stream No. 23	Stream No. 26	Stream No. 39	Stream No. 25	Stream No. 23
H ₂ O	23.695	416.667	0.3918129	2905.79336	0.01944445
H ₂ SO ₄	1161.037	3750	3.52631607	26152.1403	0.17500001
Total	1184.732	1184.729			

Scale Up

For a 100 MT/d H₂SO₄ production,

$$100 \text{ MT/d} = \frac{100 \text{ MT}}{\text{d}} \left| \frac{1000 \text{ kg}}{1 \text{ MT}} \right| \frac{1 \text{ d}}{24 \text{ hr}}$$

$$= 4166.667 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$\text{Multiplying Factor} = \frac{4166.667 \text{ kg/hr}}{285 \text{ kg/hr}} = 14.62$$

Table 27: Scale up calculation of the material balance.

Stream Number	Variable name of mass flow rate	Basis mass flow rate (kg/hr)	Mass flow rate after scale up (kg/hr)	Variable name of molar flow rate	Basis molar flow rate (kmol/hr)	Molar flow rate after scale up (kmol/hr)
6, 42	m ₀	100	1461.988	n ₀	3.125	45.6871
37	m ₁	-	-	n ₁	20.833	304.5760
7, 8	m ₂	-	-	n ₂	20.833	304.5760
4	m ₃	-	-	n ₃	10.4167	152.2909
9, 10	m ₄	-	-	n ₄	30.2339	442.016
11, 12	m ₅	-	-	n ₅	29.8237	436.019
13, 14, 15	m ₆	293.254	4287.34	n ₆	29.6938	434.1210
16, 17	m ₇	-	-	n ₇	28.4762	416.319
25	m ₈	-	-	n ₈	18.6256	272.304
19	m ₉	12.524	183.0994	n ₉	19.8432	290.106
20, 21	m ₁₀	-	-	n ₁₀	28.4694	416.2202
39	m ₁₁	-	-	n ₁₁	0.268	3.9181
22	m ₁₂	785.102	11478.100	n ₁₂	28.44	415.789
27, 32, 41	m ₁₃	27.18	397.368	n ₁₃	0.285	4.1667
1	m ₁₄	910.256	13307.837	n ₁₄	-	-
2	m ₁₅	910.23	13307.4572	n ₁₅	-	-
40	m ₁₆	0.0246	0.3596	n ₁₆	-	-
31, 38	m ₁₇	874.07	12778.802	n ₁₇	-	-
18	m ₁₈	883.08	12910.527	n ₁₈	-	-
3	m ₁₉	901.22	13175.732	n ₁₉	-	-
36	m ₂₁	84.37	1233.479	n ₂₁	4.69	68.5673
23	m ₂₂	2859.59	41806.87	n ₂₂	31.77	464.4737
28, 33	m ₂₃	1.26	18.4210	n ₂₃	0.0133	0.1944
29	m ₂₄	25.92	378.9473	n ₂₄	-	-
26	m ₂₅	285	4166.667	n ₂₅	3.167	46.2963

7. Energy and Utility Balance

7.1 Energy Balance around Sulfur Melter (F-102)

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Table 28: Worksheet for Sulfur Melter.

Name	BFW Inlet	BFW Outlet	Sulfur Melter
Vapor	1	0	—
Temperature (°C)	400	30	—
Pressure (kPa)	6307	101	—
Molar Flow ($\frac{\text{kgmol}}{\text{hr}}$)	21.47	21.47	—
Mass Flow ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	386.82	386.82	—
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow ($\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$)	0.39	0.39	—
Molar Enthalpy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol}}$)	-229054.54	-284521.62	—
Molar Entropy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}}$)	117.89	7.82	—
Heat Flow ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{hr}}$)	-4918303.99	-6109303.99	838092.41

Reaction:

Heat of Fusion, $\Delta H_m = 14.17 \text{ kJ/mol}$

For sulfur:

$$H_{\text{S(solid)}} = \int_{30}^{115} 0.0183 + 1.84 \times 10^{-5}T \, dT = 1.669 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

For water vapor:

$$H_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \int_{400}^T (0.03346 + 0.688 \times 10^{-5}T + 0.8 \times 10^{-8}T^2 - 3.59 \times 10^{-12}T^3) dT$$

Energy Balance Equation:

$$\sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}} = -n\Delta H_m$$

Solving gives: $T = 30^\circ\text{C}$

7.2 Energy Balance around Furnace (F-101)

Reference temperature: S, O₂, N₂, SO₂ at 25°C

Species	Flow In (kmol/hr)	H _{in} (kJ/mol)	Flow Out (kmol/hr)	H _{out} (kJ/mol)
S	45.687	H ₁	–	–
O ₂	63.962	H ₂	18.274	H ₄
N ₂	240.618	H ₃	240.619	H ₅
SO ₂	–	–	45.687	H ₆

$$H_1 = \int_{25}^{140} 0.0183 + 1.84 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 2.27907 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$H_2 (\text{O}_2, 37.692^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.692} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5} T) \, dT = 0.3738 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$H_3 (\text{N}_2, 37.692^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.692} (0.029 + 0.2199 \times 10^{-5} T) \, dT = 0.369 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$H_4 (\text{O}_2) = \int_{25}^T (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5} T) \, dT$$

$$H_5 (\text{N}_2) = \int_{25}^T (0.029 + 0.2199 \times 10^{-5} T) \, dT$$

$$H_6 (\text{SO}_2) = \int_{25}^T (38.91 \times 10^{-3} + 3.904 \times 10^{-5} T) \, dT$$

Heat of combustion, $\Delta H^{\circ}_c = -296.8 \text{ kJ/mol}$

Extent of reaction = 45687.125 mol/h

Energy Balance Equation:

$$\Delta\dot{H} = \varepsilon\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{out} \times n_{out} - \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{in} \times n_{in}$$

Solving gives: $T_{ad} = 1300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

7.3 Energy Balance around Waste Heat Boiler (HE 101)

Reference Temperature and Pressure: 25°C & 1bar

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, \dot{n} ($\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}}$)	Enthalpy, \hat{H} ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$)	Molar Flow, \dot{n} ($\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}}$)	Enthalpy, \hat{H} ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$)
N_2	24618.858	\hat{H}_1	24618.858	\hat{H}_5
O_2	18274.85	\hat{H}_2	18274.85	\hat{H}_6
SO_2	45687.125	\hat{H}_3	45687.125	\hat{H}_7
H_2O	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_4	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_8

Table 29: Worksheet for Waste Heat Boiler.

Name	Gas Inlet	Gas Outlet	Water Inlet	Water Outlet
Vapor	1	1	0	1
Temperature (°C)	1300	667	30	150
Pressure (kPa)	101.3	101.3	101.3	101.3
Molar Flow ($\frac{\text{kgmol}}{\text{hr}}$)	304.6	304.6	149.7	149.7
Mass Flow ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	10250	10250	2697	2697
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow ($\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$)	10.97	10.97	2.702	2.702
Molar Enthalpy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol}}$)	448.4	-2.304×10^4	-2.845×10^5	-2.367×10^5
Molar Entropy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol } ^\circ\text{C}}$)	253.3	234.3	7.823	137
Heat Flow ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{hr}}$)	1.366×10^5	-7.017×10^6	-4.259×10^7	-3.543×10^7

Inlets:

$$H_1 = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2}(\text{at } 1300^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{1300} (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_2 = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2}(\text{at } 1300^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{1300} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_3 = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_2}(\text{at } 1300^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{1300} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T - 3.104 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_4 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C, 1bar}) = \int_{25}^{30} (75.4 \times 10^{-3}) dT = 0.377 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

Outlets:

$$H_5 = \hat{H}_{N_2}(\text{at } 667^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{667} (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_6 = \hat{H}_{O_2}(\text{at } 667^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{667} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_7 = \hat{H}_{SO_2}(\text{at } 667^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{667} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T - 3.104 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_8 = \hat{H}_{H_2O}(\text{at } 150^\circ\text{C, 1bar}) = 50.218 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

From energy balance equation,

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

By solving the equation, we get

$$\therefore n_{H_2O} = 149.7 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$$

7.4 Energy Balance on First Bed Converter (B-101)

The reaction Equation is:

The extent of reaction ε and $\Delta \hat{H}_r^0$ are,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \hat{H}_r^0 &= \hat{H}_r^0(\text{SO}_3) - \frac{1}{2} \hat{H}_r^0(\text{O}_2) - \hat{H}_r^0(\text{SO}_2) \\ \Rightarrow \Delta \hat{H}_r^0 &= -395.18 - \frac{1}{2} \times (-146.4) - (-296.9) \text{ kJ/mol} \\ \Rightarrow \Delta \hat{H}_r^0 &= -98.28 \text{ kJ/mol} \\ \varepsilon &= \frac{45686.407 - 15990.49836}{1} \\ \Rightarrow \varepsilon &= 29696.744 \text{ mol} \end{aligned}$$

Reference: N₂(g), O₂(g), SO₂(g) and SO₃(g) at 25°C.

Species	N _{in} of stream 4	ΔĤ ₄	N _{in} of stream 38	ΔĤ ₃₈	N _{out} of stream 9	ΔĤ ₉
N ₂	120304.16	Ĥ ₇	240618.47	Ĥ ₉	360923.1	Ĥ ₁₂
O ₂	31979.59	Ĥ ₈	18274.85	Ĥ ₁₀	35405.95	Ĥ ₁₃
SO ₂	-	-	45687.13	Ĥ ₁₁	15990.38	Ĥ ₁₄
SO ₃	-	-	-	-	29696.42	Ĥ ₁₅

$$\hat{H}_7 = \int_{25}^{37.69} 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT = 0.369 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_8 = \int_{25}^{37.69} 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 0.374 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_9 = \int_{25}^{37.69} 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT = 19.343 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{10} = \int_{25}^{37.69} 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 20.316 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{11} = \int_{25}^{657} 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 30.062 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{12} = \int_{25}^T 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{13} = \int_{25}^T 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{14} = \int_{25}^T 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{15} = \int_{25}^T 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

ΔĤ of first bed

$$\Delta\dot{H} = \varepsilon\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{out} \times n_{out} - \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{in} \times n_{in}$$

From here by solving the equation, we get outlet temperature for the first bed is T = 652.878°C.

7.5 Energy Balance around Heat Exchanger 105

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
N ₂	24687.144	\hat{H}_{12}	24687.144	\hat{H}_{17}
O ₂	2421.767	\hat{H}_{13}	2421.767	\hat{H}_{18}
SO ₂	1093.742	\hat{H}_{14}	1093.742	\hat{H}_{19}
SO ₃	2031.235	\hat{H}_{15}	2031.235	\hat{H}_{20}
H ₂ O	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_{16}	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_{21}

Table 30: Worksheet for Heat Exchanger 105.

Name	Gas Inlet	Gas Outlet	Water Inlet	Water Outlet
Vapor	1	1	0	0
Temperature (°C)	652.9	597	30	80
Pressure (kPa)	101.3	101.3	101.3	101.3
Molar Flow ($\frac{\text{kgmol}}{\text{hr}}$)	442	442	236	236
Mass Flow ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	14690	14690	4251	4251
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow ($\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$)	15.80	15.80	4.260	4.260
Molar Enthalpy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol}}$)	-1.916×10^4	-2.119×10^4	-2.845×10^5	-2.807×10^5
Molar Entropy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}}$)	231.3	229.1	7.823	19.41
Heat Flow ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{hr}}$)	-8.47×10^6	-9.365×10^6	-6.714×10^7	-6.625×10^7

Inlets:

$$H_{12} = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2}(\text{at } 652.9^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{652.9} (0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6}T) dT$$

$$H_{13} = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2}(\text{at } 652.9^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{652.9} (0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{14} = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_2}(\text{at } 652.9^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{652.9} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{15} = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_3}(\text{at } 652.9^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{652.9} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{16} = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{30} (0.03346 + 0.688 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

Outlets:

$$H_{17} = \hat{H}_{N_2}(\text{at } 597^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{427} (0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6}T) dT$$

$$H_{18} = \hat{H}_{O_2}(\text{at } 597^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{427} (0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{19} = \hat{H}_{SO_2}(\text{at } 597^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{427} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{20} = \hat{H}_{SO_3}(\text{at } 597^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{427} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{21} = \hat{H}_{H_2O}(\text{at } 80^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{80} (0.03346 + 0.688 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

From energy balance equation we get,

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{H_2O} = 236 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.6 Energy Balance on Second Bed

The reaction Equation is:

The extent of reaction ε is,

$$\varepsilon = \frac{15990.38 - 3997.43}{1}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varepsilon = 11992.95 \text{ mol}$$

Reference: N₂(g), O₂(g), SO₂(g) and SO₃(g) at 25°C.

Species	N _{in}	$\Delta \hat{H}_8$	N _{out}	$\Delta \hat{H}_{10}$
N ₂	360923.1	\hat{H}_{17}	360922.8	\hat{H}_{21}
O ₂	35405.9	\hat{H}_{18}	29409.5	\hat{H}_{22}
SO ₂	15990.5	\hat{H}_{19}	3997.429	\hat{H}_{23}
SO ₃	29696.64	\hat{H}_{20}	41689.6	\hat{H}_{24}

$$\hat{H}_{17} = \int_{25}^{597} 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT = 19.115 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{18} = \int_{25}^{597} 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 18.277 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{19} = \int_{25}^{597} 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 26.993 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{20} = \int_{25}^{597} 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 38.034 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{21} = \int_{25}^T 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{22} = \int_{25}^T 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{23} = \int_{25}^T 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{24} = \int_{25}^T 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$\Delta\dot{H}$ of second bed

$$\Delta\dot{H} = \varepsilon\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{\text{out}} \times n_{\text{out}} - \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{\text{in}} \times n_{\text{in}}$$

From here by solving the equation, we get outlet temperature for the second bed is $T = 660.582^\circ\text{C}$.

7.7 Energy Balance around Heat Exchanger 106

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
N ₂	24687.120	\hat{H}_{22}	24687.120	\hat{H}_{27}
O ₂	2011.613	\hat{H}_{23}	2011.613	\hat{H}_{28}
SO ₂	273.424	\hat{H}_{24}	273.424	\hat{H}_{29}
SO ₃	2851.569	\hat{H}_{25}	2851.569	\hat{H}_{30}
H ₂ O	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_{26}	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_{31}

Table 31: Worksheet for HE 106.

Name	Gas Inlet	Gas Outlet	Water Inlet	Water Outlet
Vapor	1	1	0	0
Temperature (°C)	660.6	487	30	80
Pressure (kPa)	101.3	101.3	101.3	101.3
Molar Flow ($\frac{\text{kgmol}}{\text{hr}}$)	442	442	737.3	737.3
Mass Flow ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	14850	14850	13280	13280
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow ($\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$)	15.53	15.53	13.31	13.31
Molar Enthalpy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol}}$)	-1.861×10^4	-2.494×10^4	-2.845×10^5	-2.807×10^5
Molar Entropy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}}$)	233	225.5	7.823	19.41
Heat Flow ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{hr}}$)	-8.227×10^6	-1.103×10^7	-2.098×10^8	-2.070×10^8

Inlets:

$$H_{22} = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2}(\text{at } 660.6^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{660.6} (0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6}T) dT$$

$$H_{23} = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2}(\text{at } 660.6^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{660.6} (0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{24} = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_2}(\text{at } 660.6^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{660.6} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{25} = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_3}(\text{at } 660.6^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{660.6} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{26} = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{30} (0.03346 + 0.688 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

Outlets:

$$H_{27} = \hat{H}_{N_2}(\text{at } 487^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{487} (0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6}T) dT$$

$$H_{28} = \hat{H}_{O_2}(\text{at } 487^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{487} (0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{29} = \hat{H}_{SO_2}(\text{at } 487^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{487} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{30} = \hat{H}_{SO_3}(\text{at } 487^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{487} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_{31} = \hat{H}_{H_2O}(\text{at } 80^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{80} (0.03346 + 0.688 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{H_2O} = 737.3 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.8 Energy Balance on Third Bed

The reaction Equation is:

The extent of reaction ε is,

$$\varepsilon = \frac{3997.6246 - 199.881}{1}$$

$$\Rightarrow \varepsilon = 3797.74 \text{ mol}$$

Reference: N₂(g), O₂(g), SO₂(g) and SO₃(g) at 25°C.

Species	N _{in}	$\Delta\hat{H}_8$	N _{out}	$\Delta\hat{H}_{10}$
N ₂	360922.80	\hat{H}_{27}	360924.10	\hat{H}_{31}
O ₂	29409.53	\hat{H}_{28}	27510.26	\hat{H}_{32}
SO ₂	3997.43	\hat{H}_{29}	199.70	\hat{H}_{33}
SO ₃	41689.60	\hat{H}_{30}	45487.23	\hat{H}_{34}

$$\hat{H}_{27} = \int_{25}^{487} 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT = 13.65 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{28} = \int_{25}^{487} 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 14.58 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{29} = \int_{25}^{487} 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 21.39 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{30} = \int_{25}^{487} 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 29.99 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{31} = \int_{25}^T 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{32} = \int_{25}^T 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{33} = \int_{25}^T 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{34} = \int_{25}^T 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

For the third bed:

$$\Delta \dot{H} = \varepsilon \Delta \hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta \hat{H}_{\text{out}} \times n_{\text{out}} - \sum \Delta \hat{H}_{\text{in}} \times n_{\text{in}}$$

From here by solving the equation, we get outlet temperature for the third bed is $T = 505.48^\circ\text{C}$.

7.9 Energy Balance around Heat Exchanger 102

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
N ₂	360923	\hat{H}_1	360923	\hat{H}_2
O ₂	27511		27510	
SO ₂	199.8		199	
SO ₃	45487		454	
H ₂ O	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_3	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_4

Table 32: Worksheet for Heat Exchanger 102.

Name	Gas in	Gas out	Water in	Water out
Vapour	1	1	0	0
Temperature [C]	505.48	110	30	40
Pressure [kPa]	101.325	101.325	101.325	101.325
Molar Flow [kgmole/h]	442.0164	442.0164	7937.395	7937.395
Mass Flow [kg/h]	14911.65	14911.65	142993	142993
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow [m3/h]	15.5356	15.5356	143.2815	143.2815
Molar Enthalpy [kJ/kgmole]	-25239.2	-38912.9	-284522	-283760
Molar Entropy [kJ/kgmole-C]	226.1669	201.8065	7.822831	10.29192
Heat Flow [kJ/h]	-1.1E+07	-1.7E+07	-2.3E+09	-2.3E+09

Here, $\hat{H}_1 = -25239.2$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_2 = -38912.9$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_3 = -284522$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_4 = -283760$ kJ/kgmole

From energy balance equation,

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 7937.395 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.10 Energy Balance around Heat Exchanger 107

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
N ₂	360923	\hat{H}_1	360923	\hat{H}_2
O ₂	27511		27510	
SO ₂	199.8		199	
SO ₃	45487		454	
H ₂ O	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_3	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_4

Table 33: Worksheet for Heat Exchanger 107.

Name	Gas in	Gas out	CW in	CW out
vapour	1	1	0	0
Temperature (C)	110	70	30	60
Pressure (kPa)	101.3249966	101.3249966	101.3249966	101.3249966
Molar flow (kgmole/h)	442.016399	442.016399	249.9600204	249.9600204
Mass flow (kg/h)	14911.6532	14911.6532	4503.054884	4503.054884
Std ideal liq vol flow (m ³ /h)	15.53559775	15.53559775	4.512142235	4.512142235
Molar enthalpy (kJ/kgmole)	-38912.8997	-40203.3405	-284521.611	-282239.662
Molar Entropy (kJ/kgmole-C)	201.8064594	198.2499167	7.822830594	14.99752161
Heat flow (kJ/h)	-17200139.8	-17770535.8	-71119027.8	-70548631.8

Here, $\hat{H}_1 = -38912.8997$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_2 = -40203.3405$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_3 = -284521.611$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_4 = -282239.662$ kJ/kgmole

From energy balance equation,

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{out} \hat{H}_{out} - \sum \dot{n}_{in} \hat{H}_{in}$$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{H_2O} = 249.96 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.11 Energy Balance on Intermediate Absorber (B-102)

Reference: $N_2(g)$, $O_2(g)$, $SO_2(g)$ and $SO_3(g)$ at $25^\circ C$.

species	N_{in}	$\Delta\hat{H}_{in}$	N_{out}	$\Delta\hat{H}_{out}$
N_2	360923.13	1.314	360923.234	1.350
O_2	27510.68	1.334	27510.780	1.371
SO_2	199.6956	1.834	199.833	1.885
SO_3	45487.19	2.379	455.037	2.446
H_2O	-	-	27230.597	3.485
H_2SO_4	245074.20	0.717	245074.201	0.717
H_2O	27230.47	0.377	-	-
SO_3	-	-	45033.26	0.255

Heat of reaction and extent of reaction, $\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 = -66.63 \text{ kJ/mol}$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{45487.194 - 455.0367}{1} \Rightarrow \varepsilon = 45032.22 \text{ mol}$$

Inlets:

$$H_{12} = \hat{H}_{N_2}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 1.314 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_{13} = \hat{H}_{O_2}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 1.334 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_{14} = \hat{H}_{SO_2}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T - 3.104 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT = 1.834 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_{15} = \hat{H}_{SO_3}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T - 8.54 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT = 2.379 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_{16} = \hat{H}_{H_2SO_4}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = 6.593 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_{17} = \hat{H}_{H_2O}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C, 1bar}) = \int_{25}^{70} (75.4 \times 10^{-3}) dT = 3.393 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

Outlets:

$$H_{18} = \hat{H}_{N_2}(\text{at } T^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^T (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_{19} = \hat{H}_{O_2}(\text{at } T^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^T (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_{20} = \hat{H}_{SO_2}(\text{at } T^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^T (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T - 3.104 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_{21} = \hat{H}_{SO_3}(\text{at } T^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^T (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T - 8.54 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_{22} = \hat{H}_{H_2SO_4}(\text{at } 110^\circ\text{C}) = 12.719 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_{23} = \hat{H}_{SO_3}(\text{at } 110^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{110} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T - 8.54 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT = 4.649 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

From energy balance equation, $\Delta\dot{H} = \varepsilon\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{out} \times n_{out} - \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{in} \times n_{in}$

From here by solving the equation, we get outlet temperature for the intermediate absorber is $T = 173.268^\circ\text{C}$.

7.12 Energy Balance around Cooler (HE-103)

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
Gas mixture	416.3192	\hat{H}_1	416.3192	\hat{H}_2
Steam	n_{steam}	\hat{H}_3	n_{steam}	\hat{H}_4

Table 34: Worksheet for HE-103.

Name	Gas inlet	Gas Outlet	Steam Inlet	Steam Outlet
Vapor	1	1	1	1
Temperature (°C)	291.672	377	400	380
Pressure (kPa)	101.30	101.30	6306.61	6306.61
Molar Flow $\left(\frac{\text{kgmol}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	416.32	416.32	1221.13	1221.13
Mass Flow $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	11530.73	11530.73	21998.69	21998.69
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow $\left(\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}\right)$	13.83	13.83	22.04	22.04
Molar Enthalpy $\left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol}}\right)$	-8267.78	-5601.00	-229054.45	-229963.64
Molar Entropy $\left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}}\right)$	207.19	211.59	117.89	116.37
Heat Flow $\left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{hr}}\right)$	-3442036	-2331806	-2.8E+08	-2.81E+08

Here,

$$\hat{H}_1 = -8267.78 \text{ kJ/kgmole}$$

$$\hat{H}_2 = -5601.00 \text{ kJ/kgmole}$$

$$\hat{H}_3 = -229054.45 \text{ kJ/kgmole}$$

$$\hat{H}_4 = -229963.64 \text{ kJ/kgmole}$$

From energy balance equation,

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{\text{steam}} = 1221.13 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.13 Energy Balance on Fourth Bed

The reaction Equation is:

The extent of reaction ε is,

$$\varepsilon = \frac{199.834 - 2}{1} = 197.834 \text{ mol}$$

Reference: N₂(g), O₂(g), SO₂(g) and SO₃(g) at 25°C.

Species	N _{in}	$\Delta \hat{H}_8$	N _{out}	$\Delta \hat{H}_{10}$
N ₂	360923.12	\hat{H}_{45}	360923	\hat{H}_{50}
O ₂	27230.46	\hat{H}_{46}	27411.88	\hat{H}_{51}
SO ₂	199.88	\hat{H}_{47}	1.99881	\hat{H}_{52}
SO ₃	454.87	\hat{H}_{48}	652.7547	\hat{H}_{53}
H ₂ O	27.23	\hat{H}_{49}	272304.6	\hat{H}_{54}

$$\hat{H}_{45} = \int_{25}^{377} 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT = 10.501 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{46} = \int_{25}^{377} 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 10.955 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{47} = \int_{25}^{377} 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 15.901 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{48} = \int_{25}^{377} 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT = 22.049 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{49} = \int_{25}^{377} 0.029 + 2.2 \times 10^{-6} T \, dT = 78.814 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\hat{H}_{50} = \int_{25}^T 0.0291 + 1.16 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{51} = \int_{25}^T 0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{52} = \int_{25}^T 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{53} = \int_{25}^T 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

$$\hat{H}_{54} = \int_{25}^T 0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5} T \, dT$$

From energy balance equation,

$$\Delta \dot{H} = \varepsilon \Delta \hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta \hat{H}_{\text{out}} \times n_{\text{out}} - \sum \Delta \hat{H}_{\text{in}} \times n_{\text{in}}$$

From here by solving the equation, we get outlet temperature for the fourth bed is $T = 328.307^\circ\text{C}$.

7.14 Energy Balance around Economizer (HE 104)

Reference Temperature and Pressure: 25°C & 1bar

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
N ₂	360923.023	\hat{H}_1	360923.023	\hat{H}_7
O ₂	27411.875	\hat{H}_2	27411.875	\hat{H}_8
SO ₂	1.9988	\hat{H}_3	1.9988	\hat{H}_9
SO ₃	652.755	\hat{H}_4	652.755	\hat{H}_{10}
H ₂ O	272304.587	\hat{H}_5	272304.587	\hat{H}_{11}
Cooling Water	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_6	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_{12}

Table 35: Worksheet for Heat Exchanger 104.

Name	Stream 39	Stream 16	Water Inlet	Water Outlet
Vapor	1	1	0	0
Temperature (°C)	328.3	70	30	70
Pressure (kPa)	101.3	101.3	101.3	101.3
Molar Flow ($\frac{\text{kgmol}}{\text{hr}}$)	442	442	1145	1145
Mass Flow ($\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$)	12250	12250	20620	20620
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow ($\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$)	14.69	14.69	20.66	20.66
Molar Enthalpy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol}}$)	-7178	-1.505×10^4	-2.845×10^5	-2.815×10^5
Molar Entropy ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kgmol} \cdot ^\circ\text{C}}$)	209.1	192.1	7.823	17.24
Heat Flow ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{hr}}$)	-3.173×10^6	-6.652×10^6	-3.256×10^8	-3.222×10^8

Inlets:

$$H_1 = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2}(\text{at } 328.3^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{328.3} (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_2 = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2}(\text{at } 328.3^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{328.3} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_3 = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_2}(\text{at } 328.3^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{328.3} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T - 3.104 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_4 = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_3}(\text{at } 328.3^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{328.3} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T - 8.54 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_5 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 328.3^\circ\text{C}) = 75.4 \times 10^{-3} \times (100 - 25) + 40.65 + \int_{25}^{328.3} (0.03346 + 0.688 \times 10^{-5}T) dT$$

$$H_6 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}, 1\text{bar}) = \int_{25}^{30} (75.4 \times 10^{-3}) dT$$

Outlets:

$$H_7 = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_8 = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_9 = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_2}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.03891 + 3.9 \times 10^{-5}T - 3.104 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_{10} = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_3}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T - 8.54 \times 10^{-8}T^2) dT$$

$$H_{11} = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (75.4 \times 10^{-3}) dT$$

$$H_{12} = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 70^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{70} (75.4 \times 10^{-3}) dT$$

From Energy Balance,

$$\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}} \hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 1145 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.15 Energy Balance around Final Absorber (B-103)

Reference: N₂(g), O₂(g), SO₂(g) and SO₃(g) at 25°C.

species	N _{in}	ΔĤ _{in}	N _{out}	ΔĤ _{out}
N ₂	360922.92	1.314	360905.7	Ĥ ₇
O ₂	27470.52	1.334	27442.14	Ĥ ₈
SO ₂	1.999	1.834	2.004108	Ĥ ₉
SO ₃	652.754	2.379	6.569482	Ĥ ₁₀
H ₂ O	27230.451	3.393	27429.67	Ĥ ₁₁
H ₂ SO ₄	3526.315	0.717	3523.65	12.7186
H ₂ O	391.813	0.377	-	-
SO ₃	-	-	646.35	4.64978

Heat of reaction and extent of reaction

$$\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 = -66.63 \text{ kJ/mol}$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{652.75 - 6.57}{1} = 646.1852 \text{ mol}$$

Now,

$$\Delta\dot{H} = \varepsilon\Delta\hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{\text{out}} \times n_{\text{out}} - \sum \Delta\hat{H}_{\text{in}} \times n_{\text{in}}$$

From here by solving the equation, we get outlet temperature for the final absorber

$$T = 71.5418^\circ\text{C}$$

7.16 Energy Balance around Heat Exchanger 109

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
Oleum	442.016	\hat{H}_1	442.016	\hat{H}_2
CW	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_3	$n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	\hat{H}_4

Table 36: Worksheet for Heat Exchanger 104.

Name	Oleum in	Oleum out	CW in	CW out
Vapour	6.32E-02	0	0	0
Temperature [C]	110	40	30	38
Pressure [kPa]	101.3249966	101.3249966	101.324997	101.324997
Molar Flow [kgmole/h]	442.016399	442.016399	8657.62036	8657.62036
Mass Flow [kg/h]	42118.22239	42118.22239	155967.901	155967.901
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow [m3/h]	22.71034915	22.71034915	156.28265	156.28265
Molar Enthalpy [kJ/kgmole]	-729225.9853	-741157.0455	-284521.611	-283912.469
Molar Entropy [kJ/kgmole-C]	107.679661	41.22844396	7.82283059	9.80430781
Heat Flow [kJ/h]	-322329844.1	-327603568.4	-2463280096	-2458006372

Here, $\hat{H}_1 = -729225.9853$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_2 = -741157.0455$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_3 = -284521.611$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_4 = -283912.469$ kJ/kgmole

From energy balance equation, $\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{out} \hat{H}_{out} - \sum \dot{n}_{in} \hat{H}_{in}$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{steam} = 8657.62 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

7.17 Energy Balance around Drying Tower (D-101)

Reference temperature: 25°C.

Species	Flow In (kg/hr)	H_{in} (kJ/mol)	Flow Out (kg/hr)	H_{out} (kJ/mol)
H ₂ O(v)	131.744	H ₁	–	–
O ₂	3074.033	H ₂	3096.95	H ₆
N ₂	10100.393	H ₃	10105.8	H ₇
H ₂ SO ₄	12522.796	H ₄	12523.2	H ₈
H ₂ O(l)	255.567		387.316	

$$H_1 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}(v)}(\text{at } 37.4^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.4} (75.4 \times 10^{-3}) dT = 0.4207 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_2 = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2}(\text{at } 37.4^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.4} (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 0.3653 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_3 = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2}(\text{at } 37.4^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.4} (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 0.3604 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_4 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ Solution}} (\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}) = 20.468 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}} \text{ [From Enthalpy Concentration Diagram]}$$

$$H_6 = \hat{H}_{\text{O}_2} (\text{at } T^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^T (0.0291 + 1.158 \times 10^{-5}T - 6.076 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_7 = \hat{H}_{\text{N}_2} (\text{at } T^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^T (0.029 + 2.199 \times 10^{-6}T + 5.723 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT$$

$$H_8 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4} (\text{at } 37.78^\circ\text{C}) = 20.324 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}} \text{ [From Enthalpy Concentration Diagram]}$$

From energy balance equation,

Heat Produced from Acid = Heat absorbed from Air

$$\text{or, } m_{\text{out}}H_8 - m_{\text{in}}H_4 = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}}\hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}}\hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{or, } (12523.2 + 387.316) \times 20.324 - (12522.796 + 255.567) \times 20.468 \\ = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}}\hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}}\hat{H}_{\text{in}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or, } 835.789 = \sum \dot{n}_{\text{out}}\hat{H}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{n}_{\text{in}}\hat{H}_{\text{in}}$$

Solving the equation, we get: $T_{\text{out}} = 37.692^\circ\text{C}$

7.18 Energy Balance around Oleum Dilution Tank (T-101)

Inlets:

Stream	Temperature (°C)	Components	n_{in} (kmol/h)	H_{in} (kJ/mol)
n_{28}	40	H_2SO_4	0.164	H_1
		SO_3 (dissolved)	0.030	H_2
n_{19}	110	H_2SO_4	245.14	H_3
		SO_3 (dissolved)	44.966	H_4
n_{18}	37.78	$H_2O(l)$	21.517	H_5
		H_2SO_4	127.787	H_6
n_{36}	30	H_2O	n_{21}	H_7

Outlet:

Stream	Temperature (°C)	Components	nout (kmol/h)	Hout (kJ/mol)
n ₂₃	30	H ₂ SO ₄	418.068	H ₈
		H ₂ O	46.452	H ₉

Here, overall heat of reaction, ΔH_r = -75.7 kJ/mol

$$H_1 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}(\text{at } 40^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{40} (0.1391 + 1.56 \times 10^{-6}T + 1.73 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 2.1625 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_2 = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_3}(\text{at } 40^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{40} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = 0.7723 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_3 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}(\text{at } 110^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{110} (0.1391 + 1.56 \times 10^{-6}T + 1.73 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 12.718 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_4 = \hat{H}_{\text{SO}_3}(\text{at } 110^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{110} (0.0485 + 9.19 \times 10^{-5}T) dT = 4.649 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_5 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 37.78^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.78} (0.0754) dT = 0.964 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_6 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}(\text{at } 37.78^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{37.78} (0.1391 + 1.56 \times 10^{-6}T + 1.73 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 1.84 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_7 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{30} (0.0754) dT = 0.377 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_8 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{30} (0.1391 + 1.56 \times 10^{-6}T + 1.73 \times 10^{-9}T^2) dT = 0.717 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

$$H_9 = \hat{H}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(\text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}) = \int_{25}^{30} (0.0754) dT = 0.377 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}}$$

Extent of reaction, ε = 194.44 + 290106.585 = 290301.03 mol

Energy Balance Equation:

$$Q = \varepsilon \Delta \hat{H}_r^0 + \sum \Delta \hat{H}_{out} \times n_{out} - \sum \Delta \hat{H}_{in} \times n_{in}$$

$$\text{Or, } Q = -25 \times 10^9 \text{ J}$$

7.19 Energy Balance around Heat Exchanger 108

Reference Temperature: 25°C

Components	Inlet		Outlet	
	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$	Molar Flow, $\dot{n} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}} \right)$	Enthalpy, $\hat{H} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \right)$
H ₂ SO ₄ (98%)	276.22313	\hat{H}_1	276.22313	\hat{H}_2
Steam	n_{steam}	\hat{H}_3	n_{steam}	\hat{H}_4

Table 37: Worksheet for Heat Exchanger 108.

Name	Acid in	Acid out	Steam in	Steam out
Vapour	0	0	1	0
Temperature [C]	30	70	400	80
Pressure [kPa]	101.3249966	101.3249966	101.3249966	101.3249966
Molar Flow [kgmole/h]	276.22313	276.22313	26.70565992	26.70565992
Mass Flow [kg/h]	24880.38733	24880.38733	481.1051467	481.1051467
Std Ideal Liq Vol Flow [m3/h]	13.67272933	13.67272933	0.482076037	0.482076037
Molar Enthalpy [kJ/kgmole]	-746994.4771	-741869.4484	-227716.7413	-280726.1585
Molar Entropy [kJ/kgmole-C]	19.85589593	57.41487161	154.0097278	19.41037712
Heat Flow [kJ/h]	-206337152.6	-204921501.1	-6081325.85	-7496977.318

Here, $\hat{H}_1 = -746994.4771$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_2 = -741869.4484$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_3 = -227716.7413$ kJ/kgmole

$\hat{H}_4 = -280726.1585$ kJ/kgmole

From energy balance equation, $\Delta H = \sum \dot{n}_{out} \hat{H}_{out} - \sum \dot{n}_{in} \hat{H}_{in}$

By solving this equation we get, $n_{steam} = 26.705 \frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{hr}}$

8. EQUIPMENT LIST AND SIZING OF EQUIPMENT

8.1 Equipment List

Table 38: List of the equipments.

Equipment Type	Equipment ID	Equipment Name	Equipment Purpose	Equipment size	Material of Construction
Dryer	D-101	Air Drying Tower	To absorb moisture from air	Diameter = 2 m Height = 5.81 m	Carbon Steel and 2 inch Intalox saddle ceramics Packing materials
Reactor	F-101	Furnace	Sulfur dioxide production	Shell length = 6m Shell diameter = 2m	Carbon Steel Fire brick and Insulating brick
	B-101	4 Bed Converter	Sulfur trioxide production	Bed diameter = 5m First bed height = 2.08m Second bed height = 1.31m Third bed height = 1.15m Fourth bed height = 1.05m	Packing material: silica with the catalyst V2O5
	T-101	Oleum Dilution Tank	To produce sulfuric acid from oleum	Diameter = 1.28 m Height = 4 m	Carbon Steel
Absorber	B-102	Intermediate Absorption Tower	To produce oleum from sulfur trioxide and sulfuric acid	Diameter = 1.89 m Packing Height = 5.48 m	Carbon Steel and 1 inch intalox saddle ceramics Packing materials

	B-103	Final Absorption Tower	To produce oleum from sulfur trioxide and sulfuric acid	Diameter = 1.63 m Height = 7.15 m	Carbon Steel and 1inch intalox saddle ceramics Packing materials
Heat Exchanger	HE-101	Waste Heat Boiler	To cool down the furnace outlet	At tube side, OD = 3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=160	SS-416
	HE-102	Cooler	To cool down stream 13	At tube side, OD = 20 mm BWG = 14 ID = 16 mm Let, the length of the tube, L = 4 m No. of tubes, N=1560	SS-416
	HE-103	Heater	To heat up stream 16	At tube side, OD = 3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=160	SS-416
	HE-104	Cooler	To cool stream 20	At tube side, OD = 3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=160	SS-416

	HE-105	Cooler	To cool down stream 9	At tube side, OD =3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=61	SS-416
	HE-106	Cooler	To cool down stream 11	At tube side, OD =3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=160	SS-416
	HE-107	Cooler	To cool down stream 14	At tube side, OD =3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=400	SS-416
	HE-108	Heater	To heat up the Acid of stream 30	At tube side, OD =3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=304	SS-416
	HE-109	Cooler	To cool down oleum of stream 27	At tube side, OD =3/4 inch BWG = 14 ID = 0.584 inch Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m No. of tubes, N=469	SS-416
Filter	FL-101	Filter	To filter dust and PM from air	Area = 124.9 m ² No of Bags = 100 =10 x10	Stainless Steel HEPA-Grade
Tanks	T-102	H ₂ SO ₄ Circulation Tank	Circulation tank for 98% Sulfuric acid	Diameter = 2.2 m Height = 3.3 m No of Tanks = 1	Carbon Steel

	T-103	H ₂ SO ₄ Storage Tank	To store 98% Sulfuric acid	Diameter = 5.5 m Height = 8.3 m No of Tanks = 2	Carbon Steel
	T-104	Oleum Storage Tank	To store Oleum	Diameter = 3.25 m Height = 4.8 m No of Tanks = 1	Carbon Steel

8.2 Equipment Sizing

8.2.1 Sizing of Furnace

Shell diameter = 2m (assumption)

Shell length = 6m (shell length: diameter = 3: 1)

Spray nozzle would be used to eject melted sulfur.

Table 39: Details of the furnace.

Furnace shell material	Carbon steel
Insulation	13 mm outside
Refractory	13.5 inch
Fire brick	4.5 inch × 9 inch
Insulating brick	9 inch × 9 inch

8.2.2 Sizing of Intermediate Absorption Tower

In sulfuric acid absorption towers, ceramic random packing, such as Intalox saddles, is preferred over structured or metallic packings due to its superior corrosion resistance, high surface area, and ease of handling. Additionally, random ceramic packings promote efficient gas-liquid contact and turbulent flow, enhancing absorption. Their mechanical robustness and availability in standard sizes make them the most practical and economical choice for industrial-scale absorption towers.

Packing material: (random packing) Intalox saddles ceramic. (Peters, M. S., Timmerhaus, K. D., & West, R. E. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (6th ed., p. 690). McGraw-Hill)

Nominal size, $d_p = 1.0$ inch

Porosity, $\epsilon = 0.18$

Packing factor $a_p/\epsilon^3 = 100$ ft²/ft³

Diameter Calculation

Mass flow rate of liquid at the bottom of the tower,

$$L = 45.032 \times 80 + 245.074 \times 98$$

$$= 27619.812 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 7.672 \text{ kg/s}$$

Density of 13% liquid Oleum, $\rho_L = 1.90 \text{ g/mL}$ (at 1100°C) [East Harbour Group. (Year). (Oleum-Sulphuric-Acid-Fuming-MSDS-207-V3.Pdf, n.d.)

and viscosity = 5 cp

Mass flow rate of gas at the bottom of the tower,

$$G = (45.487 \times 80 + 1.1998 \times 64 + 27.511 \times 32 + 360.923 \times 28) \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 14637.94 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 4.066 \text{ kg/s}$$

The average molecular weight of the gas,

$$M_{\text{avg}} = (0.10478 \times 80 + 0.00046 \times 64 + 0.06337 \times 32 + 0.83139 \times 28) = 33.7186 \text{ kg/kmol}$$

$$\text{The density of gas } \rho_g = \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 33.72}{8.314 \times (70+273)} = 1198.12 \text{ g/m}^3 = 0.0747 \text{ lb/ft}^3$$

Figure 34: Correlation for estimating flooding rate in packed towers.

Now, from figure 01 [Peters, M. S., & Timmerhaus, K. D. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (4th ed., p. 698). McGraw-Hill.]

$$X \text{ value} = \frac{L}{G} \times \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\rho_L} \right)^{0.5} = 0.0473$$

$$Y \text{ value} = 0.17$$

$$\text{Now, } \frac{V^2 a \rho \mu L^{0.2} \rho g}{g \rho L} = 0.17$$

Therefore, flooding velocity, $V = 7.93 \text{ ft/s}$

Here, allowable vapor velocity is estimated to be 50 to 70% of the flooding velocity (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003, p. 698), which is used to determine the column diameter. Considering the absorber tower is designed for the gas velocity at 50% of the flooding velocity.

Maximum allowable vapor velocity $V_{\text{actual}} = 0.50 \times 7.93 \text{ ft/s} = 3.966 \text{ ft/s} = 1.2 \text{ m/s}$

Volumetric flow rate of gas $Q = \frac{G}{\rho g} = 3.393 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

Cross-sectional area, $A = \frac{Q}{V_{\text{actual}}} = 2.87 \text{ m}^2$

Thus, $D = 1.89 \text{ m}$

Therefore, the diameter of the tank is 1.89 m

Height calculation

Number of overall gas phase transfer unit = N_{OG} [Peters, M. S., & Timmerhaus, K. D. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (4th ed., p. 703). McGraw-Hill.]

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \frac{(1-y)l_m}{(1-y)(y^*-y)} dy$$

When the gas is dilute $(1-y)_{lm} = (1-y)$

The reaction at the interface is very instantaneous that, $y^* = 0$

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_2}^{y_1} \frac{1}{y} dy$$

Here $y_1 =$ Input mole fraction of $\text{SO}_3 = 0.1047$

And $y_2 =$ Output mole fraction of $\text{SO}_3 = 0.00109$

So, $N_{OG} = 4.565 \text{ m}$

Now, the height of an overall gas phase transfer unit is calculated using Onda's method (Towler and Sinnott, 2013, p. 901)

$$\frac{a_w}{a} = 1 - \exp \left[-0.45 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_L} \right)^{0.75} \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a \mu_L} \right)^{0.1} \left(\frac{L_w^* a}{\rho_L^2 g} \right)^{-0.05} \left(\frac{L_w^*}{\rho_L \sigma_L a} \right)^{0.2} \right]$$

Here, $a = 253 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R. (2013))

σ_c for ceramic = 61×10^{-3} N/m (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R. (2013))

σ_L for 98% sulfuric acid = 0.05 N/m (No Text - Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

μ_L = Viscosity of liquid H₂SO₄ = 0.0063 Pa.s (Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

Density of 98% liquid H₂SO₄, ρ_L = 1797.6 kg/m³ (Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

$$L_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of liquid H}_2\text{SO}_4}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = 2.733 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$S_o, a_w = 111.467 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$$

Here,

Packing size $d_p = 1.0$ inch = 0.0254 m

Association parameter of the solvent H₂SO₄, $\phi = 1$

The molecular weight of solvent B (98% H₂SO₄), $M_B = 98$ kg/kmol

$$T = (273 + 70) = 343 \text{ K}$$

Viscosity of B (H₂SO₄), $\mu_B = 0.0063$ Pa.s

Solute (SO₃) molar volume at the boiling point = V_A

Using table 18.2 -4 for atomic and molar volumes at the normal boiling point (Geankoplis, C. J., Curry, D., & Allison, R. (2018). Transport processes and separation process principles (5th ed.). Pearson.)

$$V_A = (S) + 3(O)$$

$$= (25.6 + 3 \times 7.4) \times 10^{-3} = 0.0478 \text{ m}^3/\text{kgmol}$$

$$D_L = 1.173 \times 10^{-16} (\phi M_B)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{T}{\mu_B V_A^{0.6}} \text{ (Geankoplis, 2018,}$$

$$S_o, D_L = 3.919 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$$

Therefore,

$$k_L \left(\frac{\rho_L}{\mu_L g} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.0051 \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a_w \mu_L} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\mu_L}{\rho_L D_L} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (ad_p)^{0.4}$$

$$\text{Or, } k_L = 9.132 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m/s}$$

Now, Viscosity of gas (SO₃), $\mu_v = 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$ kg/ms [at 70°C]

$$\text{Density of gas (SO}_3\text{) at 70°C, } \rho_v = \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 80 \times 10^{-3}}{8.314 \times 303}$$

$$= 2.842 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

Where, Operating pressure, $P = 1$ atm

Atomic and Structural Diffusion Volume Increments			
C	16.5	Cl	19.5*
H	1.98	S	17.0*
O	5.48	Aromatic or	-20.0
N	5.69*	hetrocyclic rings	
Diffusion Volumes of Simple Molecules			
H ₂	7.07	CO	18.9
D ₂	6.70	CO ₂	26.9
He	2.88	N ₂ O	35.9
N ₂	17.9	NH ₃	14.9
O ₂	16.6	H ₂ O	12.7
Air	20.1	CCL ₂ F ₂	114.8*
Ne	5.59	SF ₆	69.7*
Ar	16.1	Cl ₂	37.7*
Kr	22.8	Br ₂	67.2*
Xe	37.9*	SO ₂	41.1*

*Value based on only a few data points.

Figure 35: Table consisting of diffusion volume coefficients determined by Fuller.

The sum of the structural volume increments of A (SO₃),

$$\sum V_{A,i} = 17 + 5.48 \times 3 = 33.44$$

The sum of the structural volume increments of B (Other gases),

$$\sum V_{B,i} = (41.1 + 5.69 \times 2 + 5.48 \times 2) = 63.44$$

The molecular weight of A (SO₃), $M_A = 80$ kg/kmol

Molecular weight of B, $M_B = 25.336$ kg/kmol

Temperature, $T = 343$ K

For packing sizes above 15 mm, $K_5 = 5.23$

Hence,

$$D_v = \frac{1 \times 10^{-7} (T)^{1.75} \left(\frac{1}{M_A} + \frac{1}{M_B} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P \left[\sum V_{A,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} + \sum V_{B,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} \right]^2}$$

So, $D_v = 1.2144 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

$$\text{Now, } V_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of Gas stream}}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = \frac{4.0661}{2.807} = 1.448 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

So, $k_G = 5.93 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kmol/m}^2 \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{atm}$

Now, the molar gas flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$G_m = \frac{V_w}{\text{molecular weight of gas}} = 0.0181 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

And molar liquid flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$L_m = \frac{L_w}{\text{molecular weight of liquid}} = 0.0269 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{Height of the gas film transfer unit, } H_G = \frac{G_m}{K_G a_w P} = 0.273 \text{ m}$$

$$C_T = \frac{\rho L}{\text{Molecular weight of solvent}} = 19.97 \text{ kmol/m}^3$$

$$\text{Height of the liquid film transfer unit, } H_L = \frac{L_m}{K_L a_w C_T} = 1.325 \text{ m}$$

Now, the overall height of the transfer unit based on concentration driving force,

$$H_{OG} = H_G + (m G_m / L_m) \times H_L$$

According to Colburn (1939), the optimum value for the term $m G_m / L_m$ will lie between 0.7 - 0.8. Taking 0.7 for calculation,

$$H_{OG} = 0.273 + 0.7 \times 1.325 = 1.201 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Now the height of the packing, } Z = H_{OG} \times N_{OG} = 1.201 \times 4.565 = 5.48 \text{ m}$$

Calculated Diameter: 1.89 m

Packing height: 5.48 m approximately.

8.2.3 Sizing of Final Absorption Tower

Packing material: (random packing) Intalox saddles ceramic. (Peters, M. S., Timmerhaus, K. D., & West, R. E. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (6th ed., p. 690). McGraw-Hill)

Nominal size, $d_p = 1.0$ inch

Porosity, $\epsilon = 0.18$

Packing factor $a_p/\epsilon^3 = 100 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft}^3$

Diameter Calculation

Mass flow rate of liquid at the bottom of the tower,

$$L = 0.646 \times 80 + 3.524 \times 98$$

$$= 397.032 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 0.11 \text{ kg/s}$$

Density of 13% liquid Oleum, $\rho_L = 1.90 \text{ g/mL}$ (at 1100°C) (Oleum-Sulphuric-Acid-Fuming-MSDS-207-V3.Pdf, n.d.)

and viscosity = 5 cp (Norfalco_sulfuric_acid_handbook.Pdf, n.d.)

Mass flow rate of gas at the bottom of the tower,

$$\begin{aligned}
 G &= (0.6534 \times 80 + 0.00199 \times 64 + 27.47 \times 32 + 360.86 \times 28 + 27.05 \times 18) \text{ kg/hr} \\
 &= 11522.596 \text{ kg/hr} \\
 &= 3.2 \text{ kg/s}
 \end{aligned}$$

The average molecular weight of the gas,

$$M_{\text{avg}} = (0.00157 \times 80 + 0.0000048 \times 64 + 0.066 \times 32 + 0.867 \times 28 + 0.065 \times 18) = 27.68 \text{ kg/kmol}$$

$$\text{The density of gas } \rho_g = \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 27.68}{8.314 \times (70 + 273)} = 983.64 \text{ g/m}^3 = 0.0614 \text{ lb/ft}^3$$

Figure 36: Correlation for estimating flooding rate in packed towers.

Now, from figure 01 (Peters, M. S., & Timmerhaus, K. D. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (4th ed., p. 698). McGraw-Hill.)

$$\text{Flow parameter, X value} = \frac{L}{G} \times \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\rho_L} \right)^{0.5} = 0.00784$$

$$\text{Capacity parameter, Y value} = 0.23$$

$$\text{Now, } \frac{V^2 a_p \mu_L^{0.2} \rho_g}{g \rho_L} = 0.23$$

$$\text{Therefore, flooding velocity, } V = 10.182 \text{ ft/s}$$

Here, allowable vapor velocity is estimated to be 50 to 70% of the flooding velocity (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003, p. 698), which is used to determine the column diameter. Considering the absorber tower is designed for the gas velocity at 50% of the flooding velocity.

Maximum allowable vapor velocity $V_{\text{actual}} = 0.50 \times 10.182 \text{ ft/s} = 5.091 \text{ ft/s} = 1.552 \text{ m/s}$

Volumetric flow rate of gas $Q = \frac{G}{\rho_g} = 3.25 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

Cross-sectional area, $A = \frac{Q}{V_{\text{actual}}} = 2.097 \text{ m}^2$

Thus, $D = 1.63 \text{ m}$

Therefore, the diameter of the tank is $1.63 \text{ m} = 1.70 \text{ m}$ approximately.

Height calculation

Number of overall gas phase transfer unit (Peters, M. S., & Timmerhaus, K. D. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (4th ed., p. 703). McGraw-Hill.)

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \frac{(1-y)l_m}{(1-y)(y^*-y)} dy$$

When the gas is dilute $(1-y)_{lm} = (1-y)$

The reaction at the interface is very instantaneous that, $y^* = 0$

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_2}^{y_1} \frac{1}{y} dy$$

Here $y_1 =$ Input mole fraction of $\text{SO}_3 = 0.00157$

And $y_2 =$ Output mole fraction of $\text{SO}_3 = 0.0000158$

So, $N_{OG} = 4.598$

Now, the height of an overall gas phase transfer unit is calculated using Onda's method (Towler and Sinnott, 2013, p. 901)

$$\frac{a_w}{a} = 1 - \exp \left[-0.45 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_L} \right)^{0.75} \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a \mu_L} \right)^{0.1} \left(\frac{L_w^{*2} a}{\rho_L^2 g} \right)^{-0.05} \left(\frac{L_w^{*2}}{\rho_L \sigma_L a} \right)^{0.2} \right]$$

Here, $a = 253 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R. (2013))

σ_c for ceramic = $61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$. (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R. (2013))

σ_L for 98% sulfuric acid = 0.05 N/m (Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

$\mu_L =$ Viscosity of liquid $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.0063 \text{ Pa.s}$ (Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

Density of 98% liquid H₂SO₄, $\rho_L = 1797.6 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (Norfalco_sulfuric_acid_handbook.Pdf, n.d.)

$$L_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of liquid H}_2\text{SO}_4}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = 0.053 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{So, } a_w = 28.52 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$$

Here,

$$\text{Packing size } d_p = 1.0 \text{ inch} = 0.0254 \text{ m}$$

Association parameter of the solvent H₂SO₄, $\phi = 1$

The molecular weight of solvent B (98% H₂SO₄), $M_B = 98 \text{ kg/kmol}$

$$T = (273 + 70) = 343 \text{ K}$$

Viscosity of B (H₂SO₄), $\mu_B = 0.0063 \text{ Pa.s}$

Solute (SO₃) molar volume at the boiling point = V_A

Using the table 18.2 -4 for atomic and molar volumes at the normal boiling point

[Geankoplis, C. J., Curry, D., & Allison, R. (2018). Transport processes and separation process principles (5th ed.). Pearson.]

$$V_A = (S) + 3(O)$$

$$= (25.6 + 3 \times 7.4) \times 10^{-3} = 0.0478 \text{ m}^3/\text{kmol}$$

$$D_L = 1.173 \times 10^{-16} (\phi M_B)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{T}{\mu_B V_A^{0.6}} \quad (\text{Geankoplis, 2018,})$$

$$\text{So, } D_L = 3.919 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$$

Therefore,

$$k_L \left(\frac{\rho_L}{\mu_L g} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.0051 \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a_w \mu_L} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\mu_L}{\rho_L D_L} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (ad_p)^{0.4}$$

$$\text{Or, } k_L = 1.627 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m/s}$$

Now, Viscosity of gas (SO₃), $\mu_v = 2.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg/ms}$ [at 70°C]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Density of gas (SO}_3\text{) at 70}^\circ\text{C, } \rho_v &= \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 80 \times 10^{-3}}{8.314 \times 303} \\ &= 2.842 \text{ kg/m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

Where, Operating pressure, $P = 1 \text{ atm}$

The sum of the structural volume increments of A (SO_3),

$$\sum V_{A,i} = 17 + 5.48 \times 3 = 33.44$$

The sum of the structural volume increments of B (Other gases),

$$\sum V_{B,i} = (41.1 + 5.69 \times 2 + 5.48 \times 2 + 12.7) = 76.14$$

The molecular weight of A (SO_3), $M_A = 80 \text{ kg/kmol}$

Molecular weight of B, $M_B = 27.558 \text{ kg/kmol}$

Temperature, $T = 343 \text{ K}$

For packing sizes above 15 mm, $K_5 = 5.23$

Hence,

$$D_v = \frac{1 \times 10^{-7} (T)^{1.75} \left(\frac{1}{M_A} + \frac{1}{M_B} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P \left[\sum V_{A,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} + \sum V_{B,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} \right]^2}$$

So, $D_v = 1.099 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

$$\text{Now, } V_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of Gas stream}}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = \frac{3.32}{2.097} = 1.526 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

So, $k_G = 5.76 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{.s.atm}$

Now, the molar gas flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$G_m = \frac{V_w}{\text{molecular weight of gas}} = 0.01908 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

And molar liquid flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$L_m = \frac{L_w}{\text{molecular weight of liquid}} = 0.00052 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{Height of the gas film transfer unit, } H_G = \frac{G_m}{K_G a_w P} = 1.161 \text{ m}$$

$$C_T = \frac{\rho L}{\text{Molecular weight of solvent}} = 19.97 \text{ kmol/m}^3$$

$$\text{Height of the liquid film transfer unit, } H_L = \frac{L_m}{K_L a_w C_T} = 0.5597 \text{ m}$$

Now, the overall height of the transfer unit based on concentration driving force,

$$H_{OG} = H_G + (mG_m/L_m) \times H_L$$

According to Colburn (1939), the optimum value for the term mG_m/L_m will lie between 0.7 - 0.8. Taking 0.7 for calculation,

$$H_{OG} = 1.161 + 0.7 \times 0.559 = 1.553 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Now the height of the packing, } Z = H_{OG} \times N_{OG} = 1.553 \times 4.59 = 7.142 \text{ m}$$

Calculated Diameter: 1.63 m approximately.

Packing height: 7.15 m approximately.

8.2.3 Sizing of Air-Drying Tower

Packing material: (random packing) Intalox saddles ceramic. (Peters, M. S., Timmerhaus, K. D., & West, R. E. (2003). Plant design and economics for chemical engineers (6th ed., p. 690). McGraw-Hill)

Nominal size, $d_p = 2.0$ inch

Porosity, $\epsilon = 0.18$

Packing factor $a_p/\epsilon^3 = 130 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft}^3$

Diameter Calculation

Mass flow rate of liquid at the bottom of the tower,

$$L = 12910.5 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 3.58 \text{ kg/s}$$

At 37.78 °C,

Density of 97% Sulfuric Acid, $\rho_L = 1816.6 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and viscosity = 12 cp (Author(s). (Year).

Corrosion of carbon steel pipes and tanks by concentrated sulfuric acid: A review.

ResearchGate. URL)

Mass flow rate of gas at the bottom of the tower,

$$G = 13306.17 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 3.696 \text{ kg/s}$$

The average molecular weight of the gas,

$$M_{\text{avg}} = (0.0099 \times 18 + 0.231 \times 32 + 0.759 \times 28) = 28.822 \text{ kg/kmol}$$

$$\text{The density of gas } \rho_g = \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 28.822}{8.314 \times (37.78 + 273)} = 1.131 \text{ kg/m}^3 = 0.0706 \text{ lb/ft}^3$$

Now, from figure (16-20) (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003, p. 698)

Figure 37: Correlation for estimating flooding rate in packed towers.

$$X \text{ value} = \frac{L}{G} \times \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\rho_L} \right)^{0.5} = 0.024$$

$$Y \text{ value} = 0.2$$

$$\text{Now, } \frac{V^2 a_p \mu_L^{0.2} \rho_g}{g \rho_L} = 0.2$$

Therefore, flooding velocity, $V = 6.96 \text{ ft/s}$

Here, allowable vapor velocity is estimated to be 50 to 70% of the flooding velocity (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003, p. 698), which is used to determine the column diameter. Considering the absorber tower is designed for the gas velocity at 50% of the flooding velocity.

$$\text{Maximum allowable vapor velocity } V_{\text{actual}} = 0.50 \times 6.96 \text{ ft/s} = 3.48 \text{ ft/s} = 1.06 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{Volumetric flow rate of gas } Q = \frac{G}{\rho_g} = 3.266 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

$$\text{Cross-sectional area, } A = \frac{Q}{v_{\text{actual}}} = 3.081 \text{ m}^2$$

Thus, $D = 1.98 \text{ m}$

Therefore, the diameter of the tank is $1.98 \text{ m} = 2 \text{ m}$ approximately.

Height calculation

Number of overall gas phase transfer unit (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003, p. 703)

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \frac{(1-y)l_m}{(1-y)(y^*-y)} dy$$

When the gas is dilute $(1-y)l_m = (1-y)$

The reaction at the interface is very instantaneous that, $y^* = 0$

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_2}^{y_1} \frac{1}{y} dy$$

Here $y_1 =$ Input mole fraction of $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 0.0099$

And $y_2 =$ Output mole fraction of $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 0.000099$

$$N_{OG} = 9.21 \text{ m}$$

Now, the height of an overall gas phase transfer unit is calculated using Onda's method (Towler and Sinnott, 2013, p. 901)

$$\frac{a_w}{a} = 1 - \exp \left[-0.45 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_L} \right)^{0.75} \left(\frac{L_w}{a\mu_L} \right)^{0.1} \left(\frac{L_w^2 a}{\rho_L^2 g} \right)^{-0.05} \left(\frac{L_w^2}{\rho_L \sigma_L a} \right)^{0.2} \right]$$

Here, $a = 108 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (Towler and Sinnott, 2013, p. 890) (Coulson et al., 2005)

σ_c for ceramic $= 61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N/m}$ (Towler and Sinnott, 2013, p. 903)

σ_L for 98% sulfuric acid $= 0.05 \text{ N/m}$ (Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

$\mu_L =$ Viscosity of liquid $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.018 \text{ Pa.s}$ (Big Chemical Encyclopedia, n.d.)

Density of 98% liquid H_2SO_4 , $\rho_L = 1826.1 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (Norfalco_sulfuric_acid_handbook.Pdf, n.d.)

$$L_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of liquid } \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = 1.152 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{So, } a_w = 42.355 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$$

As the mole fraction of solute is very less, it is a dilute solution and the gas phase mass transfer function dominates.

Now, Viscosity of H₂O, $\mu_v = 1.87 \times 10^{-5}$ kg/ms [at 70°C]

Density of gas (H₂O) at 70°C, $\rho_v = \frac{PM}{RT} = 1.158$ kg/m³

Where, Operating pressure, P = 1 atm

The sum of the structural volume increments of A (H₂O),

$$\sum V_{A,i} = 9.44$$

The sum of the structural volume increments of B (Other gases),

$$\sum V_{B,i} = 20.1$$

The molecular weight of A (SO₃), M_A = 18 kg/kmol

Molecular weight of B, M_B = 28.644 kg/kmol

Temperature, T = 310.4 K

For packing sizes above 15 mm, K₅ = 5.23

Hence,

$$D_v = \frac{1 \times 10^{-7} (T)^{1.75} \left(\frac{1}{M_A} + \frac{1}{M_B} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P \left[\sum V_{A,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} + \sum V_{B,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} \right]^2}$$

So, $D_v = 2.99 \times 10^{-5}$ m²/s

Now, $V_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of Gas stream}}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = 1.199$ kg/m²s

So, $k_G = 1.55 \times 10^{-3}$ kmol/m².s.atm

Now, the molar gas flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$G_m = \frac{V_w}{\text{molecular weight of gas}} = 0.04162 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

And molar liquid flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$\text{Height of the gas film transfer unit, } H_G = \frac{G_m}{K_G a_w P} = 0.6311 \text{ m}$$

$H_{OG} = H_G = 0.631$ m

Now the height of the packing, $Z = H_{OG} \times N_{OG} = 0.631 \times 9.21 = 5.81 \text{ m}$

Calculated Diameter: 2 m approximately.

Packing height: 5.81 m approximately.

8.2.4 Design of 4-Bed Converter

The reaction occurring inside every bed of the converter is,

The rate expression of this reaction is expressed using the following equations. (Hill, 1977)

$$r_m = \frac{k_1 P_{\text{SO}_2} P_{\text{O}_2} - k_2 P_{\text{SO}_3} P_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P_{\text{SO}_2}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (5.1)$$

Where, P_A is the partial pressure of the correspondent compound, r_m is the rate of the reaction and k_1 and k_2 are determined using equation 5.2 and 5.3. In these equations k_1 and k_2 are represented in moles/(s g-catalyst atm^{3/2}) and moles/(s g-catalyst atm) respectively.

$$\ln k_1 = 12.07 - \frac{31000}{RT} \dots \dots \dots (5.2)$$

$$\ln k_2 = 22.75 - \frac{53600}{RT} \dots \dots \dots (5.3)$$

Here, T is the average reaction temperature in kelvin and R is the gas constant in cal/mol-K which is 1.98 cal/mol-K.

The most important parameter to define the catalytic bed of the converter are diameter, D , bed height, z , conversion rate, f , temperature, T , density of the packing material, ρ_B , concentration of the reactant, C_A , velocity of the flow, u , mass flow, G , heat capacity, C_p , and heat of reaction, ΔH . These variables are related to each other using the following equations. They are derived from the material balance and energy balance equation of the catalytic bed.

$$GC_p(T - T_0) = C_{A0}u_0(f - f_0)(-\Delta H) \dots \dots \dots (5.4)$$

$$C_{A0}u_0(f - f_0) = r_m(z - z_0)\rho_B \dots \dots \dots (5.5)$$

For each of the beds, these equations are used to determine the bed height, and outlet stream temperature of the catalytic bed. For every bed of this converter,

Bed diameter, $D = 5\text{m}$ (assumed)

Bed area, $A_c = \frac{\pi}{4} D^2$

Heat capacity, $C_p = 1.046 \text{ J/gK}$

Density of the packing material, $\rho_B = 550 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Heat of reaction, $\Delta H = -24.60 + 1.99 \times 10^{-3} T \text{ kcal/mol}$

$$\text{Mass flow, } G = 304.6 \times (0.79 \times 28 + 0.32 \times 0.06 + 0.15 \times 64) + \frac{152.3 \times (0.21 \times 32 + 0.79 \times 28) \times 1000}{A_C \times 3600}$$

$$= 199.01 \text{ g/m}^2\text{s}$$

Initial concentration of $\text{SO}_2 \times$ initial velocity of SO_2 , $C_{A0}u_0 = 0.6467 \text{ mol/m}^2\text{s}$

The process is done in atmospheric pressure. Therefore, the partial pressure would be the mole fraction of the compounds.

Table 40: Development of the partial pressure equation for different component.

Compound	Initial molar flow (kmol/hr)	Final molar flow (kmol/hr)	Partial Pressure (atm)
SO_2	45.69	$45.69 (1 - f)$	$45.69 (1 - f) / 456.9 - 22.845f$
O_2	50.263	$50.263 - 22.845f$	$(50.263 - 22.845f) / 456.9 - 22.845f$
SO_3	0	$45.69f$	$45.69f / 456.9 - 22.845f$
N_2	360.947	360.947	$360.947 / 456.9 - 22.845f$

For every small change in conversion fraction, the partial pressure is determined using the equations of table 1. The value of k_1 and k_2 are determined using equation 5.2 and 5.3. Later, these values are used to find the rate of reaction (equation 5.1) for that condition. For the change in conversion fraction, required height is determined using equation 5.5. Finally, for the particular fraction, outlet temperature is determined using equation 5.4. The calculations are done in a matlab code. The code is added in the appendices. The results of the calculation are summarized following table.

Table 41: Result of the bed height calculation.

Bed No.	Conversion, f	Inlet Temperature (°C)	Outlet Temperature (°C)	Bed height, z (m)
1	0.65	675	868.18	2.082
2	0.9	655	728.69	1.308
3	0.95	655	674.77	1.1488
4	0.99	575	586.91	1.0534

8.2.5 Sizing of T-102: Oleum Dilution Tank

Material of synthesis: Carbon Steel.

Table 42: Calculation for volumetric flowrate.

	Mass flowrate (kg/hr)	Specific Gravity	Density (kg/m ³)	Volume flowrate (m ³ /h)
Oleum inlet stream	18.4211	1.37625	1376.25	0.013385
Acid inlet stream	12910.53	1.42532	1425.32	9.05798512
DM water inlet stream	1233.48	1	1000	1.23347963
Sulfuric Acid Outlet stream	-	-	-	10.3048497

Residence time is assumed to be 30 min

So, Volume of storage tank = 5.1524 m³

Height of the tank is assumed to be 4 m

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Diameter of the tank} &= 2 \times \sqrt{\frac{A}{\pi}} \\ &= 1.28 \text{ m} \end{aligned}$$

8.2.7 Sizing of Heat exchanger

Selection of Shell and tube heat exchanger

Shell and tube heat exchangers were selected in this sulfuric acid plant because they efficiently handle highly corrosive, high-temperature streams (like hot SO₂, SO₃, air, water) with rugged construction from special alloys, offering durability, ease of maintenance (tube plugging), and reliable heat recovery for steam generation, outperforming other types in demanding chemical environments despite potentially larger size for gas-to-gas duties.

Sizing of HE 101

Tube side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate(kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., t ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Waste heat boiler	304.6	1300	667	1.366×10 ⁵	-7.017×10 ⁶	7.15×10 ⁶

Shell side: Water in, steam out						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., T ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Waste heat boiler	149.68	30	150	- 4.259×10 ⁷	-3.543×10 ⁷	-7.15×10 ⁶

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
868.39°C	5.275	0.094	853.4°C	1	2	40.54	160

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = 1.366 \times 10^5 + 7.017 \times 10^6 = 7.15 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(1300 - 150) - (667 - 30)}{\ln \frac{1300 - 150}{667 - 30}} = 868.39^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{1300 - 667}{150 - 30} = 5.275$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{150 - 30}{1300 - 30} = 0.094$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.98$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

Corrected LMTD = LMTD \times F = 853.4 $^\circ$ C

Overall U = 40.54 W/m². $^\circ$ C (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{7.15 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 853.4 \times 40.54} = 57.407 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side,

$$OD = \frac{3}{4} \text{ inch}$$

$$BWG = 14$$

$$ID = 0.584 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{Surface per line ft.} = 0.1963 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft.} = 0.0598 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}$$

Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 6 \times 0.0598 = 0.3588 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{57.407}{0.3588} = 160$$

Sizing of HE 102

Shell side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate(kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t_1 ($^\circ$ C)	Outlet Temp., t_2 ($^\circ$ C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Cooler	442	505.5	110	-1.12×10^7	-1.7×10^7	6.04×10^6

Tubel side: Water						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., T ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Cooler	7937	30	40	- 1.116×10 ⁷	-1.72×10 ⁷	6.04×10 ⁶

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
343.82°C	39.55	0.021	215.5°C	1	2	220	1560

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -1.116 \times 10^7 + 1.72 \times 10^7 = 6.04 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(505.5 - 40) - (110 - 30)}{\ln \frac{505.5 - 40}{110 - 30}} = 343.82^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{505.5 - 110}{40 - 30} = 39.55$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{40 - 30}{505.5 - 30} = 0.021$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.63$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = LMTD \times F = 215.5^\circ\text{C}$$

Number of tubes, $N_t = \frac{132.5}{0.25} = 530$

Overall heat transfer coefficient of Gases-water is range of 20-300 W/m². °C .

Therefore, $U = 20$ W/m². °C is selected (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{6.04 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 215.5 \times 20} = 390 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side, 20mm o.d., 16mm i.d., 4 m long tubes

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 4 \times 20 \times 10^{-3} \pi = 0.25 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Number of tubes, } N_t = \frac{390}{0.25} = 1560$$

Sizing of HE 103

Shell side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t_1 (°C)	Outlet Temp., t_2 (°C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas reheater	416.3	291.7	377	-3.442×10^6	-2.332×10^6	-1.11×10^6

Tube side: Steam						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T_1 (°C)	Outlet Temp., T_2 (°C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas reheater	1221	400	380	- 2.797×10^8	- 2.808×10^8	1.1×10^6

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
48.78°C	0.23	0.79	41.463°C	1	2	128.37	160

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -2.797 \times 10^8 + 2.808 \times 10^8 = 1.1 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(T_2 - t_1) - (T_1 - t_2)}{\ln \frac{T_2 - t_1}{T_1 - t_2}} = \frac{(380 - 291.7) - (400 - 377)}{\ln \frac{380 - 291.7}{400 - 377}} = 48.78^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{T_1 - T_2}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{400 - 380}{377 - 291.7} = 0.23$$

$$P = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{T_1 - t} = \frac{377 - 291.7}{400 - 291.7} = 0.79$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.85$ (Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West)

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = LMTD \times F = 41.463^\circ\text{C}$$

Overall $U = 128.37 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{1.1 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 41.463 \times 128.37} = 57.407 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side,

$$\text{OD} = 3/4 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{BWG} = 14$$

$$\text{ID} = 0.584 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{Surface per line ft.} = 0.1963 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft.} = 0.0598 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}$$

Let, the length of the tube, $L = 6 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 6 \times 0.0598 = 0.3588 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{57.407}{0.3588} = 160$$

Sizing of HE 104

Shell side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., $t_1(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Outlet Temp., $t_2(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas cooler	442	328.3	70	-3.173×10^6	-6.652×10^6	3.479×10^6

Tube side: Water						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., $T_1(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Outlet Temp., $T_2(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas cooler	1145	30	70	-3.256×10^8	-3.222×10^8	-3.479×10^6

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot ^{\circ}\text{C}$)	No. of tubes
117.04 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	6.46	0.134	96.2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	1	2	175	160

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{\text{in}} - Q_{\text{out}} = -3.173 \times 10^6 + 6.652 \times 10^6 = 3.479 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(328.3 - 70) - (70 - 30)}{\ln \frac{328.3 - 70}{70 - 30}} = 117.04^{\circ}\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{328.3 - 70}{70 - 30} = 6.46$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{70 - 30}{328.3 - 30} = 0.134$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.822$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

Corrected LMTD = LMTD \times $F = 96.2^{\circ}\text{C}$

Overall $U = 175 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot ^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{3.479 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 96.2 \times 175} = 57.404 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side, OD = $\frac{3}{4}$ inch and BWG = 14

ID = 0.584 inch

Surface per line ft. = 0.1963 ft²/ft. = 0.0598 m²/m

Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m

Area of one tube = 6 × 0.0598 = 0.3588 m²

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{57.404}{0.3588} = 160$$

Sizing of HE 105

Shell side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., t ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas cooler	442	652.9	597	-8.470 × 10 ⁶	-9.356 × 10 ⁶	886 × 10 ³

Tube side: Water						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., T ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas cooler	246	30	80	-6.714 × 10 ⁷	-6.625 × 10 ⁷	-886 × 10 ³

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
569.94°C	1.118	0.08	568.8°C	1	2	20	61

Heat duty, Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -8.470 × 10⁶ + 9.356 × 10⁶ = 886 × 10³ (Tube side)

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(652.9 - 80) - (597 - 30)}{\ln \frac{652.9 - 80}{597 - 30}} = 569.94^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{652.9 - 597}{80 - 30} = 1.118$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{80 - 30}{652.9 - 30} = 0.08$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.998$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = \text{LMTD} \times F = 568.8^\circ\text{C}$$

Overall $U = 20 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{886 \times 10^3 \times 1000}{3600 \times 568.8 \times 20} = 21.63 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side,

$$\text{OD} = 3/4 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{BWG} = 14$$

$$\text{ID} = 0.584 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{Surface per line ft.} = 0.1963 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft.} = 0.0598 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}$$

Let, the length of the tube, $L = 6 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 6 \times 0.0598 = 0.3588 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{21.63}{0.3588} = 61$$

Sizing of HE 106

Shell side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t_1 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Outlet Temp., t_2 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas cooler	442	660.6	487	-8.227×10^6	-1.103×10^7	2.803×10^6

Tube side: Water						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., T ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Gas cooler	737.3	30	80	- 2.098×10 ⁸	-2.070×10 ⁸	-2.80×10 ⁶

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
516.34°C	3.5	0.08	511.2°C	1	2	26.53	160

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -8.227 \times 10^6 + 1.103 \times 10^7 = 2.803 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(660.6 - 80) - (487 - 30)}{\ln \frac{660.6 - 80}{487 - 30}} = 516.34^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{660.6 - 487}{80 - 30} = 3.5$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{80 - 30}{660.6 - 30} = 0.08$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.99$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = LMTD \times F = 511.2^\circ\text{C}$$

Overall $U = 26.53 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{2.803 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 511.2 \times 26.53} = 57.41 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side, $OD = \frac{3}{4}$ inch and BWG = 14

$$ID = 0.584 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{Surface per line ft.} = 0.1963 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft.} = 0.0598 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}$$

Let, the length of the tube, $L = 6 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 6 \times 0.0598 = 0.3588 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{57.41}{0.3588} = 160$$

Sizing of HE 107

Shell side: Gas						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t_1 (°C)	Outlet Temp., t_2 (°C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Heat exchanger	442	110	70	-1.7×10^7	-1.8×10^7	5.70×10^5

Tube side: Water						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T_1 (°C)	Outlet Temp., T_2 (°C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Heat exchanger	250	30	60	-7.1×10^7	-7.054×10^7	-5.70×10^5

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
44.814°C	1.33	0.375	41.67702°C	1	2	26.53	400

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -7.1 \times 10^7 + 7.054 \times 10^7 = -5.70 \times 10^5$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(110 - 60) - (70 - 30)}{\ln \frac{110 - 60}{70 - 30}} = 44.814^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{110 - 70}{60 - 30} = 1.33$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{60 - 30}{110 - 30} = 0.375$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.93$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = LMTD \times F = 41.67702^\circ\text{C}$$

Overall $U = 26.53 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{5.70 \times 10^5 \times 1000}{3600 \times 41.67702 \times 26.53} = 143.198 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side,

$$\text{OD} = 3/4 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{BWG} = 14$$

$$\text{ID} = 0.584 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{Surface per line ft.} = 0.1963 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft.} = 0.0598 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}$$

Let, the length of the tube, $L = 6 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 6 \times 0.0598 = 0.3588 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{143.198}{0.3588} = 400$$

Sizing of HE 108

Shell side: Steam						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t_1 (°C)	Outlet Temp., t_2 (°C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Heat exchanger	27	400	80	-6.08×10^6	-7.5×10^6	1.42×10^6

Tube side: acid						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T_1 (°C)	Outlet Temp., T_2 (°C)	Q_{in} (kJ/h)	Q_{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Heat exchanger	276	30	70	-2.06×10^8	-2.05×10^8	-1.42×10^6

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
148.378°C	8.0	0.108	136.5°C	1	2	26.53	304

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -2.06 \times 10^8 + 2.05 \times 10^8 = -1.42 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(400 - 70) - (80 - 30)}{\ln \frac{400 - 70}{80 - 30}} = 148.378^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{400 - 80}{70 - 30} = 8 \quad \text{and} \quad P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{70 - 30}{400 - 30} = 0.108$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.92$ (Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West)

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = LMTD \times F = 136.5^\circ\text{C}$$

Overall $U = 26.53 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{1.42 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 136.5 \times 26.53} = 108.922 \text{ m}^2$$

On the tube side, OD = $\frac{3}{4}$ inch, BWG = 14 and ID = 0.584 inch

Surface per line ft. = 0.1963 ft²/ft. = 0.0598 m²/m

Let, the length of the tube, L = 6 m

Area of one tube = 6 × 0.0598 = 0.3588 m²

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{108.922}{0.3588} = 304$$

Sizing of HE 109

Shell side: oleum						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., t ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., t ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Heat exchanger	442	110	40	-3.22 × 10 ⁸	-3.3 × 10 ⁸	5.27 × 10 ⁶

Tube side: water						
Name	Flow rate (kmol/h)	Inlet Temp., T ₁ (°C)	Outlet Temp., T ₂ (°C)	Q _{in} (kJ/h)	Q _{out} (kJ/h)	Heat duty (kJ/h)
Heat exchanger	8658	30	38	- 2.463 × 10 ⁹	-2.5 × 10 ⁹	-5.27 × 10 ⁶

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
31.4°C	8.75	0.1	29.202	1	2	298	469

$$\text{Heat duty, } Q = Q_{\text{in}} - Q_{\text{out}} = -2.463 \times 10^9 + 2.5 \times 10^9 = -5.27 \times 10^6 \text{ (Tube side)}$$

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(110 - 38) - (40 - 30)}{\ln \frac{110 - 38}{40 - 30}} = 31.4^\circ\text{C (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{110 - 40}{38 - 30} = 8.75$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{38 - 30}{110 - 30} = 0.1$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.93$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

$$\text{Corrected LMTD} = \text{LMTD} \times F = 29.202^\circ\text{C}$$

Overall $U = 298 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{5.27 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 29.202 \times 298} = 168.22 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side,

$$\text{OD} = 3/4 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{BWG} = 14$$

$$\text{ID} = 0.584 \text{ inch}$$

$$\text{Surface per line ft.} = 0.1963 \text{ ft}^2/\text{ft.} = 0.0598 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}$$

Let, the length of the tube, $L = 6 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 6 \times 0.0598 = 0.3588 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{No. of tubes, } N = \frac{A}{0.3588} = \frac{168.22}{0.3588} = 469$$

8.2.6 Sizing of FL-101

Inlet Air Mass Flow, $m_1 = 13,307.837$ kg/hr

Outlet Air Mass Flow, $m_2 = 13,307.457$ kg/hr

Dust Load (Solids Removed) = $m_1 - m_2 = 0.38$ kg/hr

Operating Temperature: 25°C

Air Density: 1.184 kg/m³ (Standard Air)

$$\text{Flow, } Q = \frac{13,307.837}{1.184} = 11,240 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$$

Selected ACR: 1.5 m/min ($90 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{m}^2\text{hr}}$)

Flow Rate (Q): 187.3 m³/min

$$\text{Area} = \text{Flow Rate} / \text{ACR Calculation: Area} = \frac{187.3}{1.5} = 124.9 \text{ m}^2$$

Filter Bag Selection for Standard industrial bag dimensions are selected for ease of procurement.

Bag Diameter (D): 150 mm (0.15 m)

Bag Length (L): 3000 mm (3.0 m)

$$\text{Area per Bag} = 3.1416 \times 0.15 \times 3.0 = 1.414 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Number of Bags} = \frac{\text{Total Area}}{\text{Area per Bag Calculation}}: N = \frac{124.9}{1.414} = 88.3$$

To ensure a symmetrical tube sheet layout and provide a safety factor, we round up to the nearest square matrix.

Selected Arrangement: 10 x 10 Matrix

Total Bags Required: 100

8.2.7 Sizing of T-102: Sulfuric Acid Circulation Tank

Mass flow rate of Stream 18, $m_{22} = 41806.87 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$

Concentration of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 98\%$

Density of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 1.815 \frac{\text{gm}}{\text{cm}^3} = 1815 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

Let, Storage tank height to diameter ratio, $\frac{h}{d} = 1.5$

Volumetric flow rate, $Q = \frac{41806.87 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}}{1815 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}} = 23.034 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$

Assumed Retention time, $t = 30 \text{ min} = 0.5 \text{ hr}$

So, Volume of the tank, $V_{\text{tank}} = 23.034 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}} \times 0.5 \text{ hr} = 11.517 \text{ m}^3$

Overdesign = 5%

So, Volume of the tank with Overdesign, $V = (11.517 \times 1.05) \text{ m}^3 = 12.09 \text{ m}^3$

Let, number of tanks, $N = 1$

$$\text{or, } \frac{1}{4} N \pi d^2 h = 12.09$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{1}{4} \pi d^2 (1.5d) = 12.09$$

$$\therefore d = \sqrt[3]{\frac{12.09 \times 4}{\pi \times 1.5}} = 2.2 \text{ m}$$

$$\therefore h = 1.5d = 1.5 \times 2.2 \text{ m} = 3.3 \text{ m}$$

8.2.8 Sizing of Tank-103: Sulfuric Acid Storage Tank

Mass flow rate of Stream 22, $m_{25} = 4166.67 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$

Concentration of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 98\%$

Density of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 1.84 \frac{\text{gm}}{\text{cm}^3} = 1840 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

Let, Storage tank height to diameter ratio, $\frac{h}{d} = 1.5$

Volumetric flow rate, $Q = \frac{4166.67 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}}{1840 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}} = 2.265 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$

Retention time, $t = 7 \text{ days} = 168 \text{ hr}$

So, Volume of the tank, $V_{\text{tank}} = 2.265 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}} \times 168 \text{ hr} = 380.44 \text{ m}^3$

Overdesign = 5%

Let, number of tanks, $N = 2$

So, Volume of the tank with Overdesign, $V = (380.44 \times 1.05) \text{ m}^3 = 400 \text{ m}^3$

or, $\frac{1}{4} N \pi d^2 h = 400$

or, $\frac{1}{4} \pi d^2 (1.5d) = 200$

$\therefore d = \sqrt[3]{\frac{200 \times 4}{\pi \times 1.5}} = 5.5 \text{ m}$

$\therefore h = 1.5d = 1.5 \times 5.5 \text{ m} = 8.3 \text{ m}$

8.2.9 Sizing of Tank-104: Oleum Storage Tank

Mass flow rate of Stream 27, $m_{13} = 397.368 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}$

Concentration of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 98\%$

Density of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 1.77 \frac{\text{gm}}{\text{cm}^3} = 1770 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

Let, Storage tank height to diameter ratio, $\frac{h}{d} = 1.5$

Volumetric flow rate, $Q = \frac{397.368 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}}{1770 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}}} = 0.225 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$

Retention time, $t = 7 \text{ days} = 168 \text{ hr}$

So, Volume of the tank, $V_{\text{tank}} = 0.225 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}} \times 168 \text{ hr} = 37.72 \text{ m}^3$

Overdesign = 5%

Let, number of tanks, $N = 1$

So, Volume of the tank with Overdesign, $V = (37.72 \times 1.05) \text{ m}^3 = 39.6 \text{ m}^3$

$$\text{or, } \frac{1}{4} \pi d^2 h = 39.6$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{1}{4} \pi d^2 (1.5d) = 39.6$$

$$\therefore d = \sqrt[3]{\frac{39.6 \times 4}{\pi \times 1.5}} = 3.25 \text{ m}$$

$$\therefore h = 1.5d = 1.5 \times 3.25 \text{ m} = 4.8 \text{ m}$$

9. INDIVIDUAL DESIGN

9.1 Design of Heat Exchanger (HE-102)

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Tube Side: Cooling Water.
 Shell Side: Hot gas mixture.
 Flow type: Counter Current.

Table 43: Physical properties of fluids at their mean temperature.

Physical property at fluid mean temperature, T_m	Gas Mixture (Shell Side)	Cooling Water (Tube side)
Density, ρ (kg/m^3)	0.704	994
Viscosity, μ (cp)	0.027	0.72
Thermal Conductivity, k ($W/m^\circ C$)	0.042	0.72
Specific heat, c_p ($kJ/kg \cdot k$)	0.962	4.2

Table 44: LMTD and number of tubes.

LMTD	R	P	Corr. LMTD	No. of shell passes	No. of tube passes	Overall, U (W/m ² .°C)	No. of tubes
343.82°C	30.55	0.021	215.5°C	1	2	220	1560

Heat duty, $Q = Q_{in} - Q_{out} = -1.116 \times 10^7 + 1.72 \times 10^7 = 6.04 \times 10^6$ (Tube side)

$$LMTD = \frac{(t_1 - T_2) - (t_2 - T_1)}{\ln \frac{t_1 - T_2}{t_2 - T_1}} = \frac{(505.5 - 40) - (110 - 30)}{\ln \frac{505.5 - 40}{110 - 30}} = 343.82^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Counter flow)}$$

$$R = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{T_2 - T_1} = \frac{505.5 - 110}{40 - 30} = 39.55$$

$$P = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{t_1 - T_1} = \frac{40 - 30}{505.5 - 30} = 0.021$$

Corrected factor, $F = 0.63$ [Fig.14-4, pp 648, Max S. Peters, Klaus D. Timmerhaus, Ronald E. West]

Corrected LMTD = LMTD × F = 215.5 °C

Table 45: Overall heat transfer coefficient.

Hot fluid	Cold fluid	U (W/m ² .°C)
<i>Heat exchangers</i>		
Water	Water	800–1500
Organic solvents	Organic solvents	100–300
Light oils	Light oils	100–400
Heavy oils	Heavy oils	50–300
Gases	Gases	10–50
<i>Coolers</i>		
Organic solvents	Water	250–750
Light oils	Water	350–900
Heavy oils	Water	60–300
Gases	Water	20–300
Organic solvents	Brine	150–500
Water	Brine	600–1200
Gases	Brine	15–250
<i>Heaters</i>		
Steam	Water	1500–4000
Steam	Heavy oils	50–750
Dowtherm	Gases	30–300
Dowtherm	Heavy oils	50–300
Flue gases	Gases	20–200
Flue	Steam	30–100
	Hydrocarbon vapours	30–100

Overall heat transfer coefficient of Gases-water is range of 20-300 W/m². °C .

Therefore, U = 20 W/m². °C is selected (Table 19-1, pp 1050, Gavin, Towler)

$$\text{Area, } A = \frac{Q \times 1000}{3600 \times \text{corr.LMTD} \times U} = \frac{6.04 \times 10^6 \times 1000}{3600 \times 215.5 \times 20} = 390 \text{ m}^2$$

At tube side, 20mm o.d., 16mm i.d., 4 m long tubes

$$\text{Area of one tube} = 4 \times 20 \times 10^{-3} \pi = 0.25 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Number of tubes, } N_t = \frac{390}{0.25} = 1560$$

As the shell side fluid is relatively clean, we can use 1.25d_o triangular pitch:

$$\text{Bundle diameter, } D_b = 20 \left(\frac{1560}{0.249} \right)^{1/2.207} = 1050 \text{ mm}$$

Using a split-ring floating-head type.

From figure (Gavin, Towler), bundle diameter clearance = 72 mm

$$\text{Shell diameter, } D_s = 1050 + 72 = 1122 \text{ mm}$$

Tube side heat transfer coefficient:

Tube cross sectional area = $\frac{\pi}{4} \times 16^2 = 201 \text{ mm}^2$

Tube per pass = $\frac{1560}{2} = 780$

Total flow area = $780 \times 201 \times 10^{-6} = 0.16 \text{ m}^2$

Water mass velocity = $\frac{40}{0.16} = 250 \text{ kg/s.m}^2$

Water mean temperature = $\frac{30+40}{2} = 35^\circ\text{C}$

Water linear velocity = $\frac{250}{994} = 0.25 \text{ m/s}$

Using eq. 19.15,

$$\frac{h_i d_i}{k_f} = j_h \text{Re Pr}^{0.33} \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w}\right)^{0.14}$$

$$\text{Re} = \frac{\rho u d_i}{\mu} = \frac{994 \times 0.25 \times 16 \times 10^{-3}}{0.72 \times 10^{-3}} = 5500$$

$$\text{Pr} = \frac{C_p \mu}{k_f} = \frac{4.2 \times 10^3 \times 0.72 \times 10^{-3}}{0.62} = 4.88$$

Neglecting $\left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w}\right)^{0.14}$

$$\frac{L}{d_i} = \frac{4 \times 10^3}{16} = 250$$

From figure 19.23, $j_h = 4 \times 10^{-3}$

$$h_i = \frac{4 \times 10^{-3} \times 0.62}{16 \times 10^{-3}} \times 5500 \times (4.88)^{0.33} = 1438 \text{ W/m}^2\text{C}$$

Shell side heat transfer coefficient:

Choose baffle spacing as 1/5 shell diameter, $I_B = \frac{D_s}{5} = \frac{1122}{5} = 224.4 \text{ mm}$

Tube pitch, $P_t = 1.25 \times 20 = 25 \text{ mm}$

Cross flow area $A_s = \frac{(P_t - d_o) D_s I_B}{P_t} = \frac{(25 - 20)}{25} \times 1122 \times 224.4 \times 10^{-6} = 0.05 \text{ m}^2$

Gas mass velocity, $G_s = \frac{4.14 \text{ kg/s}}{0.05 \text{ m}^2} = 82.8 \text{ kg/s.m}^2$

Equivalent diameter, $d_e = \frac{1.10}{d_o} (P_t^2 - 0.917 \times d_o^2) = \frac{1.10}{20} (25^2 - 0.917 \times 20^2) = 14.2 \text{ mm}$

Mean shell temperature = $\frac{(505.5 + 110)}{2} = 307.75 \approx 308^\circ\text{C}$

Viscosity of gas = 0.027 cP

Thermal conductivity = 0.0426 W/m.°C

gas density = 0.704 kg/m³

heat capacity of gas = 0.962 kJ/ (kg K)

$Re = \frac{G_s d_e}{\mu} = \frac{82.8 \times 14.2 \times 10^{-3}}{0.0270 \times 10^{-3}} = 40000$

$Pr = \frac{C_p \mu}{k_f} = \frac{0.962 \times 10^3 \times 0.027 \times 10^{-3}}{0.0426} = 0.6097$

Choosing 25% baffle cut, this should be given a reasonable heat transfer coefficient without too large a pressure drops.

From figure: $j_h = 3 \times 10^{-3}$

Without viscosity correction term, $h_o = \frac{k_f}{d_e} \times j_h \text{Re} \text{Pr}^{1/3}$

$$= \frac{0.0426}{14.2 \times 10^{-3}} \times 3 \times 10^{-3} \times 40000 \times 0.6097^{1/3}$$

$$= 306 \text{ W/m}^2\text{°C}$$

Viscosity correction factor:

Mean temperature difference = $(308 - 35) \text{ °C} = 273 \text{ °C}$ across all resistances

Across water film = $\frac{U}{h_o} \times \Delta T = \frac{20}{306} \times 273 = 17.84 \text{ °C} \approx 18 \text{ °C}$

Mean wall temperature = $308 - 18 = 290 \text{ °C}$

Water viscosity at the wall, $\mu_w = 0.0942 \text{ cP}$

Viscosity, $\mu = 0.0264 \text{ cP}$

Now,

$$\left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w}\right)^{0.14} = 0.84$$

Insignificant.

Overall coefficient:

Thermal conductivity of Stainless steel 316L is $21.5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{°C}$

Take the fouling coefficients from Table. Air and industrial gases are range of 5000 – 10000 $\text{W/m}^2 \text{ °C}$. Take as highest value, 10000 $\text{W/m}^2 \text{ °C}$.

Cooling water (towers) are range of 3000 – 6000 $\text{W/m}^2 \text{ °C}$. Take as highest value, 6000 $\text{W/m}^2 \text{ °C}$

Fluid	Coefficient (W/m ² °C)	Factor (resistance) (m ² °C/W)
River water	3000–12.000	0.0003–0.0001
Sea water	1000–3000	0.001–0.0003
Cooling water (towers)	3000–6000	0.0003–0.00017
Towns water (soft)	3000–5000	0.0003–0.0002
Towns water (hard)	1000–2000	0.001–0.0005
Steam condensate	1500–5000	0.00067–0.0002
Steam (oil free)	4000–10.000	0.0025–0.0001
Steam (oil traces)	2000–5000	0.0005–0.0002
Refrigerated brine	3000–5000	0.0003–0.0002
Air and industrial gases	5000–10.000	0.0002–0.0001
Flue gases	2000–5000	0.0005–0.0002
Organic vapours	5000	0.0002
Organic liquids	5000	0.0002
Light hydrocarbons	5000	0.0002
Heavy hydrocarbons	2000	0.0005
Boiling organics	2500	0.0004
Condensing organics	5000	0.0002
Heat transfer fluids	5000	0.0002
Aqueous salt solutions	3000–5000	0.0003–0.0002

$$\frac{1}{U_o} = \frac{1}{h_o} + \frac{1}{h_{od}} + \frac{d_o \ln\left(\frac{d_o}{d_i}\right)}{2kw} + \frac{d_o}{d_i} \times \frac{1}{h_i} + \frac{1}{h_{id}} \times \frac{d_o}{d_i}$$

$$= \frac{1}{306} + \frac{1}{10000} + \frac{20 \times 10^{-3} \ln\left(\frac{20}{16}\right)}{2 \times 21.5} + \frac{20}{16} \times \frac{1}{1438} + \frac{1}{6000} \times \frac{20}{16}$$

$$U_o = 220 \text{ W/m}^2\text{°C}$$

Pressure drops:

Tube side

Tube side pressure drop is given by the equation 7.45, page-183, from “Process Heat Transfer” Tata McGraw Hill edition 1997 by Kern [84],

$$\Delta P_t = \frac{f G_t^2 L n}{5.22 \times 10^{10} D s \varphi_t}$$

Here, n= number of tube passes=2

L = length of a tube = 4m= 13 ft

G_t = Mass velocity through the tube = 1843440 lb/hr.ft²

D = tube side internal diameter = 0.0525 ft

φ_t = 1 [Assumption]

And also, s = specific gravity of the fluid through = 0.98090, f = friction factor. Friction factor is given by the figure 26, page 836, from “Process Heat Transfer” Tata McGraw Hill edition 1997 by Kern [84].

Reynolds number, $Re = 5500$. Corresponding friction factor, $f = 0.00030$

Now, we get the pressure drop,

$$\Delta P_t = \frac{0.0003 \times 1843440^2 \times 13 \times 2}{5.22 \times 10^{10} \times 0.0525 \times 0.9940 \times 1}$$

$$= 9.73 \text{ psi}$$

There is another source of pressure drop in tube side that is due to bending of tubes known as return pressure drop.

Now, the return pressure drops,

$$\Delta P_r = \frac{4n}{s} \times \frac{v^2}{2g} = \frac{4 \times 2 \times 0.82^2}{0.9940 \times 2 \times 32.17} = 0.084 \text{ psi}$$

Tube side pressure drops, $\Delta P_t = (9.73 + 0.084) \text{ psi}$
 $= 9.814 \text{ psi}$

This pressure drop is allowable as it is less than the maximum allowable pressure drop 10 psi.

Shell side:

Shell side pressure drop is given by the equation 7.44, page-184, from “Process Heat Transfer” Tata McGraw Hill edition 1997 by Kern [84],

$$\Delta P_s = \frac{f G_s^2 D_s (N + 1)}{5.22 \times 10^{10} D_e s \phi_t}$$

$$G_s = 61042.8 \text{ lb/hr.ft}^2$$

$$D_s = 3.68 \text{ ft}$$

$$N+1 = \frac{\text{length of the tube}}{\text{baffle spacing}} = \frac{12 \times L}{B} = \frac{12 \times 13}{8.83} = 18$$

Corresponding friction factor is given by the figure no. 29, page 839, from “Process Heat Transfer” Tata McGraw Hill edition 1997 by Kern [84],

$$f = 0.0016$$

$$\text{So, } \Delta P_s = \frac{0.0016 \times 61042.8^2 \times 3.68 \times 18}{5.22 \times 10^{10} \times 0.0466 \times 1.16 \times 1} = 0.14 \text{ psi}$$

This pressure drop is also less than the maximum allowable pressure drop 10 psi.

So, our proposed heat exchanger is thermally compatible to do its specific duty.

9.1.1 Mechanical Design

Material Selection and Justification

Stainless steel grade SS 416 was selected because the operating environment inside the shell is highly acidic due to the presence of corrosive gases and a significant amount of water. Although carbon steel is a cheaper alternative, it is not suitable for this service, as the combination of moisture and acidic gases would lead to rapid and severe corrosion. SS 416 offers excellent resistance to acids, alkalis, fresh water, and dry air, making it much more appropriate for this application. In water systems, the typical corrosion rate of carbon steel ranges from 0.41 to 0.76 mpy, whereas for stainless steel it is significantly lower, in the range of 0.0008 to 0.022 mpy. This large difference indicates a much longer service life and lower maintenance requirements for stainless steel. From a temperature standpoint, SS 416 can safely operate up to about 650 °C, which is well above the maximum operating temperature of our system (approximately 240 °C). While carbon steel can tolerate temperatures up to around 450 °C, it becomes susceptible to creep above 370 °C. In addition, prolonged exposure to elevated temperatures can cause graphitization in carbon steel, which reduces mechanical strength and increases the corrosion rate. Considering the highly corrosive environment, lower corrosion rate, better long-term reliability, and adequate temperature resistance, SS 416 was selected over carbon steel, despite its higher initial cost.

Shell side:

Operating pressure in shell side is around 101.3 kPa. Considering overpressure situation, we take around 15% more pressure than the

operating pressure while designing.

$$\text{Design pressure, } P_D = (101.3 \times 1.15) \text{ kPa} = 116.5 \text{ kPa} = 17 \text{ psi}$$

$$\text{Inlet temperature} = 505.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\text{Outlet temperature} = 110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$$

Shell thickness calculation:

$$P_D = 17 \text{ psi} = 0.0011952 \text{ kg} - \text{wt/mm}^2$$

Shell ID_s = 1122 mm

$$t_s = \frac{ID_s \times P_D}{2fj + P_D} + C$$

For stainless steel 416 (Grade ASTM A240),

Maximum allowable stress at 620°C is, $f = 18.5 \text{ kg/mm}^2$

Joint efficiency for welded butt joint, $j = 0.85$ (For welded butt joint) Corrosion allowance, $C = 4 \text{ mm}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, the shell thickness} &= \frac{1122 \times 0.0011952}{2 \times 18.5 \times 0.85 + 0.0011952} + 4 \\ &= 4 \text{ mm} \\ &= 0.16 \text{ inch} \end{aligned}$$

Nozzle diameter:

Let's the nozzle diameter, DN, then,

$$D = 1122 \text{ mm} = 44.17 \text{ inch}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D}{D_N} &< 4 \\ \gg D_N &> \frac{D}{4} \\ \gg D_N &> \frac{44.17}{4} \\ \gg D_N &> 11 \text{ inch} \end{aligned}$$

$$D_N = 10.75 \text{ inch} = 273 \text{ mm}$$

Nozzle thickness,

$$\begin{aligned} t_N &= \frac{P_D D_N}{2fj - P_D} + C \\ &= \left(\frac{0.0011952 \times 273.05}{2 \times 11.73 \times 0.85 - 0.0011952} + 4 \right) \text{ mm} \\ &= 4 \text{ mm} \\ &= 0.16 \text{ inch} \end{aligned}$$

Let us take the nozzle thickness 4.10 mm

Head thickness:

Head thickness is given by,

$$t_H = \frac{P_D R_C W}{2fj}$$

R_C = Crown radius which we can assume as equal to the shell ID = 1122 mm

Joint efficiency, $J = 1$

We get, $W = \frac{1}{4} \times (3 + \sqrt{\frac{R_C}{R_1}})$

Here, R_1 = Knuckle radius = $0.06 \times ID_s$ (assuming 6% of shell ID)

$$R_1 = 0.06 \times ID_s = 0.06 \times 1122 = 67.32 \text{ mm}$$

$$W = \frac{1}{4} \times (3 + \sqrt{\frac{1122}{67.32}}) = 1.77$$

Now,

$$t_H = \frac{0.11868 \times 1122 \times 1.77}{2 \times 11.73 \times 1} = 10.05 \text{ mm} = 0.396 \text{ inch}$$

Channel thickness

The thickness is given by the following equation,

$$t_C = \frac{P_D ID}{2fj - P_D} + C$$

P_D = design pressure = 0.11868 kg/mm^2

ID = shell inside diameter = 1122 mm

Permissible stress, $f = 11.73 \text{ kg/mm}^2$

J = joint efficiency = 0.85

C = corrosion allowance = 4 mm

Now,

$$t_C = \frac{0.11868 \times 1122}{2 \times 11.73 \times 0.85 - 0.11868} + 4 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 10.72 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 0.422 \text{ inch}$$

Baffles

Baffles shape = Segmental with 25% cut

Length of the tube, $L = 13 \text{ ft}$

Baffle spacing, $B = 224.4 \text{ mm} = 8.83 \text{ inch}$

$$\text{No. of baffles required} = \frac{4 \times 10^3}{224.4} = 18$$

Insulation thickness

Insulation material = mineral wool.

Mineral wool is the preferred insulation for shell and tube heat exchangers because it offers a superior balance of high-temperature stability (up to 850°C), fire resistance, and acoustic dampening to reduce operational noise. Unlike foam or standard fiberglass, its dense, hydrophobic fibres resist moisture wicking and typically contain low chloride levels, which is critical for preventing Corrosion Under Insulation (CUI) and stress corrosion cracking in stainless steel shells like 316L or 2205. Furthermore, its flexibility allows it to remain dimensionally stable during the thermal expansion and contraction of the exchanger shell, ensuring that no "hot spots" or gaps form over time, thereby maintaining long-term thermal efficiency and personnel protection.

Thermal conductivity, $K = 0.046 \text{ W/m.K}$

The heat transfer co-efficient of air, $h = 3 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$

$$\text{Critical insulation radius, } r_{\text{critical}} = \frac{K}{h} = \frac{0.046}{3} = 0.0153\text{m}$$

Critical insulation thickness for a particular insulator denotes that minimum thickness of insulation should be provided to minimize heat loss. Since critical insulation thickness is 15.33mm. So, 100mm thickness can be acceptable for this heat exchanger.

Let us take, thickness = 100 mm = 4 inch

Supports

Saddle support is basically used for horizontal cylindrical vessels. We will use saddle support for our heat exchanger. One end of the support is kept fixed and the other end is placed on roller.

Drum diameter,

$$D_o = ID_s + 2 \times \text{shell thickness}$$

$$= (1122 + 2 \times 4) \text{ mm}$$

$$= 1130 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 45 \text{ inches}$$

Table 46: Saddle support dimensions

V	Y	C	E	J	G	t ₂	t ₁	Bolt diam.	Bolt holes
78 cm	20 cm	109cm	45 cm	36cm	14cm	12mm	10mm	24mm	30mm

Figure 38: Saddle support of a horizontal heat exchanger.

Table 47: Design summary.

Shell ID	44 inch
Tube OD	0.8 inch
Number of tubes	1560
Tube length	13 ft.
Tube pass	2
Shell pass	1
Baffle spacing	8.8 inch
Number of baffles	18
Pitch	1 inch triangular pitch
LMTD	420°F
h_o	54 Btu/hr.ft ² .°F
h_i	253 Btu/hr.ft ² .°F
ΔP_s	0.14 psi
ΔP_t	9.814 psi
Shell thickness	0.16 inch
Tube ID	0.63 inch
Insulation thickness	4 inch
Nozzle diameter	11 inch
Nozzle thickness	0.16 inch
Head thickness	0.40 inch
Channel thickness	0.42 inch
Shell OD	44.32 inch

TEMA Sheet

Company:				
Service of unit:				Reference:
Item No.:				Reference:
Date: 01/02/2024		Rev No.:		Job No.:
Size / in type AEU horizontal Connected in Parallel series				
Performance of one unit				
Fluid allocation	Shell side		Tube side	
Fluid name	Hot gas mixture of SO _x , N ₂ , O ₂		Water	
Fluid flow rate (lb/hr) (In/Out)	314.6 × 10 ³		32.802 × 10 ³	
Vapor (In/Out)				
Liquid				
Non-condensable	0	0	0	0
Temperature (In/Out) (°F)	942	230	86	104
Dew/Bubble Point (°F)				
Density (lb/ft ³)				
Viscosity (cp)	0.79	0.0038	0.35	0.002
Molecular weight	33.58		18.02	
Specific heat (Btu/lb.°F)	0.23		1.004	
Thermal conductivity (Btu/hr.ft.°F)	0.0204		0.354	
Latent heat				
Pressure (psi)	14.7		14.7	
Velocity (ft/sec)	3.85 × 10 ³		8.2 × 10 ⁻¹	
Pressure drop (psi)	9.73		0.14	
Fouling resistance				
Heat exchanged (Btu/hr.)	5.72 × 10 ⁶			
Transfer rate, Service				

Construction of one Shell				Sketch	
		Shell side	Tube side		
Design pressure (psi)		17	17		
Design temperature (°F)					
Number of passes per shell		1	2		
Corrosion allowance (inch)					
Connections Size/rating (in)	In	/	/		
	Out	/	/		
	Intermediate	/	/		
Tube specification triangular		OD 0.80-inch inch	ID 0.63-	Length 13 ft Pitch	1-inch
Tube type		Plain material stainless steel		Tube pattern floating	
Shell ID		44 inch	Shell cover	Removable	
Channel or bonnet			Channel cover		
Sheet			Floating		
Floating head cover			Impingement protection		
Baffle type		Segmental	Baffle cut (%)	25	
Support tube			Type	Rod	
Bypass seal		Tube sheet joint		Expand	
Expansion joint		Tube			
Rho V-2 inlet nozzle		Bundle entrance		Bundle exit	
Gaskets		Shell side	Tube side		
Floating head cover		Dished cover			
Code requirements		TEMA class S		Chemical service	

Figure 39: Cross sectional view of split-ring floating head 1-2 shell and tube heat exchanger.

Figure 40: Dimensional view of a split-ring floating head 1-2 shell and tube heat exchanger.

Figure 41: Cross sectional view of shell and 25% segmental cut baffle.

9.1.2 P&ID of Heat Exchanger, HE-102

CV: Hot outlet gas temperature

MV: Cooling water inlet flow rate

Table 48: Valves and their abbreviation.

Valves	Abbreviation
VLV-10,16,17,02	Gate valves for shut down
VLV-01	Gate valves for vent
VLV-14,15	Gate valves for drain
VLV-19	Relief valves
VLV-11,12	Bypass valves for pump bypass
VLV-13	Control valve
TT	Temperature transmitter
TIC	Temperature indicating controller

Figure 42:P&ID diagram of Heat Exchanger

9.2 Design of Air-Drying Tower

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9.2.1 Air Drying Tower Sizing

Packing Material: Random Packing with Intalox Saddles Ceramic.

9.2.1.1 Diameter and Height:

Mass flow rate of liquid at the bottom of the tower, $L = 12910.5 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{hr}} = 3.58 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{s}}$

Density of H_2SO_4 , $\rho_L = 1816.6 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ [At 37.78°C]

Viscosity of H_2SO_4 , $\mu_L = 12 \text{ cP}$ [At 37.78°C] (Author(s). (Year). Corrosion of carbon steel pipes and tanks by concentrated sulfuric acid: A review. ResearchGate. URL]

Volumetric Flow rate of Gas, $Q_{vG} = 3.266 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}}$

Maximum allowable vapor velocity, $v_a = 1.06 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$

Gas Density, $\rho_g = 1.313 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

From the sizing calculation in the previous chapter,

Air Drying Tower Diameter, $D = 1.98 \text{ m} \approx 2 \text{ m}$

Air Drying Tower Height, $Z = 5.81 \text{ m} \approx 6 \text{ m}$

9.2.1.2 Pressure Drop Calculation

Particle Diameter, $D_p = 2 \text{ inch} = 0.0508 \text{ m}$

Viscosity, $\mu_g = 1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa s}$

Reynolds Number, $R_e = \frac{D_p v \rho_g}{\mu} = \frac{0.0508 \times 1.06 \times 1.313}{1.9 \times 10^{-5}} = 3205$

Porosity, $\varepsilon = 0.7$

From Ergun equation, (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003)

$$\frac{\Delta P}{L} = \left[150 \times \frac{(1 - \varepsilon)^2}{\varepsilon^3} \times \frac{\mu_g v_a}{d_p^2 \times g_c} \right] + \left[1.75 \times \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{\varepsilon^3} \times \frac{\rho_g v_a^2}{d_p \times g_c} \right]$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{\Delta P}{6} = \left[150 \times \frac{(1 - 0.7)^2}{0.7^3} \times \frac{1.9 \times 10^{-5} \times 1.06}{0.0508^2} \right] + \left[1.75 \times \frac{1 - 0.7}{0.7^3} \times \frac{1.313 \times 1.06^2}{0.0508} \right]$$

$$\therefore \Delta P = 38.58 \times 6 = 232 \text{ Pa}$$

9.2.2 Mechanical Design of Air-Drying Tower (D-101)

9.2.2.1 Shell Thickness Calculation:

Material used for shell design: Carbon Steel SA516 GR70

(ASTM A516 Grade 70 and ASME SA516 Grade 70 Carbon Steel Plate)

Let, shell thickness = t_s

Working Pressure, $P_w = (101325 + 232) \text{ Pa} = 101557 \text{ Pa}$

Design Pressure, $P = 1.2 P_w = 1.2 \times 101557 \text{ Pa} = 121868 \text{ Pa}$

Internal Diameter of the column, $D_i = 1.98 \text{ m}$

Permissible Stress, $f = 138 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$ (ASTM A516 Grade 70 and ASME SA516 Grade 70 Carbon Steel Plate)

Joint efficiency, $J = 0.85$

Corrosion allowance, $C = 9 \text{ mm} = 0.009 \text{ m}$

$$\therefore t_s = \frac{PD_i}{2fj - 1.2P} + C$$

$$\text{or, } t_s = \frac{121868 \times 1.98}{2 \times 138 \times 10^6 \times 0.85 - 1.2 \times 121868} + 0.009$$

$$\therefore t_s = 0.0103 \text{ m} = 10.3 \text{ mm}$$

9.2.2.2 Axial Stress Due to Pressure:

Axial Stress due to Pressure, $f_{ap} = \frac{PD_i}{4(t_s - C)}$ (Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi)

$$\therefore f_{ap} = \frac{121868 \times 1.98}{4(0.0103 - 0.009)} = 58.625 \text{ MPa}$$

9.2.2.3 Height of Head Calculation:

Shell Head: Torispherical Head/Dome. (Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi)

Crown Radius, $R_c = D_i = 1.98 \text{ m}$

Knuckle Radius, $R_k = 6\% \text{ of } R_c = 0.1188 \text{ m}$

$$\text{Stress Intensification factor, } W = \frac{1}{4} \left(3 + \sqrt{\frac{R_c}{R_k}} \right) = \frac{1}{4} \left(3 + \sqrt{\frac{1.98}{0.1188}} \right) = 1.77$$

Shell thickness, $t_h = \frac{PR_c W}{2fj}$ (Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi)

$$\therefore t_h = \frac{121868 \times 1.98 \times 1.77}{2 \times 138 \times 10^6 \times 0.85} = 0.00182 \text{ m} = 1.82 \text{ mm}$$

Considering the Corrosion allowance, $C = 9 \text{ mm}$

Final thickness of the head, $t_h = (1.82 + 9) \text{ mm} = 10.82 \text{ mm}$

External Shell Diameter, $D_o = D_i + 2 \times t_s = 1.98 + 2 \times 0.0103 \approx 2 \text{ m}$

External Head Diameter, $D_{oh} = D_i + 2 \times t_h = 1.98 + 2 \times 0.0182 = 2.016 \text{ m}$

Total height of the heads, $h_h = 0.1935 D_o - 0.455 t_h$
 $= 0.1935 \times 2 - 0.455 \times 0.01082 = 0.3822 \text{ m}$

9.2.2.4 Manhole Thickness Calculation:

Number of Manhole selected for design, $N = 2$

Inner Diameter of Manhole, $D_i = 0.55 \text{ m}$ (Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Manhole Thickness, } t_{mh} &= \frac{D_i}{2} \left[\left(\frac{fj+P}{fj-P} \right)^{0.5} - 1 \right] + C \\ &= \frac{1.98}{2} \left[\left(\frac{138 \times 10^6 \times 0.85 + 121868}{138 \times 10^6 \times 0.85 - 121868} \right)^{0.5} - 1 \right] + 0.009 \\ &= 0.01003 \text{ m} \\ &= 10.03 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

9.2.2.5 Nozzle Calculation:

Material of construction: Alloy 20(Ni – Fe – Cr with Cu)

Permissible Stress, $f = 157.9 \text{ MPa}$ (Allowable Stress of Alloy 20 at Different Temperatures)

Corrosion Allowance for Nozzles, $C = 3 \text{ mm} = 0.003 \text{ m}$

1. Gas Handling Nozzle:

$$\text{Volumetric Flow Rate, } Q_{vG} = 3.266 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}} = 3.266 \times 3600 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$$

$$\text{Density, } \rho_{vG} = 1.131 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$$

Diameter of gas nozzle, $D_{nG} = \sqrt{\frac{4Q_{vG}}{1.4\pi \times 3600}} \left(\frac{\rho_{vG}}{2500}\right)^{0.25}$ [Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi]

$$= \sqrt{\frac{4(3.266 \times 3600)}{1.4\pi \times 3600}} \left(\frac{1.131}{2500}\right)^{0.25}$$

$$= 0.25 \text{ m}$$

Thickness of gas nozzle, $t_{nG} = \frac{PD_{nG}}{2fj-P} + C$ [Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi]

$$= \frac{121868 \times 0.25}{2 \times 157.9 \times 10^6 \times 0.85 - 121868} + 0.003$$

$$= 0.003114 \text{ m} = 3.114 \text{ mm}$$

2. Liquid Handling Nozzle:

Volumetric Flow Rate, $Q_{vL} = 1.97 \times 10^{-3} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}} = 1.97 \times 10^{-3} \times 3600 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{hr}}$

Diameter of gas nozzle, $D_{nL} = \sqrt{\frac{4Q_{vL}}{1.4\pi \times 3600}}$ [Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi]

$$= \sqrt{\frac{4(1.97 \times 10^{-3} \times 3600)}{1.4\pi \times 3600}}$$

$$= 0.042 \text{ m}$$

Thickness of gas nozzle, $t_{nL} = \frac{PD_{nL}}{2fj-P} + C$ [Process Equipment Design, M V Joshi]

$$= \frac{121868 \times 0.042}{2 \times 157.9 \times 10^6 \times 0.85 - 121868} + 0.003$$

$$= 0.003019 \text{ m} = 3.019 \text{ mm}$$

9.2.2.6 Total Height of Column:

Number of manholes, $N = 2$

Packing Height, $Z = 5.81 \text{ m}$

Height of Manhole, $h_{\text{manhole}} = 0.55 \text{ m}$

Height of Support, $h_{\text{Support}} = 290 \text{ mm} = 0.29 \text{ m}$

Height of Mist Eliminator, $h_{\text{mist eliminator}} = 200 \text{ mm} = 0.2 \text{ m}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Height of manhole and support, } h_{ms} &= h_{\text{manhole}} + h_{\text{Support}} \\
 &= (0.55 + 0.29) \text{ m} \\
 &= 0.84 \text{ m}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Height of manhole and mist eliminator, } h_{ms} &= h_{\text{manhole}} + h_{\text{mist eliminator}} \\
 &= (0.55 + 0.2) \text{ m} \\
 &= 0.75 \text{ m}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Total height of the column, } H &= Z + Nh_{ms} + h_{mm} \\
 &= 5.81 + 2(0.84) + 0.75 \text{ m} \\
 &= 6.879 \text{ m} \approx 7 \text{ m}
 \end{aligned}$$

9.2.2.7 Skirt Design:

Here we have designed skirt for the vessel support.

Material of construction: Carbon Steel.

Inner Diameter of the vessel, $D_i = 1.98 \text{ m}$

Outer Diameter of the vessel, $D_o = 2 \text{ m}$

Packing Height, $Z = 5.81 \text{ m}$

Column Height, $H = 7 \text{ m}$

Diameter of Skirt, $D_{sk} = D_o = 2 \text{ m}$

Height of Skirt, $h_{sk} = D_o = 2 \text{ m}$

Packing bulk Density, $\rho_b = 30 \frac{\text{lb}}{\text{ft}^3} = 480 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

Carbon Steel Density, $\rho_{cs} = 7780 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

Liquid Density, $\rho_L = 1816.6 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

Weights above Skirt:

- Shell Weight, $W_s = \frac{\pi}{4} (D_o^2 - D_i^2) \rho_{cs} \times H \times g$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{\pi}{4} (2^2 - 1.98^2) \times 7780 \times 7 \times 9.8 \text{ N} \\
 &= 33366 \text{ N}
 \end{aligned}$$

2. Packing Weight, $W_p = \frac{\pi}{4} D_i^2 \rho_p h_p g$

$$= \frac{\pi}{4} \times 1.98^2 \times 480 \times 5.81 \times 9.8 \text{ N}$$

$$= 84152 \text{ N}$$
3. Liquid Weight, $W_L = \frac{\pi}{4} D_i^2 \rho_L Z g$

$$= \frac{\pi}{4} \times 1.98^2 \times 1816.6 \times 5.81 \times 9.8 \text{ N}$$

$$= 318480 \text{ N}$$
4. Two Heads Weight, $W_h = \frac{2}{3} (D_{oh}^2 - D_i^2) \rho_{cs} \times h_H \times g \times 2$

$$= \frac{\pi}{4} (2^2 - 1.98^2) \times 7780 \times 0.3822 \times 9.8 \times 2 \text{ N}$$

$$= 3341 \text{ N}$$
5. Other Weights, $W_{others} = W_{ladder} + W_{manhole} + W_{packing \text{ Support}}$

$$= 3000 \text{ N}$$

∴ Total weight of the vessel, $W = W_s + W_p + W_L + W_h + W_{others}$

$$= (33366 + 84152 + 318480 + 3341 + 3000) \text{ N} = 442339 \text{ N}$$

$$\therefore \text{Total Stress on the support} = \frac{W}{A} = \frac{442339}{\frac{\pi}{4} \times 2^2} = 140.8 \text{ kPa}$$

9.2.2.8 Stress Calculations:

1. Stress due to Dead Load:

$$\text{Stress, } f_{dl} = \frac{W}{\pi D_{sk} t_{sk}} = \frac{442339}{\pi \times 2 \times t_{sk}} = \frac{70400}{t_{sk}}$$

2. Stress due to Wind Load:

At Narsingdi, the maximum wind velocity, $v_{max} = 41 \frac{\text{km}}{\text{hr}} = 11.39 \text{ ms}^{-1}$

[Narsingdi Weather - Bangladesh]

$$\text{Wind Pressure, } P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 = \frac{1}{2} \times 1.225 \times 11.39^2 = 80 \text{ Pa}$$

Cylindrical surface shape factor, $k = 0.7$

The forces of wind load are acting on the lower and upper parts of the vessel are,

$$P_{fw} = k P_w Z D_o$$

$$= 0.7 \times 80 \times 5.81 \times 2$$

$$= 650.72 \text{ N}$$

Bending moment due to wind at the base of the vessel, $M_w = \frac{P_{fw}Z}{2}$

$$= \frac{650.72 \times 5.81}{2} = 1890.3416$$

$$\text{Stress, } f_{wl} = \frac{4M_w}{\pi D_0 t_{sk}} = \frac{4 \times 1890.3416}{\pi \times 2 \times t_{sk}} = \frac{1203}{t_{sk}}$$

3. Stress due to Seismic Load:

For 8.5 magnitude of earthquake, $C = 0.08$ [Bangladesh-National-Building-Code-2020.pdf]

$$\text{Stress, } f_{sl} = \frac{2CWZ}{3\pi R_{sk}^2 t_{sk}} = \frac{2 \times 0.08 \times 442339 \times 5.81}{3\pi \times \left(\frac{2}{2}\right)^2 \times t_{sk}} = \frac{43630}{t_{sk}}$$

$$\text{Maximum Compressive Stress, } f_{c(\max)} = f_{dl} + f_{wl} + f_{sl} = \frac{70400}{t_{sk}} + \frac{1203}{t_{sk}} + \frac{43630}{t_{sk}} = \frac{115233}{t_{sk}}$$

Carbon Steel SA-516 Gr70 has a Yield Point, $Y = 260 \text{ MPa}$

Under Permissible limit, $f_{c(\max)} \leq \frac{Y}{3}$

$$\text{or, } \frac{115233}{t_{sk}} \leq \frac{260 \times 10^6}{3}$$

$$\therefore t_{sk} \geq 1.33 \text{ mm}$$

$$\therefore t_{sk} = 1.33 + C = (1.33 + 3) \text{ mm} = 4.33 \text{ mm} \approx 5 \text{ mm}$$

9.2.3 Design Summary of the Air-Drying Tower (D-101)

Parameters	Values
Packing Type	Random Packing
Packing Material	Intalox Saddles Ceramic
Nominal Size	2 inch
Column Diameter	2 m
Packing Height	5.81 m
Column Height	7 m
Shell Material	Carbon Steel SA516 GR70
Shell Thickness	10.3 mm
Head Type	Torispherical
Head Thickness	10.82 mm
Height of the Heads	0.382 m
No. of Manhole	2
Manhole Diameter	0.55 m
Manhole Thickness	10.03 mm \approx 10 mm
Gas Nozzle Diameter	0.25 m
Gas Nozzle Thickness	3.114 mm \approx 3 mm
Liquid Nozzle Diameter	0.042 m
Liquid Nozzle Thickness	3.019 mm \approx 3 mm
Skirt Height	2 m
Skirt Diameter	2 m
Skirt Thickness	4.33 mm \approx 5 mm
Mist Eliminator	Mesh Pad
Standard	ASME Standards for vessels

9.2.4 Mechanical Drawing of Air-Drying Tower (D-101)

Figure 43: Cross sectional view with Dimensions and Labelling.

Top Section:

Figure 44: Zoom-in View around Liquid Inlet with Mist Eliminator.

9.2.5 Materials Inside Air Drying Tower

Figure 45: Round Shaped Mist Eliminator.

Figure 46: Multi Beam Packing Support for the Packed Bed.

Figure 47: Intalox Saddles Ceramics Packing

Size of Intalox Saddles Ceramics Packing:

Size (mm)	Specific Surface Area ($\frac{m^2}{m^3}$)	Void Fraction (%)	Number of Pairings ($\frac{Piece}{m^3}$)	Stacking Weight ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$)
19	350	75	146000	670

(25mm 50mm Random Packing RTO Ceramic Intalox Saddle Ring, n.d.)

Piping and Instrumentation Diagram of Air Drying Tower (D-101)

Figure 48: Piping and Instrumentation Diagram for Air Drying Tower.

Control Loop Variables

List of Variables:

Name	Variable
Inlet liquid Mass Flow Rate	$m_{L_{in}}$
Outlet liquid Mass Flow Rate	$m_{L_{out}}$
Inlet gas Mass Flow Rate	$m_{G_{in}}$
Outlet gas Mass Flow Rate	$m_{G_{out}}$
Inlet liquid Temperature	$T_{L_{in}}$
Outlet liquid Temperature	$T_{L_{out}}$
Inlet gas Temperature	$T_{G_{in}}$
Outlet gas Temperature	$T_{G_{out}}$
Inlet gas Nitrogen Composition	$x_{G_{in}}$
Outlet gas Nitrogen Composition	$x_{G_{out}}$
Liquid Height	H
Inside Pressure	P

For each of the Control Loop the three types of variables are listed below:

Controller	Control Variable	Manipulated Variable	Disturbance Variables
FC	$m_{G_{in}}$	$m_{G_{in}}$ (at inlet)	P, H, $m_{G_{out}}$, $m_{L_{in}}$, $m_{L_{out}}$, $T_{G_{in}}$, $T_{G_{out}}$
PC	P	$m_{G_{out}}$	$m_{G_{in}}$, $m_{L_{in}}$, $m_{L_{out}}$, H, $x_{G_{in}}$, $x_{G_{out}}$, $T_{G_{in}}$, $T_{G_{out}}$
AC	$x_{G_{out}}$	$m_{L_{in}}$	$m_{G_{in}}$, $m_{G_{out}}$, $m_{L_{out}}$, P, H, $x_{G_{in}}$, $T_{G_{in}}$, $T_{G_{out}}$
LC	H	$m_{L_{out}}$	$m_{G_{in}}$, $m_{G_{out}}$, $m_{L_{in}}$, $x_{G_{in}}$, $T_{L_{in}}$, $T_{L_{out}}$

9.3 Design of 4 Bed Converter

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4-bed converter is the heart of a typical sulfuric acid plant. This chapter includes the structural and mechanical design of the 4-bed converter of this plant. To describe the structural design, the bed height, catalyst selection, and pressure drop were determined. To define its mechanical design, material of construction of the equipment, shell thickness calculation, knuckle radius, crown radius, insulation consideration, total weight of the equipment, skirt support system, bed support system, manhole design, support system for the beds, pipe diameters, were determined. Finally, the mechanical design of the equipment and its different accessories are added.

9.3.1 Determination of Bed Height

The reaction occurring inside every bed of the converter is,

The rate expression of this reaction is expressed using the following equations.(Hill, 1977)

$$r_m = \frac{k_1 P_{\text{SO}_2} P_{\text{O}_2} - k_1 P_{\text{SO}_3} P_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P_{\text{SO}_2}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (5.1)$$

Where, P_A is the partial pressure of the correspondent compound, r_m is the rate of the reaction and k_1 and k_2 are determined using equation 5.2 and 5.3. In these equations k_1 and k_2 are represented in moles/(s g-catalyst atm^{3/2}) and moles/(s g-catalyst atm) respectively.

$$\ln k_1 = 12.07 - \frac{31000}{RT} \dots \dots \dots (5.2)$$

$$\ln k_2 = 22.75 - \frac{53600}{RT} \dots \dots \dots (5.3)$$

Here, T is the average reaction temperature in kelvin and R is the gas constant in cal/mol-K which is 1.98 cal/mol-K.

The most important parameter to define the catalytic bed of the converter are diameter, D, bed height, z, conversion rate, f, temperature, T, density of the packing material, ρ_B , concentration of the reactant, C_A , velocity of the flow, u, mass flow, G, heat capacity, C_p , and heat of reaction, ΔH . These variables are related to each other using the following equations. They are derived from the material balance and energy balance equation of the catalytic bed.

$$GC_P(T - T_0) = C_{A0}u_0 (f - f_0)(-\Delta H) \dots \dots \dots (5.4)$$

$$C_{A0}u_0(f - f_0) = r_m(z - z_0)\rho_B \dots \dots \dots (5.5)$$

For each of the beds, these equations are used to determine the bed height, and outlet stream temperature of the catalytic bed. For every bed of this converter,

Bed diameter, $D = 5\text{m}$ (assumed)

Bed area, $A_c = \frac{\pi}{4} D^2$

Heat capacity, $C_p = 1.046 \text{ J/gK}$

Density of the packing material, $\rho_B = 550 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Heat of reaction, $\Delta H = -24.60 + 1.99 \times 10^{-3} T \text{ kcal/mol}$

Mass flow, $G = 304.6 \times (0.79 \times 28 + 0.32 \times 0.06 + 0.15 \times 64) + \frac{152.3 \times (0.21 \times 32 + 0.79 \times 28) \times 1000}{A_c \times 3600}$

$= 199.01 \text{ g/m}^2\text{s}$

Initial concentration of $\text{SO}_2 \times$ initial velocity of SO_2 , $C_{A0}u_0 = 0.6467 \text{ mol/m}^2\text{s}$

The process is done in atmospheric pressure. Therefore, the partial pressure would be the mole fraction of the compounds.

Table 49: Determination of the equations of partial pressure.

Compound	Initial molar flow (kmol/hr)	Final molar flow (kmol/hr)	Partial Pressure (atm)
SO_2	45.69	$45.69 (1 - f)$	$45.69 (1 - f)/456.9 - 22.845f$
O_2	50.263	$50.263 - 22.845f$	$(50.263 - 22.845f)/456.9 - 22.845f$
SO_3	0	$45.69f$	$45.69f/456.9 - 22.845f$
N_2	360.947	360.947	$360.947/456.9 - 22.845f$

For every small change in conversion fraction, the partial pressure is determined using the equations of table 1. The value of k_1 and k_2 are determined using equation 5.2 and 5.3. Later, these values are used to find the rate of reaction (equation 5.1) for that condition. For the change

in conversion fraction, required height is determined using equation 5.5. Finally, for the particular fraction, outlet temperature is determined using equation 5.4. The calculations are done in a matlab code. The code is added in the appendices. The results of the calculation are summarized in table 2.

Table 50: Result of the bed height calculation.

Bed No.	Conversion, f	Inlet Temperature (°C)	Outlet Temperature (°C)	Bed height, z (m)
1	0.65	675	868.18	2.082
2	0.9	655	728.69	1.308
3	0.95	655	674.77	1.1488
4	0.99	575	586.91	1.0534

The comparison of these four parameters for different beds are compared below. The inlet temperatures are adjusted using trial and error calculation in order to find out minimum bed height.

Figure 49: Bed height vs Bed Number.

Figure 50: Outlet Temperature vs Bed Number.

Figure 51: Inlet Temperature vs Bed Number.

Figure 52: Conversion vs Bed Number.

9.3.2 Catalyst Selection

The catalyst of Hualian's model S101 - 2HY is sincerely selected for operation. The physical properties of this catalyst are described below. (Sulfuric Acid Catalyst (Vanadium Pentoxide) | Hualian, n.d.)

Table 51: Physical properties of the catalyst.

Name of the Property	Value
Color	Yellow or yellowish brown
Size, OD:ID:Length (mm)	11:4:10-15
Bulk density (kg/L)	0.5-0.6
V ₂ O ₅ , %	7.5-8.5
K ₂ SO ₄ , %	18.3-23.0
SiO ₂ , %	65.0-75.0
Loss on ignition, %	<3.5

9.3.3 Pressure Drop Calculation

Inner diameter of the catalyst, $r_i = 4$ mm

Outer diameter of the catalyst, $r_o = 11$ mm

Average length of the catalyst, $L = (10+15)/2$ mm

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Volume of the particle, } V_p &= \pi (r_o^2 - r_i^2)L \\ &= 4.12 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Surface Area of the particle, } A_p &= 2\pi ((r_o^2 - r_i^2) + (r_o - r_i)L) \\ &= 1.84 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Particle Diameter, } D_p &= \frac{6V_p}{A_p} \\ &= 13.46 \text{ mm}\end{aligned}$$

Sphericity, $\psi = 0.6766$

Porosity, $\varepsilon = 0.5$

Nominal gas viscosity, $\mu = 0.09$ lb/hr – ft

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Vessel inlet gas molecular weight, } M_1 &= \frac{360.947}{456.9} \times 28 + \frac{50.263}{456.9} \times 32 + \frac{45.69}{456.9} \times 64 \\ &= 32.0421\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Vessel inlet gas density, } \rho_1 &= \frac{32.0421}{0.082 \times (690 + 273)} \text{ g/L} \\ &= 0.4058 \text{ g/L}\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Vessel outlet gas molecular weight, } M_2 = 27.68$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Vessel outlet gas density, } \rho_2 &= \frac{27.68}{0.082 \times (520 + 273)} \text{ g/L} \\ &= 0.4257 \text{ g/L}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Average gas density, } \rho_{\text{avg}} &= \frac{0.4257+0.4058}{2} \times 0.062 \text{ g/L} \\ &= 0.0260 \text{ lb/ft}^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Mass flow rate per unit area, } G = \frac{199.01}{4882.43} \text{ lb/ft}^2 - \text{s} = 0.0408 \text{ lb/ft}^2 - \text{s}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Reynolds number of the gas flow, } Re &= \frac{D_p \times 0.00328 \times G \times 3600}{\mu} \\ &= 72 \end{aligned}$$

Pressure drop is determined by Carman-Kozeny equation.

$$\frac{\Delta P \rho_{\text{avg}} D_p \varepsilon^2}{G^2 L (1 - \varepsilon)} = \frac{150 (1 - \varepsilon)}{Re} + 1.75 \dots \dots \dots (5.6)$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta P = 3.139 \times 10^{-4} \text{ atm} = \mathbf{0.0046 \text{ psi}}$$

9.3.4 Mechanical Design

Material Selection for the Equipment

SO₂ and SO₃ are highly corrosive. At low temperature and dry environment, carbon steel is better than SS. But above 500°C CS loses its mechanical strength. Thus SS 316 is the best choice for the material of construction.

Shell thickness calculation

Design pressure with 10% excess pressure allowance,

$$P_i = 1 \times 1.1/10 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Stress, S=160; (Stainless Steel Companies - Suppliers, Stainless Steel Fabricators and Exporters, n.d.) at 550°C

Joint Efficiency, E=0.8;

Corrosion Allowance, C_A=2 mm

Bed diameter, D_i = 5×1000 mm = 5000 mm

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Shell thickness, } t_s &= P_i \times D_i / (2 \times S \times E - 1.2 \times P_i) \text{ mm} \\ &= 2.1495 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Total thickness} = (C_A + t_s) \text{ mm} = 4.1495 \text{ mm}$$

We consider a higher standard thickness that is often used in industries. Thus, we consider a thickness of 8 mm in total.

9.3.5 Knuckle Radius and Crown Radius

Knuckle radius and crown radius are assumed to be 50cm and 218cm respectively.

9.3.6 Insulation to shell calculation

$$\text{Thickness} = 75 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Density of the material, } \rho = 120 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$\text{Thermal conductivity of the insulation material, } k = 0.038 \text{ w/(m}\cdot\text{°C)}$$

$$\text{Convective heat transfer coefficient of the insulation material, } h=3 \text{ W/(m}^2\cdot\text{°C)}$$

$$\text{Critical radius of insulation, } r_o = k / h \text{ cm}$$

$$= 0.0127 \text{ cm}$$

$$\text{Average vessel temperature} = \frac{690+651+665+565+690.0045+651.017+665.0021+565.0021}{8} \text{ K}$$

$$= 642.75 \text{ K}$$

$$\text{Average atmospheric temperature of Narshingdi, } T = 37\text{°C}$$

$$R_i = (5/2 + 8)/1000 \text{ m}$$

$$= 2.5080 \text{ m}$$

$$R_o = (R_i+75)/1000 \text{ m}$$

$$= 2.5830 \text{ m}$$

9.3.7 Total weight of the column

$$\text{Total height of the cylinder} = (2.016+1.3084+1.1488+1.0534+1\times 6) \text{ m}$$

$$= 11.5922 \text{ m}$$

Bed diameter, $D=5$ m

$$\begin{aligned}\text{The vessel weight, } W_v &= (\pi \times 5 \times 11.5922 \times 8 \times 10^{-3} \times 9.8 \times 8000 \times 1.1) \text{ N} \\ &= 1.256 \times 10^5 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$m_v = W_v / 9.8 \text{ kg} = 1.2813 \times 10^4 \text{ kg}$$

9.3.8 Approximate Weight of Dished Portion of Head

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of the head, } W_H &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times (1.23 \times 5 + 8 \times 10^{-3})^2 \times 8000 \times 8 \times 10^{-3} \times 9.8 \text{ N} \\ &= 1.867 \times 10^4 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$m_H = W_H / 9.8 \text{ kg} = 1.91 \times 10^3 \text{ kg}$$

9.3.9 Weight of Plates

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of plates, } W_p &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times (4 \times 0.03 + 3 \times 8 \times 10^{-3}) \times 8000 \times 5^2 \times 9.8 \text{ N} \\ &= 2.22 \times 10^5 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}m_p &= W_p / 9.81 \text{ kg} \\ &= 22608 \text{ kg}\end{aligned}$$

9.3.10 Weight of Insulation

$$\text{Volume of insulation, } V_i = \pi \times (R_i^2 - R_o^2) \times 11.5922 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\rho_i = 120 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$W_i = V_i \times \rho_i \times 9.81 \text{ N} = 1.636 \times 10^4 \text{ N}$$

$$m_{\text{insulation}} = W_i / 9.81 = 1.6678 \times 10^3 \text{ kg}$$

9.3.11 Total Mass of the Equipment

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total Mass} &= m_{\text{insulation}} + m_p + m_H + m_v \\ &= 3.9 \times 10^4 \text{ kg}\end{aligned}$$

9.3.12 Skirt support design for the converter

Since the skirt remains in atmospheric temperature, CS is chosen as the material of construction of skirt. The skirt height is chosen to be 3m.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total weight} &= 3.9 \times 10^4 \times 9.81 \times 1.1 \times 1.01 \text{ N} \\ &= 4.25 \times 10^5 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Pressure due to dead load, } P_1 = \frac{4.25 \times 10^5}{\pi \times (D + 0.008 \times 2 + 0.075 \times 2) \times 0.008} \text{ Pa}$$

Pressure due to wind load,

$$\begin{aligned}P_{\text{wind}} &= 0.7 \times P_1 \times (\text{cylinder} + \text{skirt height} + 1.5) \times (D + 0.008 \times 2 + 0.075 \times 2) \text{ Pa} \\ &= 1.98 \times 10^8 \text{ Pa}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}F_{\text{wind}} &= 0.7 \times P_{\text{wind}} \times (\text{cylinder} + \text{skirt height} + 1.5) \times (D + 0.008 \times 2 + 0.075 \times 2) \text{ N} \\ &= 1.11 \times 10^{10} \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

Bending moment due to wind at the base of the vessel,

$$M_w = F_{\text{wind}} \times (\text{cylinder} + \text{skirt height} + 1.5) / 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress due to the wind, } P_{wb} &= M_w / 2 \text{ Pa} \\ &= 4.46 \times 10^{10} \text{ Pa}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Due to seismic load, } F &= 0.15 \times m_p \text{ N} \\ &= 3.39 \times 10^3 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Bending moment due to seismic load, } M_s &= 2 \times 0.15 \times m_p \times (D + 0.008 \times 2 + 0.075 \times 2) / 3 \\ &= 1.168 \times 10^4\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Stress due to seismic load, } P_{sb} = M_s / 2 = 5.84 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}$$

Maximum compressive stress at the bottom of the skirt,

$$\text{Compressive stress} = P_1 + \max(P_{sb}, P_{wb})$$

$$= 4.46 \times 10^{10} \text{ Pa}$$

Maximum tensile stress at the bottom of the skirt,

$$\text{Tensile stress} = -P_1 + \max(P_{sb}, P_{wb})$$

$$= 4.46 \times 10^{10} \text{ Pa}$$

9.3.13 Support System Selection

Each catalyst bed is covered with a 25 mm quartz layer both in the upper side and lower side of the catalyst bed. The bed is supported by stainless steel grid with a thickness of 30 mm.

9.3.14 Pipe Diameter

For 32" ID pipe, the velocity of the gas flow remains 4.144 m/s. This is a safe range to operate, hence, considered to use.

9.3.15 Manhole Selection

The manhole diameter is selected to be 60 cm.

9.3.16 Mechanical Drawing

Figure 53: Mechanical Drawing of the equipment. (Dimensions)

Figure 54: Mechanical Drawing of the equipment. (label)

Figure 55: Shell and insulation thickness of the converter.

Figure 56: Design of the catalyst.

9.3.17 P&ID Diagram of 4 Bed Converter

Figure 57: P&ID Diagram of 4 bed converter.

To design the control loops of this equipment, the following control and manipulated variables are considered for each of the beds.

First Bed

Control Variable : Pressure of first bed, temperature of stream number 38.

Manipulated Variable : Flowrate of stream number 38, flow rate of cooling water in HE 101.

Second Bed

Control Variable : Temperature of stream number 8.

Manipulated Variable : Flow rate of cooling water in HE 105.

Third Bed

Control Variable : Temperature of stream number 11.

Manipulated Variable : Flow rate of cooling water in HE 106.

Fourth Bed

Control Variable : Pressure of fourth bed, temperature of stream number 13.

Manipulated Variable : Flowrate of stream number 13, flow rate of cooling water in HE 102.

Relief valves are assigned in necessary points.

9.4 Design of Intermediate Absorption Tower (B-102)

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9.4.1 Intermediate Absorption Tower

9.4.2 Packing material selection

Intalox saddles Ceramic is selected for absorber designs because their unique geometric shape provides a 25% larger surface area and higher free volume than traditional packing, significantly enhancing mass transfer efficiency while minimizing pressure drop. Their superior acid resistance (greater than 99.6%) and thermal stability make them ideal for harsh chemical environments, while their random orientation prevents liquid channeling, ensuring uniform wetting and high throughput for long-term, reliable operation. (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

Packing material: (random packing) Intalox saddles ceramic. (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

Nominal size, $d_p = 1.0$ inch

Porosity, $\epsilon = 0.18$

Packing factor $a_p/\epsilon^3 = 100$ ft²/ft³

9.4.3 Diameter Calculation

Mass flow rate of liquid at the bottom of the tower,

$$L = 45.032 \times 80 + 245.074 \times 98$$

$$= 27619.812 \text{ kg/hr} = 7.672 \text{ kg/s}$$

Density of 13% liquid Oleum, $\rho_L = 1.90 \text{ g/mL}$ (at 1100°C)(Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

and viscosity = 5 cp

Mass flow rate of gas at the bottom of the tower,

$$G = (45.487 \times 80 + 1.998 \times 64 + 27.511 \times 32 + 360.923 \times 28) \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 14637.94 \text{ kg/hr}$$

$$= 4.066 \text{ kg/s}$$

The average molecular weight of the gas,

$$M_{\text{avg}} = (0.10478 \times 80 + 0.00046 \times 64 + 0.06337 \times 32 + 0.83139 \times 28) = 33.7186 \text{ kg/kmol}$$

The density of gas $\rho_g = \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 33.72}{8.314 \times (70+273)} = 1198.12 \text{ g/m}^3 = 0.0747 \text{ lb/ft}^3$

Now, from the next four figures, (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

Figure 58: Correlation for estimating flooding rate in packed towers.

Flow parameter, X value = $\frac{L}{G} \times \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\rho_L}\right)^{0.5} = 0.0473$

We get Capacity Parameter, Y value= 0.17

Now, $\frac{V^2 a_p \mu_L^{0.2} \rho_g}{g \rho_L} = 0.17$

Therefore, flooding velocity, $V = 7.93 \text{ ft/s}$

Here, allowable vapor velocity is estimated to be 50 to 70% of the flooding velocity (Peters & Timmerhaus, 2003, p. 698), which is used to determine the column diameter. Considering the absorber tower is designed for the gas velocity at 50% of the flooding velocity.

Maximum allowable vapor velocity $V_{\text{actual}} = 0.50 \times 7.93 \text{ ft/s} = 3.966 \text{ ft/s} = 1.2 \text{ m/s}$

Volumetric flow rate of gas $Q = \frac{G}{\rho_g} = 3.393 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

Cross-sectional area, $A = \frac{Q}{V_{\text{actual}}} = 2.87 \text{ m}^2$

Thus, $D = 1.89 \text{ m}$

Therefore, the diameter of the tank is 1.89 m

9.4.4 Height calculation

Number of overall gas phase transfer unit (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \frac{(1-y) \text{lm}}{(1-y)(y^*-y)} dy$$

When the gas is dilute $(1-y)_{\text{lm}} = (1-y)$

The reaction at the interface is very instantaneous that, $y^* = 0$

$$N_{OG} = \int_{y_2}^{y_1} \frac{1}{y} dy$$

Here $y_1 =$ Input mole fraction of $\text{SO}_3 = 0.1047$

And $y_2 =$ Output mole fraction of $\text{SO}_3 = 0.00109$

So, $N_{OG} = 4.565 \text{ m}$

Now, the height of an overall gas phase transfer unit is calculated using Onda's method

(Towler and Sinnott, 2013, p. 901)

$$\frac{a_w}{a} = 1 - \exp \left[-0.45 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_L} \right)^{0.75} \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a \mu_L} \right)^{0.1} \left(\frac{L_w^{*2} a}{\rho_L^2 g} \right)^{-0.05} \left(\frac{L_w^{*2}}{\rho_L \sigma_L a} \right)^{0.2} \right]$$

Here, $a = 253 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$

σ_c for ceramic = 61×10^{-3} N/m (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

σ_L for 98% sulfuric acid = 0.05 N/m (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

μ_L = Viscosity of liquid H₂SO₄ = 0.0063 Pa.s (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

Density of 98% liquid H₂SO₄, ρ_L = 1797.6 kg/m³ (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

$$L_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of liquid H}_2\text{SO}_4}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = 2.733 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{So, } a_w = 111.467 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$$

Here, Packing size $d_p = 1.0$ inch = 0.0254 m

Association parameter of the solvent H₂SO₄, $\phi = 1$

The molecular weight of solvent B (98% H₂SO₄), $M_B = 98$ kg/kmol

$$T = (273 + 70) = 343 \text{ K}$$

Viscosity of B (H₂SO₄), $\mu_B = 0.0063$ Pa.s

Solute (SO₃) molar volume at the boiling point = V_A

Using the table 18.2 -4 for atomic and molar volumes at the normal boiling point (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

$$V_A = (S) + 3(O)$$

$$= (25.6 + 3 \times 7.4) \times 10^{-3} = 0.0478 \text{ m}^3/\text{kgmol}$$

$$D_L = 1.173 \times 10^{-16} (\phi M_B)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{T}{\mu_B V_A^{0.6}} \quad (\text{Geankoplis, 2018,})$$

$$\text{So, } D_L = 3.919 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$$

Therefore,

$$k_L \left(\frac{\rho_L}{\mu_L g} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = 0.0051 \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a_w \mu_L} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\mu_L}{\rho_L D_L} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (ad_p)^{0.4}$$

$$\text{Or, } k_L = 9.132 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m/s}$$

Now, Viscosity of gas (SO₃), $\mu_v = 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$ kg/ms [at 70°C]

$$\text{Density of gas (SO}_3\text{) at } 70^\circ\text{C, } \rho_v = \frac{PM}{RT} = \frac{101325 \times 80 \times 10^{-3}}{8.314 \times 303}$$

$$= 2.842 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

Where, Operating pressure, $P = 1 \text{ atm}$

Atomic and Structural Diffusion Volume Increments			
C	16.5	Cl	19.5*
H	1.98	S	17.0*
O	5.48	Aromatic or	-20.0
N	5.69*	hetrocyclic rings	
Diffusion Volumes of Simple Molecules			
H ₂	7.07	CO	18.9
D ₂	6.70	CO ₂	26.9
He	2.88	N ₂ O	35.9
N ₂	17.9	NH ₃	14.9
O ₂	16.6	H ₂ O	12.7
Air	20.1	CCL ₂ F ₂	114.8*
Ne	5.59	SF ₆	69.7*
Ar	16.1	Cl ₂	37.7*
Kr	22.8	Br ₂	67.2*
Xe	37.9*	SO ₂	41.1*

*Value based on only a few data points.

Figure 59: Table consisting of diffusion volume coefficients determined by Fuller.

The sum of the structural volume increments of A (SO₃),

$$\sum V_{A,i} = 17 + 5.48 \times 3 = 33.44$$

The sum of the structural volume increments of B (Other gases),

$$\sum V_{B,i} = (41.1 + 5.69 \times 2 + 5.48 \times 2) = 63.44$$

The molecular weight of A (SO₃), $M_A = 80 \text{ kg/kmol}$

Molecular weight of B, $M_B = 25.336 \text{ kg/kmol}$

Temperature, $T = 343 \text{ K}$

For packing sizes above 15 mm, $K_5 = 5.23$

Hence,

$$D_v = \frac{1 \times 10^{-7} (T)^{1.75} \left(\frac{1}{M_A} + \frac{1}{M_B} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P \left[\sum V_{A,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} + \sum V_{B,i}^{\frac{1}{3}} \right]^2}$$

So, $D_v = 1.2144 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

$$\text{Now, } V_w = \frac{\text{Mass flow rate of Gas stream}}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = \frac{4.0661}{2.807} = 1.448 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{So, } k_G = 5.93 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{.s.atm}$$

Now, the molar gas flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$G_m = \frac{V_w}{\text{molecular weight of gas}} = 0.0181 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

And molar liquid flow rate per unit cross-sectional area,

$$L_m = \frac{L_w}{\text{molecular weight of liquid}} = 0.0269 \text{ kmol/m}^2\text{s}$$

$$\text{Height of the gas film transfer unit, } H_G = \frac{G_m}{K_G a_w P} = 0.273 \text{ m}$$

$$C_T = \frac{\rho L}{\text{Molecular weight of solvent}} = 19.97 \text{ kmol/m}^3$$

$$\text{Height of the liquid film transfer unit, } H_L = \frac{L_m}{K_L a_w C_T} = 1.325 \text{ m}$$

Now, the overall height of the transfer unit based on concentration driving force,

$$H_{OG} = H_G + (mG_m/L_m) \times H_L$$

According to Colburn (1939), the optimum value for the term mG_m/L_m will lie between 0.7 -

0.8. Taking 0.7 for calculation,

$$H_{OG} = 0.273 + 0.7 \times 1.325 = 1.201 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Now the height of the packing, } Z = H_{OG} \times N_{OG} = 1.201 \times 4.565 = 5.485 \text{ m}$$

Calculated Diameter: 1.89 m

Packing height: 5.50 m approximately.

9.4.5 Mechanical Design

Shell Design

The absorber shell is selected as carbon steel due to its proven corrosion resistance in concentrated sulfuric acid service and its widespread use in industrial sulfuric acid absorption towers operating at elevated temperatures.

The correlation for calculating the thickness of the shell given in is:

$$\text{Thickness of shell, } t_s = \frac{PD_i}{2SE-1.2P} + C \text{ (Towler, G., \& Sinnott, R., 2013)}$$

The internal diameter of the vessel $D_i = 1.89 \text{ m}$

The working pressure = 101325 N/m^2

Design pressure $P = 1.2 \times 101325 \text{ N/m}^2 = 121590 \text{ N/m}^2$

Maximum allowable stress $S = 9.50 \times 10^7 \text{ N/m}^2$ (by interpolation) (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

Welded Joint efficiency $E = 0.85$ (Considering double welded butt joints if spot-examined) (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

Corrosion allowance $C = 9 \text{ mm} = 9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ (Considering corrosive condition) (*Plant Design and Economics for Chemical Engineers*, 2003)

$$\text{So, } t_s = \frac{PD_i}{2SE-1.2P} + C$$

$$t_s = 10.43 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$$

$$= 10.43 \text{ mm}$$

Now, Outer diameter of the shell, $D_o = D_{in} + 2 \cdot t_s$

$$= 1.911 \text{ m}$$

Head Thickness calculation

Torispherical head is selected for the absorber because they provide efficient stress distribution under internal pressure while being more economical.

$$\text{Thickness of Head, } t_h = \frac{PR_c W}{2fJ} \text{ (Joshi, M. V. (n.d.), n.d.)}$$

Where, Welded Joint efficiency, $J = 0.85$

Crown radius, $R_c = D_i = 1.89 \text{ m}$

Knuckle radius, $R_k = 6\% \text{ of } R_c = 0.113 \text{ m}$

Maximum allowable stress $S = f = 9.50 \times 10^7 \text{ N/m}^2$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stress concentration factor, } W &= \frac{1}{4} \left(3 + \sqrt{\frac{R_c}{R_k}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \left(3 + \sqrt{\frac{1.89}{0.113}} \right) \\ &= 1.77 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, with corrosion allowance, $t_h = \frac{PR_c W}{2fJ} + C = 11.533 \text{ mm}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, Outer diameter of the head, } D_{oh} &= D_{in} + 2 * t_h \\ &= 1.914 \text{ m} \end{aligned}$$

Head Height Calculation

Outer Diameter of the head, $D_{oh\ t} = 1.914\text{ m}$

Figure 60: Colomn Head.[23]

For Torispherical heads,

Here, $D = 1.914\text{ m}$

Inside knuckle radius, $r = 0.1 D = 0.191\text{ m}$

Inside Radius, $R = 1.914\text{ m}$

Wall thickness before forming, $s = t_h = 11.533\text{ mm}$

Straight flange height, $h = 3.5 \times s$

$$= 0.0403\text{ m}$$

Height of Head, $H_h = 0.192D + s + h$

$$= 0.419\text{ m}$$

Manhole Thickness calculation

Two manholes, fabricated from carbon steel, are provided on the absorber shell to facilitate internal inspection, maintenance, and installation of column internals.

The opening diameter of the manhole is taken 0.6 m.

Now, Thickness of manhole, $t_m = \frac{D_i}{2} \times \left[\left\{ \frac{f_j + P}{f_j - P} \right\}^{0.5} - 1 \right] + C$ [20]

$$= \frac{1.89}{2} \times \left[\left\{ \frac{9.5 \times 10^7 \times 0.85 + 121590}{9.5 \times 10^7 \times 0.85 - 121590} \right\}^{0.5} - 1 \right] + 0.009$$

$$= 10.43\text{ mm}$$

Nozzle thickness calculation

Carbon steel was selected as the material of construction for both the gas inlet and liquid inlet nozzles.

Volumetric flow rate of gas, $Q_v = 12218 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

Density of gas = 1.19 kg/m^3

Taking Allowable momentum flux limit, $\rho_v \times v^2 = 2500 \text{ Pa}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Diameter of nozzle gas, } D_{ng} &= \sqrt{\frac{4Q_v}{1.4\pi \times 3600}} \times \left(\frac{\rho_v}{2500}\right)^{0.25} \\ &= 0.26 \text{ m} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thickness of nozzle gas, } t_{ng} &= \frac{PD_{ng}}{2f_j - P} + C \\ &= \frac{121590 \times 0.26}{2 \times 9.5 \times 10^7 \times 0.85 - 121590} + 0.009 \\ &= 9.19 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

Volumetric flow rate of liquid, $Q_L = 14.53 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Diameter of nozzle liquid, } D_{nl} &= \sqrt{\frac{4Q_L}{1.4\pi \times 3600}} \\ &= 0.061 \text{ m} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thickness of nozzle liquid, } t_{nl} &= \frac{PD_{ng}}{2f_j - P} + C \\ &= 9.04 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

Liquid Distributor

A trough distributor of Type DT 2 is selected for the absorber liquid inlet to ensure uniform irrigation of the packed bed. The distributor is specified to be fabricated from Carbon steel.

Outside Diameter = 1.85 m

Number of troughs = 6

Minimum width of support ring = 60 mm

Approximate Weight = 130 kg

Figure 61: Schematic of Liquid Distributor type DT 2[21].

Number of Packing Material Calculation

Here,

Tower inside diameter, $D = 1.89$ m

Packing height, $H = 5.5$ m

Nominal size, $d_p = 1$ inch = 0.0254 m

Porosity: $\epsilon = 0.18$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Tower packing volume, } V_{\text{packing}} &= \frac{\pi D^2 H}{4} \\ &= 15.4 \text{ m}^3\end{aligned}$$

Number of packing per cubic meters of tower volume = 59000 (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total number of 1" saddles, } N &= V_{\text{packing}} \times \text{Number of packing per m}^3 \\ &= 15.4 \times 59000 \\ &= 908,600\end{aligned}$$

So, the absorber requires roughly 909,000 intalox saddles (1" ceramic) for the packing height and tower diameter.

Figure 62: Intalox saddles (1" ceramic) figures (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

Total Column Height Calculation

Height of packing, $z = 5.50$ m

Height of head, $H_h = 0.419$ m

Height of packing support, $t_{ps} = 0.2$ m

Height of manhole = 0.6 m

Height of mist eliminator = 0.6 m

Total Height of the column without head = 7.50 m

Total Height of the column with head = 7.92 m

Pressure Drop Calculation

Pressure drop in packed tower,

$$\Delta P = h \times \gamma \times 10^{\frac{\phi L}{\rho_L}} \times \frac{G^2}{\rho_G}$$

where ΔP = pressure drop in psf

h = packed height = 5.50 m = 18 ft

L = superficial liquid mass velocity = 2014.85 lb/(h.ft²)

ρ_L = density of liquid = 118.61 lb/ft³

ρ_G = density of gas = 0.075 lb/ft³

From Table 4 [24]

$$\gamma = 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\phi = 0.0028$$

Thus $\Delta P = 36.72$ psf

Pressure drop per meter = 6.69 psf

Support Design

Skirt support is provided to ensure uniform load distribution, maintain structural stability, and facilitate safe installation. This support type is cost-effective for moderate diameters while keeping stresses within allowable limits.

Height of the skirt support = 3m

The inner diameter of the vessel, $D_i = 1.890$ m

The outer diameter of the vessel, $D_o = 1.911$ m

Outer diameter of the head = $D_{oh} = 1.914$ m

Height of packing, $z = 5.50$ m

Height of head, $H_h = 0.419$ m

Thickness of manhole, $t_m = 10.43$ mm

Mass of liquid distributor = 130 kg

Density of Carbon steel, $\rho_s = 7900$ kg/m³

Density of liquid, $\rho_L = 1797.6$ kg/m³

Bulk Density of packing, $\rho_p = 673$ kg/m³ (Towler, G., & Sinnott, R., 2013)

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Now, Weight of the shell} &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times (D_o^2 - D_i^2) \times H \rho_s g \\ &= 38.264 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of packing} &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times D_i^2 \times h_p \rho_p g \\ &= 102.037 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of liquid} &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times D_i^2 \times H \rho_L g \\ &= 414.671 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of two heads} &= \frac{2}{3} \times (D_{oh}^2 - R_c^2) \times H_h \rho_s g \times 2 \\ &= 3.8026 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of Packing Support} &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times D_i^2 \times t_{ps} \rho_s g \\ &= 43.5157 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of two manholes} &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times D_{manhole}^2 \times t_m \rho_s g \times 2 \\ &= 457.18 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of mist eliminator} &= \frac{\pi}{4} \times D_i^2 \times t_{mist} \rho_s g \\ &= 130.547 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Weight of Liquid Distributor} &= 130 \times 9.8 \\ &= 127.53 \text{ kN}\end{aligned}$$

So, total weight, $W = 734.57$ kN

Stress Analysis

Axial stress

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Axial stress due to pressure, } f_{ap} &= \frac{PD_i}{4(t_s - C)} \text{ Joshi, M. V. (n.d.).} \\ &= \frac{121590 \times 1.89}{4(0.0104 - 0.009)} \\ &= 4.01 \times 10^7 \text{ Pa}\end{aligned}$$

Stress due to the weight of the vessel

$$\text{Stress due to the weight of the vessel, } f_d = \frac{W}{\pi D_{sk} t_{sk}} \text{ Joshi, M. V. (n.d.).}$$

Where,

Diameter of the skirt, D_{sk} = Internal diameter of the vessel = 1.89 m

The thickness of the skirt support is t_{sk}

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress due to the weight of the vessel, } f_d &= \frac{734570}{3.14 \times 1.89 \times t_{sk}} \\ &= 123.78 \text{ kN/m.t}_{sk}\end{aligned}$$

Stress due to wind load

The forces due to wind load acting on the vessel are determined as

$P_{lw} = K \times P_1 \times H \times D_o$, for height below 20 m.[26]

Where K is the coefficient depending on the shape factor

Assume, $K = 0.7$ for cylindrical surface

D_o = Outside diameter of the column = 1.911 m

P_1 is the wind pressure for the lower part of the vessel = 700 N/m²

$P_{lw} = K \times P_1 \times H \times D_o = 0.7 \times 700 \times 7.92 \times 1.911 = 7422.3 \text{ N/m}^2$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Bending moment due to wind at the base of the vessel, } M_w &= P_{lw} \times \frac{H}{2} \\ &= 29408.3 \text{ N.m}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{The stress due to wind load will be, } f_w &= \frac{4M_w}{\pi D_o t_{sk}} \\ &= 19.603 \text{ kN/m.t}_{sk}\end{aligned}$$

Stress due to seismic load

$$\text{Stress due to seismic load, } f_{sb} = \frac{2CWH}{3 \pi (R_{sk})^2 t_{sk}}$$

Where,

Radius of the skirt, $R_{sk} = 0.945 \text{ m}$.

Seismic Coefficient, $C = 0.08$ of the earthquake (Zone IV)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stress due to seismic load, } f_{sb} &= \frac{2 \times 0.08 \times 734570 \times 7.92}{3 \pi (0.945)^2 t_{sk}} \\ &= 110.597 \text{ kN/mt}_{sk} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximum compressive stress, } f_{cmax} &= f_{sb} + f_d \\ &= (110.597 \text{ kN/mt}_{sk}) + (123.78 \text{ kN/m.t}_{sk}) \\ &= 234.377 \text{ kN/m.t}_{sk} \end{aligned}$$

Yield strength of CS SA-516 Gr 70 = 250 MPa

Now,

(1/3) Yield point $\geq f_c$ is permissible [26]

Here, $f_{cmax} = f_c$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, } f_c &= \frac{250 \text{ MPa}}{3} \\ &= 83.33 \text{ Mpa} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus, } t_{sk} &= \frac{234377}{83.33 \times 10^6} \\ &= 2.81 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

9.4.6 Tower Specifications

Table 52: Specification of B-102.

Item	Intermediate absorption Tower (Packed Column)
Item No	B-102
No of requirement	01
Code	ASME standards for vessels
Shell material	Carbon Steel (10.4 mm thickness)
Head type	Tori-spherical (11.5 mm thickness)
Manhole thickness	10.43 mm
Inner Diameter of Shell	1.89 m
Gas nozzle diameter	0.26 m
Liquid nozzle diameter	0.06 m
Gas nozzle thickness	9.2 mm
Liquid nozzle thickness	9.04 mm
Nozzle material	Carbon Steel
Support type	Skirt
Support material	Carbon Steel
Support outer diameter	1.893 m
Support thickness	2.8 mm
Packing type	Random
Packing material	1 inches intalox ceramic saddles
Liquid distributor	trough distributor of Type DT 2
Mist eliminator	Mesh pad

9.4.7 Mechanical Drawing

Figure 63: Schematic diagram of Intermediate Absorber

Figure 65: Top View of the Absorption Tower.

Figure 66: Top View of the Packing Support.

Figure 67: Top View of Mist Eliminator.

P&ID of Intermediate Absorption Tower (B-102)

Table 68: Table for control, measured and manipulated variables of P&ID.

Control Loop	Control Objective	Controlled Variable (CV)	Manipulated Variable (MV)
Temperature Control (TIC-101)	To maintain optimal absorption efficiency and protect materials from excessive heat and corrosion by regulating acid inlet temperature	Acid Inlet Temperature (Sensed by TT on the Acid Inlet line)	Cooling Water (CW) Flow Rate of the Heat Exchanger HE-108
Pressure Control (PIC-102)	To ensure stable column operation, prevent gas blow-through, and maintain the pressure required for downstream processes	Column Overhead Pressure (Sensed by PT)	Gas Outlet Flow Rate
Level Control (LIC-103)	To maintain a constant liquid inventory in the column and prevent the column from flooding	Liquid Level in the bottom of the absorber (Sensed by LT)	Liquid Product Flow Rate on the bottoms outlet

P&ID

Figure 69: P&ID diagram of Intermediate Absorption Tower (B- 102).

Here,

 = Pneumatic Signal

 = Check Valve

 = Control Valve

 = Gate Valve

- - - = Electrical Signal

 = Globe valve

 = Level transmitter

 = Level Indicating Controller

 = Temperature transmitter

 = PSV (Pressure Safety Valve)

 = Temperature Indicating Controller

 = Pressure Indicator

 = Pressure transmitter

 = Pressure Indicating Controller

 = Temperature Indicator

 = Flow Indicator

 = Transducer

10. HAZOP ANALYSIS

10.1 HAZOP analysis of Heat Exchanger (HE-102)

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HAZOP Study:

Table 53: HAZOP study applied to intermediate absorption tower pre-cooler.

Hazards & Operability Review						
Project name: Design of intermediate absorption pre-cooler (shell & tube heat exchanger)						
Process: Converter to intermediate absorption tower						
Section: Intermediate absorption pre-cooler (shell & tube heat exchanger, HE-102)						
Study node	Process parameters	Deviations	Possible causes	Possible consequences	Existing protection	Action required
Thermic fluid	Flow	No	1.Closed the control valve. 2.Failure of control valves & closed valves. 3. Blocked thermic fluid lines.	1. Inlet gas with high temperature to the intermediate absorber.	Temperature controller	1.Select valve to fail open. 2. Install thermic fluid flow meter & low flow alarm.
		High	1.Open the controlled valves. 2.Open the valves due to controller failure. 3. Mechanical failure in variable speed drive pump.	1.Vibration 2. Erosion.	Temperature controller	1.Install high flow alarm in the cooling water inlet.
		Low	1.Fouling. 2.Pump degradation.	1.Poor cooling.	Temperature controller	1.Install low flow alarm. 2.Continuous check & monitoring

						thermic fluid lines.
		Part of	Same causes as flow becomes low.	Same consequences as flow becomes low.	Same protection as flow becomes low.	Same actions as flow becomes low.
		Reverse	1.Failure of pump. 2.Due to high backpressure.	1.Gases may not cool down properly. 2. Process line efficiency may decrease.	Temperature controller.	1.Continuous check & monitor of pump. 2. Install non return valve.
		Other than	Considered not possible			
		Sonner than	1.Failure of pump. 2.Failure of controller & control valves.	1.Gases may not cool down properly. 2.Process efficiency degrades.	Temperature controller.	1.Continuous check & monitoring the
		Later than	Same causes as sooner than.	Same consequences as sooner than.	Same protection as sooner than.	Same actions as sooner than.

	Temperature	High	1. Scale formation on the tube side. 2. Inlet cooling water lower flow rate. 3. Higher flow rate of inlet gas mixture. 4. Warm conditions.	1. High temperature gases to the inlet of absorber. 2. Tube rupture. 3. Lower absorbance in the intermediate absorption tower.	Temperature controller.	1. Install high temperature alarm.
		Low	Not considered.	Not considered.	Not considered.	Not considered.
	Pressure	High	1. High gas flow rate.	Shell Rupture leading to release of gases in the environment.	Relief valves (Already considered)	Not considered.
		Low	1. Low gas flow rate.	Lower production rate in the absorber.	Not considered.	Install Low pressure alarm in the outlet of hot gas flow line.

10.2 HAZOP analysis of Air Drying Tower (D-101)

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HAZOP Analysis of Air Drying Tower (D-101)

Node: Air Drying Tower (D-101)

Design Intent: To dry "Moist Air" using "98% Sulfuric Acid" at a controlled flow rate ($m_{G_{in}}$), maintaining stable liquid height (H) and inside pressure (P) to get "Dry Air" and "97% H₂SO₄".

Table 54: HAZOP Analysis table for Air Drying Tower (D-101)

Parameter	Guide Word	Deviation	Causes (Typical)	Consequences	Existing Safeguards (from P&ID)	Recommendations
Pressure (P)	More	High pressure in tower	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Blockage in Dry Air outlet 2. FC fails open 3. Upstream surge 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Release of toxic/corrosive gases 2. Flange leaks 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PRV (Pressure Relief Valve) 2. PI (Pressure Indicator) 3. PT/PC loop 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install High-Pressure Alarm (PAH) 2. Regular PRV testing
Level (H)	More	High liquid level	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. LC outlet valve fails closed 2. Surge in H₂SO₄ inlet flow 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acid carryover into Dry Air line 2. Damage to downstream equipment 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. LT/LC (Level Control Loop) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install High-Level Alarm (HLA) 2. Redundant LT
	Less	Low liquid level	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Loss of acid supply 2. Pump failure 3. Rupture in outlet line 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Loss of liquid seal 2. Gas "blow-through" into acid outlet 3. Pump cavitation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. LT/LC (Level Control Loop) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install Low-Level Alarm (LLA) 2. Pump trip interlock
Flow ($m_{G_{in}}$)	No	No moist air flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upstream blower failure 2. Isolation valve closed in error 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Loss of production 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FT/FC (Flow Control Loop) 2. PI (Pressure Indicator) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install Low-Flow Alarm 2. Regular patrol of inlet lines
	No	No 98% Acid flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acid pump failure 2. Line blockage 3. Supply tank empty 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Moist air passes through 2. Severe corrosion in downstream units 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AT/AC (Analytical Control) on outlet gas 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low-Flow Alarm on acid line 2. Backup pump with auto-start
Composition ($x_{G_{out}}$)	Other than	High moisture in Dry Air	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Diluted acid 2. Low acid flow 3. Packing failure in D-101 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Downstream corrosion 2. Product quality degradation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AT/AC (Analytical/Moisture Control) on Dry Air line 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Frequent manual sampling 2. Check packing integrity
Temperature (T_{Lin})	More	High acid temperature	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Heat exchanger failure upstream 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduced absorption efficiency 2. Accelerated tower corrosion 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Variable T_{Lin} is monitored 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install High-Temp Alarm 2. Interlock to shut off feed 3. Install Temperature Controller (TC)

10.3 HAZOP analysis of 4 Bed Converter (B-101)

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Table 55: HAZOP analysis of 4 bed converter.

Study Node: 4 Bed Converter.					
Parameter	Guide Word	Possible Causes	Possible Consequences	Existing Safeguards	Recommendations
Temperature	More	1. High inlet stream temperature	1. High temperature will cause lesser yield. 2. High temperature may cause catalyst deactivation	1. Temperature indicator provided. 2. Temperature controller provided.	1. Install high temperature alarm and temperature reading.
	Less	1. Poor incoming air temperature. 2. Poor flow of SO ₂ .	1. Reaction rate will be lower. 2. Poor flowrate may create vacuum.	1. Temperature indicator provided. 2. Temperature controller provided.	1. Regular maintenance of the flow pipes.
Pressure	More	1. Incoming air/sulfur dioxide flow is more than set value.	1. Opening of the relief valve. 2. Deposition of gas in the relief tank. 3. Low conversion rate.	1. Pressure control is provided. 2. Relief system is provided.	1. More relief tanks can be installed.
	Less	1. Low flow of air/sulfur dioxide.	1. Vacuum buildup.	-	1. Install pressure detector.
Flowrate	More	1. Higher gas flowrate than set value	1. Opening of the relief valve. 2. Deposition of gas in the relief tank. 3. Low conversion rate.	1. Pressure control is provided. 2. Relief system is provided	1. Flow rate indicator should be installed.
	Less	1. Less air flow rate. 2. Disturbance in furnace.	10.1 Vacuum buildup.	-	1. Install pressure detector.
Moisture	Presence of moisture	1. Malfunction in air dryer.	1. Catalyst poisoning.	-	1. Moisture content should be tested regularly.

10.4 HAZOP analysis of Intermediate Absorption Tower (B-102)

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Table 56: Study Node 1: Gas Inlet Line at Absorber Bottom

Design Intent: To supply SO₃ containing gas to the absorber at appropriate flow, temperature, and near-atmospheric pressure for effective absorption.

Parameter	Guideword	Deviation	Possible Causes	Consequences	Existing Safeguards	Recommendations
Flow	No	No gas flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Inlet valve closed Severe blockage in gas line 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> No absorption Circulation of acid without conversion Plant throughput loss 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Absorber Inlet Gas Flow indicator 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Install low flow alarm at inlet
	More	Excess gas flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Excess converter throughput Operator error during converter operation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced gas liquid contact time Incomplete SO₃ absorption Increased acid mist carryover Increased pressure drop across packed bed and mist eliminator 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Absorber inlet Gas Pressure indicator Absorber Inlet Gas Flow indicator 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Install high-flow alarm Operating procedure to limit converter gas rate based on absorber capacity
	Less	Low gas flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced converter throughput Partial blockage or fouling in gas line Operator initiated load reduction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Non - optimal gas liquid contact time Reduced SO₃ absorption efficiency Over-wetting of packing at fixed acid circulation rate Increased operating cost 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Absorber Inlet Gas Flow indicator Absorber inlet pressure indicator 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Install low gas flow alarm at absorber inlet SOP defining minimum gas flow for stable absorber operation
Pressure	More	High pressure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Gas outlet blockage Mist eliminator fouling 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Column overpressure PSV lifting Acid mist release 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> PSV 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Routine inspection and cleaning of mist eliminator
Temperature	More	High gas temperature	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Upstream converter upset Cooling failure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Acid degradation Accelerated corrosion Increased mist formation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Inlet Gas Temperature indication via DCS 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure proper maintenance of upstream gas cooling system. Define maximum

						allowable inlet temperature.
	Less	Gas cooler than expected	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upstream converter upset 2. Ambient Cooling effect 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduced absorption efficiency 2. Minor condensation possible 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inlet Gas Temperature indication via DCS 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Ensure temperature remains within normal operating range

Table 57: Study Node 2: Acid Inlet Line & Liquid Distributor

Design Intent: To uniformly distribute 98% H₂SO₄ over the packed bed at controlled temperature and flow.

Parameter	Guide word	Deviation	Possible Causes	Consequences	Existing Safeguards	Recommendations
Flow	No	No liquid flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pump failure 2. Inlet valve closed 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dry packing 2. SO₃ breakthrough 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acid flow indication at inlet 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide standby acid pump 2. Implement startup verification in SOP
	More	Excess liquid flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pump overspeed 2. Valve stuck open 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Flooding of packing 2. Increased pressure drop 3. Potential acid carryover 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acid flow monitoring by Flow Indicator 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High acid flow alarm and operating procedure limits 2. Periodic pump check
	Less	Low liquid flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pump wear 2. Distributor fouling 3. Partial blockage in line 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Poor wetting of packing 2. Unabsorbed SO₃ in outlet gas 3. Reduced absorption efficiency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acid flow indication 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Periodic distributor inspection 2. Pump maintenance
Temperature	More	Hot acid	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cooling water failure in HE-108 2. Heat exchanger fouling 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Severe corrosion 2. acid mist formation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TIC-101 2. Alarm on DCS 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define maximum operating temperature 2. SOP limits for startup/shutdown
Distribution	Other	Maldistribution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plugged distributor holes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Channeling 2. Reduced efficiency 3. Local Hot spots 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Proper distributor design 2. Proper maintenance practices 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure uniform acid distribution 2. Increase inspection frequency

Table 58: Study Node 3: Packed Bed Section

Design Intent: To provide sufficient contact area and residence time for mass transfer between gas and liquid phases.

Parameter	Guideword	Deviation	Possible Causes	Consequences	Existing Safeguards	Recommendations
Pressure Drop	More	High ΔP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Flooding 2. Fouled packing 3. Mist eliminator blockage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Overpressure 2. PSV lift 3. Capacity loss 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PSV 2. PIC-102 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install DP transmitter across packed bed with high ΔP alarm
	Less	Low ΔP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Packing collapse 2. Channeling 3. Low acid flow 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Poor gas - liquid contact 2. Reduced absorption efficiency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acid flow indication and operator control 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitor ΔP and absorption efficiency to detect abnormal behavior
Temperature	More	Local hot spots	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dry zones due to low acid flow 2. Maldistribution 3. High inlet gas or liquid temperature 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Packing damage 2. Corrosion 3. Acid mist formation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TIC-101 2. Gas Inlet temperature indication via DCS 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Perform thermal inspection during shutdown 2. Ensure uniform liquid distribution

Table 59: Study Node 4: Bottoms Liquid Outlet & Level Control

Design Intent: To maintain stable liquid inventory and remove product oleum safely.

Parameter	Guideword	Deviation	Possible Causes	Consequences	Existing Safeguards	Recommendations
Level	More	High level of Liquid	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> LIC-103 failure Outlet valve closed Downstream blockage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Flooding Increased ΔP 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> LIC-103 PSV Drain valve (V-118) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Install independent high-level alarm (LAH)
	Less	Low level of liquid	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Excess withdrawal Leakage Faulty level measurement 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Poor liquid distribution Dry packing Hot spots Reduced absorption efficiency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> LIC-103 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Install low-level alarm to prevent operation under dry conditions
Flow	No	No liquid out	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Outlet isolation valve closed Valve failure Line blockage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Column flooding Rising column pressure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> LIC-103 PSV Drain valve (V-118) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Implement routine inspection and maintenance of the bottom line and drain valve (V-118)

Table 60: Study Node 5: Gas Outlet Line

Design Intent: To discharge treated gas with minimal acid mist carryover.

Parameter	Guide word	Deviation	Possible Causes	Consequences	Existing Safeguards	Recommendations
Flow	No	No gas outflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Outlet isolation valve closed 2. Severe mist eliminator plugging 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rapid pressure rise 2. PSV lifting 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PSV 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install high-pressure alarm
Pressure	More	High pressure at outlet	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mist eliminator fouling or blockage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PSV lifting 2. Acid mist emission 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PSV 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install DP transmitter across packed bed with high ΔP alarm
Composition	Other	Acid mist carryover	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mist pad damage 2. Improper installation 3. High gas velocity 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Visible stack emissions 2. Downstream corrosion 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mist eliminator 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish inspection and scheduled replacement program

11. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

11.1 Introduction

Sulfuric acid manufacturing plant is a major chemical industry plant that involves the handling of hazardous raw materials and the generation of acidic emissions, effluents, and solid residues. Due to the highly corrosive and environmentally sensitive nature of sulfuric acid production, such facilities have the potential to significantly affect air quality, water resources, soil characteristics, and surrounding communities if not properly designed and managed. Therefore, careful planning, regulatory compliance, and environmental safeguards are essential to ensure that the plant operates in an environmentally responsible manner.

Land-use regulations such as zoning ordinances and building codes play a critical role in guiding industrial development and protecting natural resources through environmental laws and zoning policies. These regulatory frameworks are implemented by environmental authorities to control pollution, manage waste streams, and protect environmental quality. Environmental regulations, issued by DOE, generally address key areas such as air pollution control through emission standards and discharge permits, water pollution management through treatment requirements and discharge limits and solid and hazardous waste management through restrictions on disposal practices and legal responsibility for safe handling. In addition, environmental governance requires prior evaluation of proposed projects to assess their potential environmental and social consequences.

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is a structured decision-support tool used to identify, predict and evaluate the potential environmental impacts of a project before it is implemented. The main objective of an EIA is to integrate environmental considerations into the planning and approval stages of development. This process helps decision-makers avoid or minimize adverse impacts and ensures that appropriate mitigation measures are incorporated into project design.

An EIA study generally includes impact identification, prediction and evaluation as core components. The process begins with preliminary environmental screening and collection of background information to guide detailed field investigations. Experienced engineers and environmental professionals then assess baseline environmental conditions within the project's zone of influence. This includes generating baseline data for air quality, surface and groundwater, soil quality, noise levels and biological components such as vegetation.

A comprehensive assessment of the proposed production process is carried out to identify potential pollution sources and evaluate the adequacy of planned pollution control technologies. Predictive tools and, where applicable, dispersion and impact models are applied to estimate future environmental changes. Based on these findings, an Environmental Management Plan (EMP) is developed, outlining appropriate mitigation, monitoring, and management measures to ensure regulatory compliance and environmental protection throughout the construction and operational phases of the sulfuric acid plant.

11.2 Environmental impact assessment and mitigation plan

11.2.1 Soil and Geology

Assessment: Dilarpur is located within the Madhupur Tract and the Old Brahmaputra Floodplain. The soil is primarily composed of Madhupur Clay and silt. Geologically, Narsingdi falls under Seismic Zone II (Moderate Risk) according to the Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC) discussed in chapter 3.3.3 and 3.3.4.

Impact: Construction and operational activities can affect soil quality and local geology. Excavation and leveling during construction may cause temporary soil erosion and improper handling of sulfuric acid or by-products can contaminate soil. Risk of soil acidification from acid spillage and structural instability due to the soft sedimentary nature of floodplain soil.

Mitigation:

1. **Piling & Foundation:** Deep piling and reinforced foundation systems shall be adopted to ensure structural stability under soft clay–silt conditions and moderate seismic risk. Structural design shall comply with BNBC seismic provisions to minimize vibration-related soil failure.
2. **Impermeable Lining:** All storage areas must have high-density polyethylene (HDPE) liners or acid-proof brick flooring to protect the Madhupur clay layer from seepage.
3. **Spill Prevention and Rapid Neutralization:** Spill response kits containing lime or soda ash shall be placed at critical locations. Any accidental acid spillage shall be immediately neutralized and contaminated soil shall be removed and disposed of as hazardous waste.
4. **Soil Erosion Control During Construction:** Temporary measures such as silt fences, compacted access roads, controlled excavation, and proper storage of topsoil shall be implemented to minimize erosion and sediment transport.
5. **Regular Soil Monitoring:** Periodic soil sampling shall be conducted around storage tanks, process units, and waste handling areas to monitor pH, sulfate concentration, and potential contamination. Corrective measures shall be taken if abnormal changes, such as pH fluctuation or contamination are detected.
6. **Controlled Waste and Debris Management:** Construction debris and excavated materials shall be disposed of at approved locations. Contaminated soil, if generated, shall be handled as hazardous waste in accordance with environmental regulations.

11.2.2 Air Quality

Assessment: Air emissions arise from both construction and operation phases. Construction generates dust and particulate matter, while operation produces SO₂, SO₃, acid mist and fine particulate matter via Contact Process. In the absence of proper control systems, these pollutants may react with atmospheric moisture to form acidic aerosols and acid rain, which can adversely affect nearby agricultural areas in Narsingdi, particularly sensitive crops such as bananas and leafy vegetables.

Impact: Potential for Acid Mist and high SO₂ concentrations in the immediate downwind area of Dilarpur. If the pollution level reached a critical level, individuals at risk will feel immediate effects. Short-term exposure to high concentrations can lead to noticeable health effects even among healthy individuals, while sensitive groups (children, elderly people and individuals with respiratory conditions) are more vulnerable. The yearly data was collected from air plume-labs website.

Figure 70: AQI of Narsingdi from September 2025 to February 2026 (Air Plumelabs, n.d.)
(Environmental Conservation Rules (ECR) 2023, n.d.)

Figure 71: Different pollutant concentration in Narsingdi and comparison with near areas

(Air Plumelabs, n.d.)

Mitigation:

1. Efficient Mist Eliminators: The efficiency of mist eliminators in absorption towers and drying towers should be monitored properly. Their performance will be routinely inspected, cleaned, and maintained to prevent deterioration in removal efficiency.
2. Emission Control: Regular leak detection and repair (LDAR) programs will be implemented.
3. Construction Phase Dust Control: Water spraying on unpaved roads, covering of construction materials, speed control of vehicles, and use of dust suppressants will be enforced to minimize particulate emissions during construction.
4. CEMS: A real-time monitoring unit will be installed at the stack to provide 24/7 data of a Continuous Emission Monitoring System (CEMS) to track SO_x levels.

11.2.3 Liquid Waste

Assessment: Large volumes of water are used for cooling. Liquid waste comes from process water, boiler condensate and accidental spills.

Impact: Untreated or inadequately treated effluent may lead to acidification and thermal pollution of nearby surface water bodies and contamination of shallow groundwater, affecting aquatic life, irrigation suitability and domestic water sources in the surrounding areas, including the distributaries of the Brahmaputra River system.

Mitigation:

1. Emergency Response for Liquid Spills: Spill kits, neutralizing agents (lime or soda ash), and emergency response procedures shall be available at all critical locations. Operators will be trained to contain and neutralize accidental liquid releases immediately.
2. Water Recycling and Reuse: Treated effluent and boiler condensate shall be reused for coolers, floor washing, gardening, and utility purposes wherever feasible. This will significantly reduce freshwater withdrawal and liquid waste discharge.
3. Thermal Load Management: Hot effluent streams shall be passed through cooling ponds or heat exchangers to avoid thermal shock to treatment systems and receiving water bodies.
4. Online Monitoring and Compliance Checks: Online pH, temperature, and flow monitoring systems will be installed. Periodic laboratory analysis of COD, TDS, sulfate and heavy metals will ensure compliance with discharge standards. (*Department of Environment (DoE). (2021)., n.d.*)

11.2.4 Solid Waste

Assessment: Solid waste is generated from plant operations, maintenance activities, and domestic sources. The major industrial solid wastes include spent vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5) catalyst, sulfur furnace slag/ash, filter residues and sludge from pollution control units. In addition, non-hazardous domestic waste is produced from offices and worker facilities. Among these, spent catalyst and sulfur furnace slag are classified as hazardous due to their chemical composition and potential toxicity.

Impact: Improper handling or disposal of spent catalyst containing V_2O_5 may result in leaching of toxic metals into soil and groundwater, posing risks to terrestrial ecosystems and agricultural productivity. Uncontrolled disposal of sulfur furnace slag and contaminated sludge may also

lead to localized soil contamination and long-term degradation of land quality. (*Hazardous Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, Bangladesh. (n.d.)*, n.d.)

Mitigation:

1. **Secure and Segregated Storage:** Spent catalysts must be stored in leak-proof, concrete-lined pits before being sent to an authorized hazardous waste recycler.
2. **Sulfur Purification and Furnace Optimization:** Sulfur feedstock shall be filtered and purified prior to combustion to reduce ash and slag formation. Optimizing furnace operating conditions will further minimize slag generation.
3. **Waste Minimization:** Catalyst life shall be maximized through proper operating temperature control and prevention of catalyst poisoning. This reduces the frequency of catalyst replacement and overall hazardous waste generation.
4. **Authorized Recycling and Disposal:** Hazardous solid wastes such as spent catalyst and contaminated slag shall be transported only by licensed contractors to authorized hazardous waste treatment, recycling, or disposal facilities. Documentation and tracking of waste movement shall be maintained.
5. **Periodic Environmental Audits:** Regular audits shall be carried out to ensure compliance with hazardous waste management regulations and to identify opportunities for waste reduction and reuse.

11.2.5 Noise, Light, and Vibration Pollution

Assessment: Noise and vibration are primarily generated from continuous operation of mechanical equipment such as pumps, compressors, turbines, generators, blowers, and material handling systems. High-velocity air blowers and rotating machinery produce steady background noise and low-frequency vibrations. In addition, high-intensity lighting used for night-time operations may cause light spills beyond the plant boundary.

Impact: Prolonged exposure to elevated noise levels may cause nuisance and discomfort to nearby residential communities in Dilarpur and can disturb local livestock, potentially affecting animal behavior and productivity. Continuous vibration may also contribute to worker fatigue and, over time, may affect the structural integrity of equipment foundations. Light pollution may disrupt the natural nighttime environment and cause visual discomfort to nearby residents. (*Noise Pollution (Control) Rules 2006, Bangladesh. (n.d.)*. Doelab., n.d.)

Mitigation:

1. **Acoustic Barriers:** Major noise-generating equipment such as the main air blower, compressors, and turbines shall be housed in acoustically insulated enclosures. Noise barriers will be installed around high-noise zones to ensure compliance with industrial noise limits (≤ 75 dB during daytime and ≤ 70 dB at night at the plant boundary).
2. **Vibration Pads:** Installing Anti-vibration Mounts (AVM) under heavy rotating machinery to absorb vibrations and prevent their transmission to the ground and surrounding structures.
3. **Operational Scheduling:** Maintenance activities involving high noise levels shall be scheduled during daytime hours where possible to minimize disturbance to nearby communities.
4. **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):** Workers in high-noise areas shall be provided with appropriate hearing protection such as earplugs or earmuffs. Exposure duration will be managed in accordance with occupational noise standards.
5. **Regular Monitoring:** Periodic noise and vibration monitoring shall be conducted at the plant boundary and near sensitive receptors. Corrective actions will be taken if measured values exceed permissible limits.

11.2.6 Occupational Health & Safety**Impact Assessment:**

In the heat exchangers, excessive high gas pressure can lead to PSV uplifting, causing a massive release of SO_2 and SO_3 into the workplace. Malfunctions in the Air-Drying Tower (D-101) level control can cause acid carryover into dry air lines, leading to severe chemical burns or equipment corrosion. The 4-bed converter requires careful management of V_2O_5 catalyst. High temperatures (above 450°C) can deactivate the catalyst, while moisture ingress leads to catalyst poisoning. Absorption failures in the tower (B-102) can release unabsorbed SO_3 as a corrosive mist.

Mitigation:

1. **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):** Workers must be equipped with specialized PPE, including PVC suits, acid-resistant boots, and masks with gas filters to protect against SO_2 , SO_3 , and acid mist exposure (Team, 2025, 2025).

2. **Emergency Wash Facilities:** Emergency eye-wash stations and safety showers shall be installed near high-risk units, particularly around the absorption towers and the D-101 drying tower to allow immediate decontamination in case of accidental exposure. (Team, 2025, 2025)
3. **On-site Neutralization Facilities:** Adequate quantities of neutralizing agents such as sodium bicarbonate or milk of magnesia shall be stored on-site to allow rapid neutralization of acid splashes and small floor spills, minimizing injury and secondary corrosion risks (Team, 2025, 2025).
4. **Regular Health Surveillance:** Periodic medical check-ups focusing on respiratory function, skin condition, and eye health shall be conducted for workers exposed to sulfuric acid fumes and mists. Health records will be maintained to identify early signs of occupational illness.
5. **Safe Work Zoning and Signage:** High-risk zones shall be clearly marked with hazard signage and access restrictions. Only trained and authorized personnel will be allowed entry into areas with potential SO₂/SO₃ exposure or hot acid handling.

11.2.7 Resource Consumption

Impact Assessment:

A 100 MTPD sulfuric acid plant requires large volumes of water for cooling due to the highly exothermic nature of the process. As Narsingdi is already an industrially intensive area, excessive groundwater abstraction from the Dilarpur aquifer may lower the water table and affect local agriculture. Discharge of hot cooling water from units such as the Intermediate Absorption Pre-cooler (HE-102) into nearby rivers like the Meghna or Shitalakhya can cause thermal shock to aquatic life. In the humid climate of the region, sulfur dust may form acidic runoff, potentially degrading the Madhupur Clay soil structure. Additionally, the spent Vanadium Pentoxide (V₂O₅) catalyst is a hazardous waste, and improper disposal poses a serious risk of soil and groundwater contamination.

Mitigation:

1. **Water Recycling and Thermal Control:** Coolers are used to recycle cooling water with only minimal make-up requirements.
2. **Waste Heat Recovery and Energy Efficiency:** Waste heat from the sulfur burner and 4-bed converter have been recovered through waste heat boilers to generate high-pressure steam,

which will be used to drive turbines for powering pumps and blowers, significantly reducing external energy demand.

3. **Safe Sulfur Storage and Leachate Control:** Elemental sulfur is stored in covered and paved storage areas equipped with leachate collection systems to prevent acidic runoff and seepage into surrounding soils in Narsingdi.
4. **Spent Catalyst Regeneration and Safe Disposal:** Deactivated vanadium pentoxide catalysts are returned to authorized manufacturers for regeneration or sent to licensed hazardous waste handlers, preventing improper disposal in local landfills and reducing environmental risks.

11.2.8 Climate Change & Carbon Footprint

Impact Assessment:

Transportation of elemental sulfur to Dilarpur and distribution of sulfuric acid to nearby industries rely on diesel-powered trucks, contributing to CO₂ emissions. The Contact Process is highly exothermic and uncontrolled release of reaction heat to the environment represents energy loss, increasing dependence on external power and indirectly raising the carbon footprint. Accidental SO₂ leakage from units such as the Intermediate Absorption Tower (B-102) can form sulfate aerosols in the atmosphere. Although these aerosols may reflect solar radiation, they are toxic and can damage vegetation, thereby reducing local carbon sequestration capacity and worsening ecosystem degradations.

Mitigation:

1. **Energy-Efficient Utilities:** Equip pumps, blowers, and compressors with high-efficiency motors and variable-frequency drives (VFDs) to optimize electricity use and reduce CO₂ emissions associated with power consumption.

11.2.9 Biodiversity & Ecosystem Impacts

Impact Assessment:

The Madhupur Clay soils in Dilarpur support microbial communities essential for nitrogen fixation. Acidic seepage from sulfur storage or accidental spills can sterilize the topsoil, reducing soil fertility. {Citation} The local drainage eventually connects to the Meghna River system, so any accidental release of acidic effluent or concentrated acid mist may lower the pH of nearby wetlands (beels). Most local aquatic species, including Rui and Catla fish and macroinvertebrates, cannot survive if the water pH falls below 5.0.((PDF) *Environmental Impact of Chemical Industry Air Pollutants (Sulfuric Acid Production) Submitted To*, n.d.)

Mitigation:

1. Acid Mist Control: High-efficiency mist eliminators shall be installed and routinely maintained in the Intermediate Absorption Tower and Final Absorption Tower to prevent acid plume formation and off-site dispersion toward nearby residential and agricultural areas.
2. Absorber Process Control: Inlet gas flow indicators with low-flow alarms shall be used to maintain optimal gas-to-liquid ratios in the absorption towers, ensuring efficient SO₃ capture and preventing unabsorbed emissions to the atmosphere.

P&ID

Figure 72: P & ID diagram of Intermediate absorber with inlet gas flow indicators & low flow alarm

11.2.10 Socio-Economic Development Options

Impact Assessment:

The establishment of a sulfuric acid plant in Dilarpur provides a local source of sulfuric acid, significantly reducing logistics costs and the risks associated with transporting hazardous chemicals over long distances. Local availability of sulfuric acid will support textile industries, alum production for water treatment in nearby dyeing plants, and phosphate fertilizer production for surrounding agricultural lands. Furthermore, the operation of complex units such as the 4-Bed Converter and DCDA towers requires skilled labor, creating employment opportunities and fostering career development for engineering graduates in the region.

Mitigation:

1. **Community Safety and Early Warning Systems:** High-pressure alarms on the drying tower and temperature controllers on the pre-cooler shall be integrated with a localized siren system and regular community safety drills. Periodic awareness sessions will be conducted for nearby residents to communicate risks, emergency actions and safety measures, strengthening trust and preparedness.
2. **Transport and Infrastructure Management:** Access roads and tanker routes shall be reinforced and routinely maintained to withstand heavy vehicle loads. Dedicated entry and exit routes for hazardous material transport will be designated to minimize traffic disruption and reduce accident risks in residential areas.
3. **Community Health Monitoring and Support:** A baseline health survey of residents in Dilarpur shall be established, followed by periodic respiratory health screening to track potential long-term exposure trends and to verify the performance of emission control systems such as mist eliminators and DCDA units [8].
4. **Local Employment and Skill Development:** Preference will be given to local residents for non-specialized jobs, and technical training or apprenticeship opportunities will be supported in collaboration with nearby institutions to improve employability and ensure long-term socio-economic benefits for the community.

11.2.11 Emergency Preparedness & Disaster Management

Impact Assessment:

A failure in the Absorption Tower (B-102) or a shell rupture in the Pre-cooler (HE-102) could release a dense cloud of sulfur trioxide, which reacts with the humid air of Narsingdi to form a hazardous white acid mist capable of traveling several kilometers and causing severe respiratory distress. Similarly, a rupture in bulk storage tanks or a malfunction in the Air-Drying Tower (D-101) level control could result in a large-scale release of 98% sulfuric acid. Given that Dilarpur is located in BNBC Seismic Zone II, an earthquake could compromise the structural integrity of the 4-bed converter or storage vessels, potentially triggering simultaneous fire and chemical leaks. ((PDF) Assessment of Geo-Engineering Properties of Madhupur Clay Soil in Narsingdi, Bangladesh: Implications for Civil Construction, n.d.)

Mitigation:

1. Pressure Relief and Overpressure Protection: Redundant Pressure Relief Valves (PRVs) and High-Pressure Alarms (PAHs) shall be installed on the D-101 tower and converter to prevent vessel overpressure and potential rupture.

Piping and Instrumentation Diagram of Air Drying Tower (D-101)

Figure 73: Piping and instrumentation tower for air drying tower

2. **Moisture Control in Dry Air System:** Continuous online monitoring of moisture content in the dry air line shall be implemented to prevent catalyst poisoning, corrosion of downstream equipment and loss of process efficiency.
3. **Chemical Spill Neutralization Capacity:** Adequate quantities of lime (calcium carbonate) shall be stockpiled on-site for rapid neutralization of acid spills before contaminants can reach groundwater or nearby surface water bodies. (Team, 2025, 2025)
4. **Emergency Response Equipment and PPE:** On-site emergency response teams shall have 24/7 access to Self-Contained Breathing Apparatus (SCBA) and acid-proof Level A protective suits to ensure safe intervention during gas releases or acid spill incidents. (Team, 2025, 2025)
5. **Local Medical Preparedness and Capacity Building:** Nearby clinics in Narsingdi shall be supported through training and basic preparedness programs to ensure effective treatment of acid inhalation injuries and chemical burns during emergency situations.

11.3 Conclusion

The Environmental Impact Assessment of the sulfuric acid plant demonstrates that the project has the potential to generate notable environmental impacts on air quality, surface and groundwater resources, soil properties, noise environment, and surrounding ecosystems if adequate control measures are not implemented. The main environmental risks are associated with sulfur dioxide and acid mist emissions, low pH liquid effluents, hazardous solid wastes such as spent catalysts and continuous noise and vibration from plant operations. In addition, occupational health and community safety are important considerations due to the hazardous nature of sulfuric acid production and handling.

The assessment further indicates that these impacts can be effectively managed through the application of appropriate pollution prevention and control technologies, proper waste treatment and disposal systems, resource-efficient practices, and continuous environmental monitoring. The proposed mitigation plans provide structured framework for implementing mitigation measures, monitoring environmental performance and ensuring compliance with relevant environmental regulations and standards throughout the construction and operational phases of the project.

With strict adherence to the management plan, periodic environmental audits, and commitment to best available techniques and continuous improvement, the sulfuric acid plant can operate in an environmentally responsible manner. Therefore, the project may be considered environmentally acceptable, provided that all recommended mitigation and monitoring measures are fully implemented and regularly reviewed to minimize long-term environmental and social impacts.

12. PLANT LAYOUT

12.1 Plant Layout

The industry is assumed to be established at the northern coast of Dilarpur, Narsingdi. Apart from the necessary equipments, the plant also contains a sulfur storage warehouse, tank farm, pump farm, heat exchanger farm, workshop, utility building, E & I maintenance, laboratory, fire station, medical center and a mosque. We also have a parking area and security checkpoint near the entrance. The main road inside the industry is a 9m wide L shaped road which ensures easy passing of the trucks. Enough space and ventilation for movement have been allotted among each of the buildings.

Figure 74: Plant layout of the sulfuric acid plant

13. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

13.1 Cost of Equipment

The table below summarizes the costs of all equipment required for the construction of the process plant. The prices are quoted on a purchased equipment Free on Board (FOB) basis. These cost data have been collected from sources including Made-in-China, Alibaba, and Matche.com.

Table 61: Cost of the heat exchangers.

Serial	Heat Exchanger	Construction Material	Area (ft ²)	Cost (USD)
1	HE-101	SS 416	16	2,304
2	HE-102	SS 416	390	56,160
3	HE-103	SS 416	30	4,320
4	HE-104	SS 416	57	8,208
5	HE-105	SS 416	22	3,168
6	HE-106	SS 416	10	1,440
7	HE-107	SS 416	79	11,376
8	HE-108	SS 416	74	10,656
9	HE-109	SS 416	342	49,248
Total				146,880

Table 62: Cost of the pumps.

Serial	Pump	Power (kW)	Cost (USD)
1	P-101	35	3500
2	P-102	203	2800
3	P-103	30	1500
4	P-104	5	450
Total			8250

Table 63: Cost of other equipment.

Equipment	Name	Material of Construction	Cost (USD)	Reference
FI-101	Filter	Stainless Steel HEPA-Grade	2,000	(Silvia, 2025)
BL-101	Blower	CS	4,000	(<i>Product on Alibaba.Com, n.d.</i>)
D-101	Drying tower	Brick-lined CS	153,000	(<i>Product on Alibaba.Com, n.d.</i>)
F-102	S melter		5,000	(<i>[Hot Item] Sulphonation Plant Sulfur Melting Tank, n.d.</i>)
F-101	Furnace	CS with Fire brick and Insulating brick	200,000	[67]
B-101	4 bed converters	SS 316	600,000	[65]
B-102	IAT	Brick-lined CS	145,700	(<i>Voc Absorption Tower Odor Treatment</i>)
B-103	FAT IAT	Brick-lined CS	136,000	(<i>Voc Absorption Tower Odor Treatment</i>)
T-101	Oleum dilution tank	CS	44,200	[66]
T-103	Acid storage tank	CS	152,600	[66]
T-104	Oleum storage tank	CS	43,400	[66]
T-102	Acid circulation tank	CS	36,300	[66]
-	Turbine	-	143,000	[69]
-	Valves	-	5,000	[70]

Total purchase cost (in USD) = \$ 1825330

(Freight + Import + Transportation) charges = 35%

Delivered equipment cost (in USD) = \$ 2,464,196

13.2 Determination of Fixed Capital Investment

Table 64: Estimation of Capital Investment

Items	Percentage of delivered equipment cost for fluid processing plant (%)	Cost (USD)
Direct Cost		
Purchased equipment (Delivered)	100	2,464,195.50
Installation	47	1,158,171.89
Instrumentation and control	36	887,110.38
Piping	68	1,675,652.94
Electrical	11	271,061.51
Building	18	443,555.19
Yard	10	246,419.55
Service facilities	70	1,724,936.85
Land	-	2,800,000.00
Total Direct Cost		11,671,103.80
Indirect Cost		
Engineering and supervision	33	813,184.52
Construction and expenses	41	1,010,320.16
Legal expenses	4	98,567.82
Contractor's fee	22	542,123.01
Contingency	44	1,084,246.02
Total Indirect Cost		3,548,441.52
Fixed Capital Investment		15,219,545.32
Working Capital Investment		2,685,802.12
Total Capital Investment		17,905,347.44

13.3 Determination of TPC

From Table 05,

$$\text{TPC} = \text{Direct Cost} + \text{Fixed Charge} + \text{Plant Overhead} + \text{General Expense}$$

Here, Direct cost

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{Raw material} + (0.1 + 0.015 + 0.15 + 0.01 + 0.005) \times \text{TPC} \\ &+ (0.05 + 0.005) \times \text{FCI} \\ &= \$3326551 + 0.28 \times \text{TPC} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fixed Charge} &= \text{Depriciation} + (0.02 + 0.01 + 0.03) \times \text{FCI} = \$558879 + 0.06 \times \text{FCI} \\ &= \$1552626 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Plant Overhead} = 0.07 \times \text{TPC}$$

$$\text{General Expense} = (0.02 + 0.05 + 0.0005) \times \text{TPC} = 0.0705 \times \text{TPC}$$

Now,

$$\text{TPC} = \$3326551 + 0.28 \times \text{TPC} + \$1552626 + (0.07 \times \text{TPC}) + (0.0705 \times \text{TPC})$$

$$\therefore \text{TPC} = \mathbf{\$8,419,634}$$

Table 65: Estimation of total production cost.

Manufacturing Cost		
Direct Production Costs	Percent. (%)	Cost (USD)
Raw materials	-	2,489,476.57
Operating labor (10-20% of total product cost)	10	841,963.40
Direct supervisory (10-20% of operating labor cost)	1.5	126,294.51
Utilities (10-20% of total product cost)	15	1,262,945.10
Maintenance and repairs (2- 10% FCI)	5	760,977.27
Operating supplies (0.5-1% of FCI)	0.5	76,097.73
Laboratory charges (10-20% of operating labor)	1	84,196.34
Patents and royalties (0-6% of total product cost)	0.5	42,098.17
Fixed Charges		
Depreciation (10% of fixed capital investment for machinery)	10	558,879.54
Local taxes (1-4% of fixed capital investment)	2	304,390.91
Insurance (0.4-1% of fixed capital investment)	1	152,195.45
Financing (10% of total production cost)	3	537,160.42
General Expenses		
Administrative costs (2- 5 % Of total product cost)	2	168,392.68
Distribution costs (2 - 20 % of total product cost)	5	420,981.70
R&D (about 5 % of total product cost)	0.05	4,209.82
Total Production Cost		8,419,633.97

13.4 Profit and Profitability Analysis

Profit Calculation

Price of H_2SO_4 = \$320/MT [66] (Price of Oleum = \$400/MT[71])

No. of Stream days = 330 days/yr

Total Production of H_2SO_4 = 100 MTPD

Total Production of Oleum = 9.09 MTPD

Total Sales = \$11759880

Daily Energy production = 55588.15958 kWh

Energy Sales per year = \$1511553 [72]

Revenue = \$19271433

Total Investment, TCI = \$17905347

Total Production Cost (TPC) = \$8419634

Total Income per year = Revenue – TPC = \$4851800

Fixed Capital Investment, FCI = \$15,219,545.32

Total Land area = 35000 m^2 (8.65 acres)

Land cost = \$2,800,000 [73]

Salvage Value = 10% of (FCI – Land) = \$1,241,945.53

Useful life = 20 years

Depreciation = $\frac{(FCI - \text{Salvage})}{\text{Useful Life}} = \$1558,879.54$

Tax rate = 27.05% [74]

Net Profit after taxation = Total Income per year – Taxes = \$3517554

Net cash flow = Net Profit after taxation + Depreciation = \$4,076,434.01

13.5 Feasibility Analysis
13.6 Cash Flow Diagram

MARR, $i = 15\%$

$$\begin{aligned}
 PW &= TCI + A (P/A, 15\%, 20) + (S+L) (P/F, 15\%, 20) \\
 &= -17,905,347.44 + 4,076,434.01 (P/A, 15\%, 20) + (1,241,945.53+2,800,000) (P/F, 15\%, 20) \\
 &= \$7,857,368.78
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 FW &= TCI (F/P, 15\%, 20) + A (F/A, 15\%, 20) + (S+L) \\
 &= -17,905,347.44 (F/P, 15\%, 20) + 4,076,434.01 (F/A, 15\%, 20) + (1,241,945.53+2,800,000) \\
 &= \$128,597,920.01
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 AW &= TCI (A/P, 15\%, 20) + A + (S+L) (A/F, 15\%, 20) \\
 &= -17,905,347.44 (A/P, 15\%, 20) + 4,076,434.01 + (1,241,945.53+2,800,000) (A/F, 15\%, 20) \\
 &= \$1,255,304.79
 \end{aligned}$$

As $PW, FW, AW > 0$, the project is considered as feasible.

Internal rate of return analysis

MARR = 15%

IRR calculation by PW method,

PW (i' %) = 0

Or, TCI + A (P/A, i' %, 20) + (S+L) (P/F, i' %, 20) = 0

Or, $-17,905,347.44 + 4,076,434.01 \times \frac{(1+i')^{20}-1}{i'} + (1,241,945.53+2,800,000) (1+i')^{-20} = 0$

Or, $i' = 0.2246$ or $22.46\% > 15\%$

Calculating IRR using graphical method,

Table 66: Table for IRR determination.

Interest Rate (%)	Present Worth (million)	Interest Rate (%)	Present Worth (million)
5	34.42	22	0.35
6	30.11	23	(0.40)
7	26.32	24	(1.10)
8	22.98	25	(1.74)
9	20.03	26	(2.34)
10	17.40	27	(2.90)
11	15.06	28	(3.42)
12	12.96	29	(3.91)
13	11.08	30	(4.37)
14	9.39	31	(4.80)
15	7.86	32	(5.20)
16	6.47	33	(5.58)
17	5.21	34	(5.94)
18	4.06	35	(6.28)
19	3.01	36	(6.60)
20	2.05	37	(6.90)
21	1.17	38	(7.19)

Figure 75: Determination of IRR

From the figure, it is also found that the value of i for which PW is zero is 22.46%.

$IRR = 22.46\% > MARR$.

The project is feasible as IRR is greater than MARR.

ERR Analysis

Here,

$$I(F/P, i, 20) = A(F/A, 10\%, 20) + S$$

$$\text{Or, } i = 0.1711$$

So, $ERR = 17.11\% > MARR$.

The project is feasible as ERR is greater than MARR.

13.7 Payback period

Table 67: Table for payback period determination.

End of Year	Net Cash Flow	Cumulative PW of cash flow at i=0%	Cumulative PW of cash flow at i=15%
0	\$-17,905,347.44	\$-17,905,347.44	\$-17,905,347.44
1	\$4,076,434.01	\$-13,828,913.43	\$-14,360,622.21
2	\$4,076,434.01	\$-9,752,479.42	\$-11,278,252.46
3	\$4,076,434.01	\$-5,676,045.42	\$-8,597,930.93
4	\$4,076,434.01	\$-1,599,611.41	\$-6,267,216.55
5	\$4,076,434.01	\$2,476,822.59	\$-4,240,508.40
6	\$4,076,434.01	\$6,553,256.60	\$-2,478,153.49
7	\$4,076,434.01	\$10,629,690.60	\$-945,670.96
8	\$4,076,434.01	\$14,706,124.61	\$386,922.55
9	\$4,076,434.01	\$18,782,558.61	\$1,545,699.51
10	\$4,076,434.01	\$22,858,992.62	\$2,553,331.66
11	\$4,076,434.01	\$26,935,426.62	\$3,429,533.52
12	\$4,076,434.01	\$31,011,860.63	\$4,191,448.18
13	\$4,076,434.01	\$35,088,294.63	\$4,853,982.67
14	\$4,076,434.01	\$39,164,728.64	\$5,430,099.62
15	\$4,076,434.01	\$43,241,162.64	\$5,931,070.88
16	\$4,076,434.01	\$47,317,596.65	\$6,366,698.06
17	\$4,076,434.01	\$51,394,030.65	\$6,745,504.30
18	\$4,076,434.01	\$55,470,464.66	\$7,074,901.04
19	\$4,076,434.01	\$59,546,898.66	\$7,361,332.98
20	\$4,076,434.01	\$67,665,287.20	\$7,857,368.78

Figure 76: Determination of Payback period.

Simple payback period is at the end of 5 years

Discounted payback period is at the end of 8 years

13.7 Sensitivity Analysis Spider Plot

Figure 77: Spider Plot of sensitivity analysis.

The spider plot shows that the project's present worth is most sensitive to changes in annual net cash flow and total capital investment, as indicated by the steep slopes of their respective lines. An increase in annual net cash flow significantly improves the present worth, while higher capital investment sharply reduces it. MARR also has a noticeable inverse impact, though less pronounced compared to these two factors. In contrast, useful life has a moderate positive effect on present worth, showing gradual improvement as it increases. Salvage value exhibits minimal influence across the entire range, with a flat trend line.

The project shows no significant sensitivity to salvage value. However, it is sensitive to changes in MARR, useful life, total capital investment (TCI), and annual net cash flow within the specified range of percentage variations.

14. PROJECT SCHEDULING

14.1 Tasks and Their Duration

All the tasks to establish the plant can be categorized in 5 categories, shown on the following table. Buffer time is also added in the schedule.

Task Category	Task Title	Start Date	End Date	Duration (Months)
Conceptual Design & Feasibility	Site Selection & Environmental Audit	1-Jan-26	1-Feb-26	1
	Market Study	1-Feb-26	1-Mar-26	1
	Preliminary PFD	1-Mar-26	1-Apr-26	1
	Material & Energy Balances	1-Apr-26	1-Jun-26	2
Basic Engineering Design (BED)	Major Equipment Selection/Sizing	1-Jun-26	1-Sep-26	3
	P&ID Development	1-Sep-26	1-Dec-26	3
	Long Lead Item (LLI) Ordering	1-Dec-26	1-Jan-27	1
	Economics Assessment	1-Jan-27	1-Feb-27	1
	Buffer after Basic Engineering	1-Feb-27	15-Feb-27	0.5
Detailed Engineering Design	Piping & Layout Design	15-Feb-27	1-May-27	2.5
	Civil, Structural & Foundation Design	1-May-27	1-Oct-27	5
	Electrical & Automation Design	1-Oct-27	1-Jan-28	3
	Final Equipment Datasheets	1-Jan-28	1-Apr-28	3
	Buffer after Detailed Engineering	1-Apr-28	15-Apr-28	0.5
Procurement & Construction	Site Preparation & Earthwork	15-Apr-28	1-Jun-28	1.5
	Civil Construction	1-Jun-28	1-Sep-28	3
	Equipment Delivery	1-Aug-28	1-Jan-29	5
	Structural Steel Erection	1-Jan-29	1-Apr-29	3
	Equipment Installation	1-Apr-29	1-Jul-29	3

	Piping, Instrumentation & Electrical	1-Jul-29	1-Oct-29	3
	Buffer after Construction & Erection	1-Oct-29	1-Sep-29	-1
Commissioning & Startup	Hydrotesting & Inspection	1-Sep-29	1-Oct-29	1
	Pre-commissioning	1-Oct-29	1-Nov-29	1
	Startup & Trial Runs	1-Nov-29	1-Feb-30	3

14.2 Gantt Chart

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15. CONCLUSION

15.1 Conclusion

This project successfully developed the conceptual design of a 100 MTPD sulfuric acid production plant along with 9.09 MPTD oleum based on the Double Contact Double Absorption (DCDA) process. The selected process was found to be the most suitable due to its high sulfur conversion efficiency, low sulfur dioxide emissions and ability to produce high-purity sulfuric acid that meets industrial specifications.

A comprehensive market survey indicated a growing demand for sulfuric acid in Bangladesh, particularly in fertilizer, textile, chemical, and metal-processing industries. The proposed plant location at Dilarpur, Narsingdi was selected after evaluating raw material availability, transportation facilities, utility access, and proximity to major consumers. Sulfur, air, water and vanadium pentoxide catalyst were identified as the principal raw materials, with reliable supply sources available. The process design included the development of the Process Block Diagram (PBD), Process Flow Diagram (PFD), utility specifications and material balance calculations for a production capacity of 100 metric tons per day Sulfuric Acid.

Overall, the proposed plant is technically feasible and capable of supporting the increasing domestic demand for sulfuric acid while reducing dependence on imports. In addition, the production surplus offers opportunities for export and future industrial growth. The project demonstrates the practical application of chemical engineering design principles in developing a sustainable and economically attractive sulfuric acid manufacturing facility for Bangladesh.

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Matlab Code

```
%First Bed
clc
clear all
close all
%Data
D=5;%m
A=3.14*D^2/4;%m2
G=(304.6*(0.79*28+0.32*0.06+0.15*64)+152.3*(0.21*32+0.79*28))*1000/(A*3600);%g/m2s
CAouo=(304.6*0.15)*10^3/(A*3600);%mol/m2s

rb=550;%kg/m3
cp=1.046;%J/gK

T(1)=675+273;%K
f(1)=0;
z(1)=0;

n=((.65-0)/.01)+1;
R=1.98;
for i=1:n
    k1(i)=exp(12.07-31000/(R*T(i)));
    k2(i)=exp(22.75-53550/(R*T(i)));

    xso2(i)=(45.69-45.69*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xo2(i)=(50.263-22.845*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xso3(i)=45.69*f(i)/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xn2(i)=360.947/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
%reaction rate
    rm(i)=abs((k1(i)*xso2(i)*xo2(i)-k2(i)*xso3(i)*(xo2(i))^(1/2))/(xso2(i))^(1/2));

    f(i+1)=f(i)+0.01;
    %bed height
    z(i+1)=z(i)+CAouo*.01/(rm(i)*rb);%m
    %temperature
    T(i+1)=(CAouo*.01*4184*24.6+G*cp*T(i))/(G*cp+1.99*4184*10^-3*CAouo*0.01);%K
end

figure

% --- Plot ONLY temperature ---
plot(z, T, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2)
xlabel('Bed Depth (meter)')
ylabel('Temperature (K)')
title('Temperature and Conversion vs Bed Depth of First Bed')

grid off
```

```

box on
set(gca,'FontSize',11)

% --- Left axis limits ---
yl = ylim;

% --- Create right axis ---
yyaxis right
ylim(yl)
ylabel('Conversion (%)')

% --- Map temperature ticks to conversion ---
yyaxis left
yt = yticks;      % Temperature ticks

% Interpolate conversion corresponding to those temperatures
f_interp = interp1(T, f, yt, 'linear', 'extrap');

% Switch to right axis and relabel
yyaxis right
yticks(yt)
yticklabels(compose('%.3f', f_interp))

%Spreadsheet formation
T=T';
xo2=xo2';
xso2=xso2';
xso3=xso3';
xn2=xn2';
f=f';
rm=rm';
z=z';
Result=[T(1:i) xo2 xso2 xso3 xn2 f(1:i) z(1:i)];
%Confirmation
z(i)
T(i)-273

%Second Bed
clc
clear all
close all
%Data
D=5;%m
A=3.14*D^2/4;%m2
G=(304.6*(0.79*28+0.32*0.06+0.15*64)+152.3*(0.21*32+0.79*28))*1000/(A*3600);%g/m2s
CAouo=(304.6*0.15)*10^3/(A*3600);%mol/m2s

rb=550;%kg/m3
cp=1.046;%J/gK

T(1)=655+273;%K
f(1)=.65;
z(1)=0;

n=((.90-0.65)/.01)+1;

```

```

R=1.98;
for i=1:n
    k1(i)=exp(12.07-31000/(R*T(i)));
    k2(i)=exp(22.75-53550/(R*T(i)));

    xso2(i)=(45.69-45.69*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xo2(i)=(50-22.845*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xso3(i)=45.69*f(i)/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xn2(i)=360.947/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
%reaction rate
    rm(i)=- (k1(i)*xso2(i)*xo2(i)-k2(i)*xso3(i)*(xo2(i))^(1/2))/(xso2(i))^(1/2);

    f(i+1)=f(i)+0.01;
    %bed height
    z(i+1)=z(i)+CAouo*.01/(rm(i)*rb);%m
    %temperature
    T(i+1)=(CAouo*.01*4184*24.6+G*cp*T(i))/(G*cp+1.99*4184*10^-3*CAouo*0.01);%K
end

```

figure

```

% --- Plot ONLY temperature ---
plot(z, T, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2)
xlabel('Bed Depth (meter)')
ylabel('Temperature (°C)')
title('Temperature and Conversion vs Bed Depth of Second Bed')

grid off
box on
set(gca,'FontSize',11)

% --- Left axis limits ---
yl = ylim;

% --- Create right axis ---
yyaxis right
ylim(yl) % Same physical scale
ylabel('Conversion (%)')

% --- Map temperature ticks to conversion ---
yyaxis left
yt = yticks; % Temperature ticks

% Interpolate conversion corresponding to those temperatures
f_interp = interp1(T, f, yt, 'linear', 'extrap');

% Switch to right axis and relabel
yyaxis right
yticks(yt)
yticklabels(compose('%.3f', f_interp))

%Spreadsheet formation
T=T';
xo2=xo2';

```

```

xso2=xso2';
xso3=xso3';
xn2=xn2';
f=f';
rm=rm';
z=z';
Result=[T(1:i) xo2 xso2 xso3 xn2 f(1:i) z(1:i)];
%Confirmation
z(i)
T(i)-273

%Third Bed
clc
clear all
close all
%Data
D=5;%m
A=3.14*D^2/4;%m2
G=(304.6*(0.79*28+0.32*0.06+0.15*64)+152.3*(0.21*32+0.79*28))*1000/(A*3600);%g/m2s
CAouo=(304.6*0.15)*10^3/(A*3600);%mol/m2s

rb=50;%kg/m3
cp=1.046;%J/gK

T(1)=660+273;%K
f(1)=.9;
z(1)=0;

n=((.95-.90)/.01)+2;
R=1.98;
for i=1:n
    k1(i)=exp(12.07-31000/(R*T(i)));
    k2(i)=exp(22.75-53550/(R*T(i)));

    xso2(i)=(45.69-45.69*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xo2(i)=(50.263-22.845*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xso3(i)=45.69*f(i)/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xn2(i)=360.947/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
%reaction rate
    rm(i)=abs((k1(i)*xso2(i)*xo2(i)-k2(i)*xso3(i)*(xo2(i))^(1/2))/(xso2(i))^(1/2));

    f(i+1)=f(i)+0.01;
    %bed height
    z(i+1)=z(i)+CAouo*.01/(rm(i)*rb);%m
    %temperature
    T(i+1)=(CAouo*.01*4184*24.6+G*cp*T(i))/(G*cp+1.99*4184*10^-3*CAouo*0.01);%K
end

figure

% --- Plot ONLY temperature ---
plot(z, T, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2)
xlabel('Bed Depth (meter)')

```

```

ylabel('Temperature (°C)')
title('Temperature and Conversion vs Bed Depth of Third Bed')

grid off
box on
set(gca,'FontSize',11)

% --- Left axis limits ---
yl = ylim;

% --- Create right axis ---
yyaxis right
ylim(yl)          % Same physical scale
ylabel('Conversion (%)')

% --- Map temperature ticks to conversion ---
yyaxis left
yt = yticks;      % Temperature ticks

% Interpolate conversion corresponding to those temperatures
f_interp = interp1(T, f, yt, 'linear', 'extrap');

% Switch to right axis and relabel
yyaxis right
yticks(yt)
yticklabels(compose('%.3f', f_interp))

%Spreadsheet formation
T=T';
xo2=xo2';
xso2=xso2';
xso3=xso3';
xn2=xn2';
f=f';
rm=rm';
z=z';
Result=[T(1:i) xo2 xso2 xso3 xn2 f(1:i) z(1:i)];
%Confirmation
z(i)
T(i)-273

%Fourth Bed
clc
clear all
close all
%Data
D=5;%m
A=3.14*D^2/4;%m2
G=(304.6*(0.79*28+0.32*0.06+0.15*64)+152.3*(0.21*32+0.79*28))*1000/(A*3600);%g/m2s
CAouo=(304.6*0.15)*10^3/(A*3600);%mol/m2s

rb=550;%kg/m3
cp=1.046;%J/gK

```

```

T(1)=575+273;%K
f(1)=.95;
z(1)=0;

n=-((.95-0.99)/.01)+1;
R=1.98;
for i=1:n
    k1(i)=exp(12.07-31000/(R*T(i)));
    k2(i)=exp(22.75-53550/(R*T(i)));

    xso2(i)=(45.69-45.69*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xo2(i)=(50.263-22.845*f(i))/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xso3(i)=45.69*f(i)/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
    xn2(i)=360.947/(456.9-22.845*f(i));
%reaction rate
    rm(i)=abs((k1(i)*xso2(i)*xo2(i)-k2(i)*xso3(i)*(xo2(i))^(1/2))/(xso2(i))^(1/2));

    f(i+1)=f(i)+0.01;
    %bed height
    z(i+1)=z(i)+CAouo*.01/(rm(i)*rb);%m
    %temperature
    T(i+1)=(CAouo*.01*4184*24.6+G*cp*T(i))/(G*cp+1.99*4184*10^-3*CAouo*0.01);%K
end

```

figure

```

% --- Plot ONLY temperature ---
plot(z, T, 'b-', 'LineWidth', 2)
xlabel('Bed Depth (meter)')
ylabel('Temperature (°C)')
title('Temperature and Conversion vs Bed Depth of Fourth Bed')

grid off
box on
set(gca, 'FontSize', 11)

% --- Left axis limits ---
yl = ylim;

% --- Create right axis ---
yyaxis right
ylim(yl) % Same physical scale
ylabel('Conversion (%)')

% --- Map temperature ticks to conversion ---
yyaxis left
yt = yticks; % Temperature ticks

% Interpolate conversion corresponding to those temperatures
f_interp = interp1(T, f, yt, 'linear', 'extrap');

% Switch to right axis and relabel
yyaxis right

```

```
yticks(yt)
yticklabels(compose('%.3f', f_interp))

%Spreadsheet formation
T=T';
xo2=xo2';
xso2=xso2';
xso3=xso3';
xn2=xn2';
f=f';
rm=rm';
z=z';
Result=[T(1:i) xo2 xso2 xso3 xn2 f(1:i) z(1:i)];
%Confirmation
z(i)
T(i)-273
```

Appendix B: Relation Between Temperature, Conversion and Bed height of Each Bed

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Workload Distribution

Name	Contribution	Individual Equipment	Signature
Tanjila Bahar Lubna (2002072)	Product Specifications; Uses and Applications of Sulfuric Acid; Bangladesh and Global Perspectives; Climate and Meteorological Conditions; PFD Preparation; Material Balance typing; Energy Balance calculations of heat exchangers; Heat Exchangers Sizing; Mechanical Design and P&ID of HE-102; HAZOP Study of HE-102; Environmental impact assessment and mitigation measures; Economic Cost Collection.	HE-102	
Md. Rayhan (2002095)	Raw Material Specifications and Sources, Future Prospects of H ₂ SO ₄ Market, Market Price Trend, Different Processes, PFD Labeling, Material balance typing, stream tables preparation, All Energy Balance typing, Listing and Sizing of Tanks, Mechanical Design and P&ID of Air Drying Tower, HAZOP Analysis of D-101, Environmental impact assessment and mitigation plan, Equipment cost finding and Formatting.	D-101	
Tahzib Rayhan Himadry (2002110)	Distribution of Customers and Seasonal Variations in Demand, Product Specification of Sulfuric Acid, Utilities and Sources, Geological data and utility, PFD Preparation, Material Balance of 4 bed converter, Furnace and Intermediate Absorption Tower, Final MB Table Preparation, Energy Balance of Heat Exchangers, 4 Bed Converter, Final EB Table Preparation, Listing and sizing of 4 Bed Converter and Oleum Dilution tank, Detailed design of 4 Bed Converter, P&ID drawing and HAZOP Analysis of 4 Bed Converter, Plant Layout Preparation, Pump cost calculations, Plant Scheduling Preparation, Referencing and Overall formatting.	4 Bed Converter B-101	
Esmot Jahan (2002118)	Justification of the Production and Production capacity; Selection and Justification of the Process; Rough Estimation of Gross Profit and feasibility analysis; Detailed Description of the full Process; PBD Preparation; All Material Balance calculations and writings; Final MB table preparation; Energy Balance of Intermediate absorption Tower, Final Absorption Tower, Oleum Dilution tank, Air drying tower and Heat Exchangers along with writings; Listing and sizing of Intermediate absorption Tower, Final Absorption Tower, Oleum dilution tank, Air drying tower and Heat Exchangers; Detailed mechanical design and P&ID drawing of Intermediate Absorption Tower (B-102); HAZOP Analysis of B-102; Environmental impact assessment and mitigation measures; Full Economic Analysis along with Feasibility analysis and Sensitivity analysis; Overall Formatting.	Intermediate Absorption Tower B-102	

Marking Scheme for the final report

Group No. B12

Name of the Examiner:

Total Marks: 60

Elements	Marks	
Project definition (2)		
Design Basis (2)		
Selection of the process and process description (2)		
Block Diagram of the Plant (PBD) (2)		
Process Flow diagram (PFD) (4)		
Material, Energy and Utility Balance (10)		
Basic Engineering Design (Sizing) (6)		
Detailed Engineering Design (Individual) (12) PID (4)	2002072	
	2002095	
	2002110	
	2002118	
HAZOP Study (4)		
Plot Plan and Equipment layout (2)		
Economic Analyses (6)		
Environmental Impact (2)		
Project Scheduling (2)		
Total (60)	2002072	
	2002095	
	2002110	
	2002118	

